

RURITAGE

Heritage for Rural Regeneration

Role Model Regeneration Enhancement Report

Deliverable 3.5

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2. Background Information

Table 1: technical Information

Project Full title	Rural regeneration through systemic heritage-led strategies	
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Table 2: Revision History

D	Deliverable
WP	Work Package
M	Month
RHH	Rural Heritage Hub
RM	Role Model
R	Replicator
SIA	Systemic Innovation Area
CNH	Cultural and Natural Heritage
CHMP	Community based Heritage Management and Planning
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
DRHH	Digital Rural Heritage Hub
C	Challenges
O	Objectives
SC	Steering Committee

3. Executive Summary

The RURITAGE Role Models represent thirteen tremendously diverse rural areas across Europe and beyond. By working on the 6 identified Systemic Innovation Areas (SIAs) – Pilgrimage, Local Food, Migration, Art&Festival, Resilience, Landscape – Role Models (RMs) have been selected as good practices in heritage-led rural regeneration and have been studied in WP1 to extract the so called ‘Role Model Actions’ (Del 1.1) and ‘Lessons Learned’ (Del 1.2). While the knowledge generated has been used by Replicators in the development of their own heritage-led regeneration strategies (Del 3.4) and is now in the phase of being summarized in the RURITAGE Decision Support System and Replication Toolbox in WP5, from M24 Role Models have been working on the co-development of their enhancement plans. The assumption behind this work is that sustainable growth isn’t a final state but a process, and represents a continuous tension towards the further regeneration of the local territories.

As Replicators, RMs established their RHH at the beginning of the project identifying a physical place and working on reinforcing the local community of stakeholders active of heritage-led regeneration (Del 3.1). This work started with the implementation of the so-called practices repository that have been implemented within WP1 and have been by RMs to discuss and validate the practices that have been identified in their territories in Task 1.1.

The establishment of Rural Heritage Hub in RMs facilitated the discussion with their stakeholders that, thanks to the multilevel and multidirectional knowledge exchange implemented in WP2, and using the RURITAGE workshop (Task 2.1) and tools (WP5), have been asked to work on the reinforcement of their heritage-led strategies, towards the enhancement of their own model actions and SIAs or through the development of new actions, touching upon other SIAs. From the beginning of the project, RMs have had the possibility of fostering the knowledge on their own territory and learning from the knowledge of the other RURITAGE partners.

The Enhancement plans have been co-developed by RMs together with their stakeholders from M24 (May 2020) to M36 (May 2021). The co-development phase foresaw the implementation of various workshops within the RHHs following a simplified version of the process described in the Community-based Heritage Management and Planning (CHMP) (Del 2.1). During the co-development phase, RMs are benefitting from other RMs, Rs and KFPs knowledge through the learning and mentoring visits (WP2), the Digital Rural Heritage Hub (WP2), the RURITAGE webinars (WP2) and through the Systemic Innovation Board and other project meetings (WP8).

Unfortunately, the co-development phase was implemented during several local lockdowns and restrictions due to the COVID-19 pandemic affecting RMs countries. This condition led to the adaptation of many activities that moved online, have been edited or canceled. Nevertheless, most of RMs did manage to keep an efficient and smooth collaboration with local stakeholders and resulted even more motivated to keep working on their enhancement plans. The challenges presented by the actual crisis, such as rising unemployment, civic disengagement, and greater challenges for more vulnerable groups added to the threats already present in rural areas. Nevertheless, the COVID-19 pandemic has also raised important opportunities for rural areas that have been discussed within the RURITAGE consortium (see Del 7.5) and that supported RMS in developing their enhancement plans. For all these reasons, after careful consideration with the coordinator and the EU Commission Project Officer, RMs have obtained to enlarge the duration of Task 3.4 to be able to implement their Enhancement plans during the project implementation.

The Role Models have developed a total of 51 actions, touching upon all the 6 SIAs. Although each Role Model was initially recognised as a “good practice” within one main SIA, all the Role Models included several SIAs as driver in their heritage-led strategy and action (24%, Landscape; 24% Local Food; 19% Pilgrimage; 16% Art&Festivals; 8% Resilience and 6% Migration). Similarly to the Replicators (see Del 3.4), RMs’ actions touch upon a wide spectrum of heritage. 51% of the actions included in the 13 Role Model plans addressed intangible heritage, while 39% are related with tangible and 10% with digital heritage. Notably they follow a similar trend of Rs actions (58% intangible heritage, 36% tangible heritage and 6% digital heritage), with a small increase related with Digital heritage based actions, probably related with the increasing role of this type of heritage due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

This report summarizes the results of the co-development phase in Role Models (Task 3.4). During this phase, RURITAGE RMs have developed their Enhancement plans and specific actions together with their local community. These actions will be co-implemented from May 2021. Specific objectives of this report are:

- Present the establishment of the RMs Rural Heritage Hub, in terms of their physical space and the community involved in the RURITAGE project.
- Summarize the co-development phase that took place in each RHH, to report on the participation of local stakeholders and community in the development of the Rms Enhancement plans .
- Present the RMs enhancement plans, providing details about objectives, challenges and actions of each RURITAGE RM.

This Deliverable presents in detail all the steps that led to the development of the RMs Enhancement plans and specifically:

- Section 4 states the specific objectives of this document.
- Section 5.1 describes the set up, launch and implementation of the activities within the RHHs, while Section 5.2 sums up the information concerning the main stakeholders involved in each RHHs.
- Section 6 provides a brief overview of RMs enhancement actions, analyzing the type of heritage they have been using and the SIAs they have been referring to.

Section 8 details all the Enhancement plans of the 13 RMs of the RURITAGE projects, including the presentation of their RHHs, the definition of the challenges and related objectives that the plan would like to reach and the full operational programme. The operational programme details the actions that the RMs will implement in the next year.

4. Overview of the RMs Rural Heritage Hubs: main activities and stakeholders' involved

4.1 Launch of the RHH and co-development phase events

Within each RURITAGE RM area, RMs had to set their Rural Heritage Hubs (RHH).

On the one side, RHHs is the physical meeting place to investigate and further boost the social innovation potential related with heritage in a participatory and co-creation process. On the other side, they are also at the core of the capacity building and mutual learning approach, ensuring knowledge and skills transference from RMs to the RURITAGE Replicators (Rs) and between RMs. The RMs RHH include stakeholders that contributed to the development and the implementation of local strategies identified and analyzed in WP1. To further contribute to foster and secure citizen's engagement and ownership of culture heritage, RMs have been then asked to keep working with their local stakeholders to identify new actions to enhance their heritage-led regeneration. While RMs have been extensively presented in Del 1.1; in Table 1 we here report the list of RMs and the relevant SIAs they had been selected for.

	RM1 - CAMINO DE SANTIAGO-WAY OF SAINT JAMES, Spain (FSMLRPH)
	RM2 - MARIA UT-MARY'S WAY, Romania (ProEDU, HCC)
	RM3 - PRESERVING OLD TRADITIONS FOR INNOVATING AGRO-FOOD PRODUCTION IN APULIA, Italy (DARE)
	RM4 - COFFEE PRODUCTION IN WORLD HERITAGE LANDSCAPE, Colombia (FCM)
	RM5 - MIGRANTS HOSPITALITY AND INTEGRATION IN ASTI PROVINCE, Italy (PIAM)
	RM6 - BOOSTING MIGRANT INTEGRATION WITH NATURE IN LESVOS ISLAND, Greece (NHMLPF)
	RM7 - DISCOVERING AND MAKING PROFESSIONAL PERFORMING ARTS ACCESSIBLE TO RURAL COMMUNITIES LIVING IN VILLAGES AND SMALL TOWNS, SOMERSET, United Kingdom (TakeArt)
	RM8 - THE LIVING VILLAGE OF THE MIDDLE AGE, VISEGRAD, Hungary (VVO, EMI)
	RM9 - TEACHING CULTURE FOR LEARNING RESILIENCE IN CRETE, Greece (UOC)
	RM10 - NATURAL HAZARDS AS INTANGIBLE CNH FOR HUMAN RESILIENCE IN SOUTH ICELAND, Iceland (Katla)
	RM11 - A CNH-LED APPROACH IN AUSTRÁTT MANORIAL LANDSCAPE (NMBU)
	RM12 - DOURO CULTURAL LANDSCAPE, DRIVER FOR ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT, Spain (AEICE)
	RM13 - THE NORTHERN HEADLANDS AREA OF IRELAND'S WILD ATLANTIC WAY, Ireland (WESTBIC)

Table 3: A summary of all RURITAGE RMs.

As it happened for Rs, RMs first worked on the activation of the RHH, identifying suitable spaces and engaging local stakeholders and then worked together with their stakeholders in co-development activities to define their enhancement actions.

This process foreseen two different phases: the RHH set up and the co-development phase.

To RHH set up, included two main types of events for Role Models:

- the **Practices Repository workshop**, to tailor the practices identified in WP1 and agreeing with the stakeholders on the results of that process;
- the official **launch of the RHH**, one opening event aimed at involving not only key stakeholders but all local residents.

The co-development phase for Role Models consisted in the identification of additional workshops to run, to involve their stakeholders in the analysis of the current situation, and the identification of main challenges and needs to be then addressed by the enhancement plan:

- the participatory workshop – as described in Del 2.1. The **participatory workshop**, aimed at picking out a list of actions to be included in the Enhancement plan to further foster rural regeneration in RMs' areas

- an elective an **elective workshop** to be chosen among the ones already included in the Deliverable 2.1 and proved to be successful for Rs (i.e., the serious game workshop, the business model workshop, the round table with key stakeholders)

As for the first two workshops, specific guidelines for RMs have been developed, starting from the ones available for the Rs. Due to the need of organising such workshops in 2020, the guidelines have been adapted to embed tips and remote working modalities to keep working while facing the Covid-19 pandemic.

Setting up the Rural Heritage Hubs

Practices Repository workshop

The practices repository workshop was held in all RMs in the first semester of 2019. The aim of the workshop was to present, discuss and agree on identified best practices from WP1 in the RM's area to better understand key success factors and encountered difficulties and to further enhance cultural heritage ownership of local stakeholders. Stakeholders involved in those practices were invited to gain from them insights on the process, barriers faced, and solutions encountered. More than 200 participants were involved in this specific workshop across the Role Models.

Launch of the Rural Heritage Hub (RHH)

The primary objective of the launch of the hub has been to officially launch the RURITAGE Hub space and gather additional stakeholders to take part in the coming Hub activities. Similarly to what happened in Replicators (see Deliverable 3.4), this activity, conceived as an open public event, contributed to disseminate the RURITAGE project, and to present the further activities to be organised in the Hubs. More than 320 participants were involved in the launch of the RHH across the Role Models.

Figure 1: The launch of the RHH at RM1. Photo courtesy of FSMLRPH.

Since the second half of 2019, while conducting bilateral knowledge transfer activities with Rs and other RMs (Task 2.4) and contributing to the success of the multilevel and multidirectional knowledge workshops (Deliverable 2.4), thanks also to the active involvement of the Role Models in the Digital RHH and the webinars (Task 2.5), they started to implement tailored activities in their RHHs to further enhance their heritage-led strategies, working both on their reference SIA and on additional SIAs other than the one they represent in the project.

The co-development phase in RMs

Figure 2: The participatory workshop organised of PIAM. Photo courtesy of PIAM.

Participatory workshop

This workshop aimed at entering into the core of the co-development phase of the RMs' enhancement plans. By using playing cards to exploit the knowledge and model actions already included in Deliverables 1.1 and 1.2, it consisted in a participated workshop where stakeholders used RURITAGE cards to discuss potential actions for the Enhancement plan coming either from other RURITAGE RMs, or from the RURITAGE covid-19 resilience in practice collection. The main outcomes have been the selection of the main actions as the more relevant by local stakeholders, and the definition of new practices and ideas coming from the stakeholders. More than 360 participants were involved in the participatory workshop across the Role Models, therefore contributing to the identification of the actions to be included in the Enhancement Plans.

Round table with key stakeholder – the elective workshop

Due to covid-19 pandemic, the most effective and easy-to-organise workshop was the round table with key stakeholders.

Figure 3: Many meetings moved online. Here is one of KATLA's roundtable meetings with stakeholders. Photo courtesy by KATLA.

The general objective of the round tables with local stakeholders has been to define and detail the activities necessary to carry out the actions of the enhancement strategies. After the participatory workshop, RMs have selected the actions to be included in their Enhancement Plan. The round tables with key stakeholders helped in carefully detail how to co-implement the actions in close collaboration with stakeholders and supported by KFPs and other RMs and Rs. More than 70 participants were involved in the round tables. Due to COVID-19 restrictions, not all the Role Models managed to organised this workshop, while others decided to organise more than one session, to work with smaller groups and increase the number of interactions among stakeholders.

4.2 Stakeholders engagement and participation

In order to simplify, this section only describes the stakeholder participation in each RHH in terms of number of participants, gender balance, and type of stakeholders, which is important to be analysed based on the RM’s SIA of interest. A more thorough analysis, involving a wider range of indicators, will be performed and presented in Deliverable D3.6 “Report on the involvement of communities in cultural heritage”.

The following graph summarizes the number of participants of the activities organized in each RM’s RHH, as well as gender information about the different participants, while a short summary paragraph has been developed to detail the type of stakeholders participation in each RM RHH. The number of events organized by RMs differs from case to case because of difficulties in organizing all events due to COVID-19 related restrictions, despite some being organized on-line, as well as their specific needs, as some RMs managed to successfully develop the Enhancement plans in fewer events.

Graph 1. An overview of the number of participants of the activities organized in each RM’s RHH.

- RM1 - CAMINO DE SANTIAGO-WAY OF SAINT JAMES (FSMLRPH)**
 More than 80 stakeholders participated (32% females and 68% males) in the hub activities where, as expected, higher participation is appreciated in the Repository and Launch events. Among the type of stakeholders engaged, these include representatives of the regional CyL government (Tourism, and Heritage areas), provincial and local governments (mayors or councilmen), the Catholic Church (parish

priests), tourism development agents and technicians, Local Action Groups, civil associations around the Santiago Way, museums, Foundation dedicated to disabled people, NGO entities working for rural development, private hostels for pilgrims, researchers, professionals and other entrepreneurs.

- **RM2 - MARIA UT-MARY'S WAY (ProEDU, HCC)**
Participation reached around 130 stakeholders (59% females and 41% males), peaking at the Launch event, but being also high at the Participatory workshop. These stakeholders included local network organisations, local investors, pilgrims, volunteers, employees of partner institutions of Harghita City Council, Pro EDU and Szent, representatives of local and regional authorities, Miercurea Ciuc, Gellért Foundation, youth organisations, regional coordinators of Via Mariae, tourism organisations, local institutions and civil organisations.
- **RM3 - PRESERVING OLD TRADITIONS FOR INNOVATING AGRO-FOOD PRODUCTION IN APULIA (DARE)**
Approximately 60 stakeholders participated in DARE's RHH activities (59% females and 41% males) being, as expected, higher at the Repository and Launch event that were organized at the same time. Among the participating stakeholders, these include representatives of universities and research centres, policy makers of European Parliament, regional government, local municipality, journalists, local stakeholder of food system, food producers, rural innovation hub Vazzap, architecture and design company DDUM, erasmus students, and other stakeholders.
- **RM4 - COFFEE PRODUCTION IN WORLD HERITAGE LANDSCAPE (FCM)**
In FCM's case, only the Repository and Launch events were delivered, as the rest will happen during the co-implementation phase. So far, around 30 participants (47% females and 53% males) have been engaged: representatives from the Association of municipalities of the coffee cultural landscape (director), farmers of different municipalities, leaders of Communal Action, Salento's and Argelia's local government..
- **RM5 - MIGRANTS HOSPITALITY AND INTEGRATION IN ASTI PROVINCE (PIAM)**
PIAM managed to involve about 150 stakeholders (45% females and 55% males) in their activities, being specially high in the Participatory workshop. Among these, there were representatives of the Municipality of Chiusano d'Asti, Municipality of Castellero, National Sport Association for mountain hiking UISP Montagna, Bewood Outdoor Brigade Association, ARGO Cooperative, Agricoltura Indigena, citizens, and other local public and private entities.
- **RM6 - BOOSTING MIGRANT INTEGRATION WITH NATURE IN LESVOS ISLAND (NHMLPF)**
Likewise, NHMLPF saw higher participation numbers during the Participatory workshop in comparison to the rest of events, with an overall engagement of 150 stakeholders (46% females and 54% males): representatives of regional and local governing bodies, Northern Aegean Region, Municipality of Lesvos, Ephorate of Antiquities of Lesvos, University of the Aegean, primary and secondary education schools, Lesvos Chamber, Lesvos, and associations (Tour guide association, Lesvos Hoteliers Association, Molyvos, Eressos, Plomari and Kalloni Tourism Associations, etc.), and, travel agents, professionals and companies in the tourism sector (Lesvos Alternative Sailing, Lesvos Ride, Lesvos Diving Center, and Nisiopi Marine Park), professionals in the cultural sector, ICOM Hellenic National Committee, art galleries and archaeological museums (Archaeological Collection of Eressos, etc.), cultural organisations and networks, etc.
- **RM7 - DISCOVERING AND MAKING PROFESSIONAL PERFORMING ARTS ACCESSIBLE TO RURAL COMMUNITIES LIVING IN VILLAGES AND SMALL TOWNS, SOMERSET (TakeArt)**
TakeArt reached a fairly stable engagement throughout the co-development phase (despite the expected peak in the Launch event). On average, more than 50 people (53% female and 47% male) participated in their activities, including representatives of local government, economic development, local food system

(local food producers, suppliers, etc.), rural touring, education, art venues, community organizations, voluntary sector, art promoters, performers, and activists, heritage/museums and health services.

- **RM8 - THE LIVING VILLAGE OF THE MIDDLE AGE, VISEGRAD (VVO, EMI)**

In the same way, RM8 experienced a stable participation with higher numbers in the Launch event, counting for over 170 stakeholders (49% females and 51% males). The type of stakeholders involved were representatives from cultural organisations, service providers, environmental organisations, TDM Visegrád (Visegrád Tourist Association), participants of the Palace Games, local government (Municipality of Visegrád), local restaurants, graphic artists, regional TV/media, local and regional companies, institutions and organizations (Pro Visegrád Nonprofit Ltd, Visegrád Tours Ltd., St. George Order of Knights, Hotel Silvanus Visegrád, Hotel Visegrád, King Matthias Community Centre, etc.), advisors and local citizens.

- **RM9 - TEACHING CULTURE FOR LEARNING RESILIENCE IN CRETE (UOC)**

The participation in UoC's RHH activities were fairly stable throughout the process, having almost 60 stakeholders participating (49% females and 51% males), including representatives of local authorities (Rethimnon, Malevisi, Amari and Mylopotamos municipalities, mayors and deputy mayors), development agency AKOMM, environmental education centre Anogia, social cooperative enterprises, Friends of Amari Cultural Association, Damasta Cultural Associations, a local community development agency, archaeological museum, citizens, journalists, cultural associations (Androidus project, etc.), local participatory social company NIDEA, tourism companies (Wild Nature Travel, etc.), and event organizers (Psiloritis Race).

- **RM10 - NATURAL HAZARDS AS INTANGIBLE CNH FOR HUMAN RESILIENCE IN SOUTH ICELAND (Katla)**

In Katla's case, around 120 people was engaged in their hub activities (63% females and 37% males). Interestingly, participation was the highest in the second elective workshop, the Raound-tables, as 3 separate sessions were organized. Overall, the type of stakeholders taking part in the activities were the Katla Geopark and center representatives, rangers from the western part of Vatnajökull national-park, Department of civil protection and emergency management, planning and building inspector, president of the municipal council, local food companies, local buisness owner/manager (Lava show, etc.), University center of south Iceland, citizens, museums (Skógasafn, etc.), and the cultural heritage agency of Iceland.

- **RM11 - A CNH-LED APPROACH IN AUSTRÅTT MANORIAL LANDSCAPE (NMBU)**

As for NMBU, around 80 participants were engaged (*gender balanced cannot be determined due to lack of data*), which include representatives from the tourism industry, municipalities, local food production sector, local and regional agricultural offices, local government, Trøndelag Regional church, National pilgrimage office Norway, farmers, landowners, citizens, etc.

- **RM12 - DOURO CULTURAL LANDSCAPE, DRIVER FOR ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT (AEICE)**

AEICE reached a fairly stable participation of about 120 stakeholders (34% females and 66% males) during its RHH activities. These stakeholders include, among other, partners of the Douro initiative, municipalities, provincial government, regional government, companies in the habitat sector (rehabilitation, architectural studies), consultancy firms (technology, environment, marketing, communication agencies, etc.), companies in the tourism sector (inbound tourism agencies, travel agencies, hotel accommodation), technology centres, non-profit organisations, service consultancy, university, public foundations, tourist office, tourism services, wine routes/wineries, cultural and creative industry companies, health and nature tourism, local food producers and media.

- **RM13 - THE NORTHERN HEADLANDS AREA OF IRELAND'S WILD ATLANTIC WAY (WESTBIC)**

WESTBIC, with a steady participation except for the Launch event, managed to engage around 50

stakeholders (41% females and 59% males). These were, mainly, representatives of local community development companies and agencies (Coiste Forbartha na Carraige, Lár Chomhairle Paróiste Gleann Cholm Cille, Kilcar Parish Council, etc.), Language Planning Office, Cultural and Language Institute (Oideas Gael), language support organisation “Glór na nGael”, local and regional authorities, Tourism Development Agency (Fáilte Ireland), Local Historical and Heritage group, Whiskey and Gin Distillery, knitwear and wool manufacturers, food and drink producers, creative design company, Signatory Discovery Point of Wild Atlantic Way, active tourism companies and guides, transport and accommodation providers, Restoration of Corn Mill Heritage Project, and citizens.

The engagement of above-mentioned stakeholders has followed a different path from RM to RM. In some cases, stakeholders’ and communities’ involvement took place from early stages of the RHH set-up and thus they participated in most activities, whereas in other cases, the engagement of specific groups of stakeholders occurred at later stages as new needs and interest in other SIAs were being identified and explored along the co-development phase. In addition, it is worth mentioning that, although not all stakeholders were directly involved in the development of the Enhancement plans and will not be in their implementation, their contribution and role in the final result is also considered very relevant.

5. Overview of the RMs enhancement actions and relation with the COVID-19 pandemic

The Enhancement plans presented below will support the Role Model communities in further strengthening and developing their local sustainably through Cultural and Natural Heritage. According to the European framework for Action on Cultural Heritage (2018), there is an urgent need for emphasizing the value and potential of cultural heritage as a resource for sustainable growth and quality of life in a constantly evolving society. The European Framework for Action on Cultural Heritage looks at the tangible, intangible and digital dimensions of cultural heritage as inseparable and interconnected. As stated in Del 3.4, the understanding of tangible, intangible and digital heritage within the RURITAGE Enhancement plans is in accordance to the UNESCO definitions. Tangible heritage is the physical leavings of previous generations as well as the concrete of new, including built and natural heritage, tangible artefacts and archaeological leavings. The intangible heritage related actions include traditions, inherited and living, that has shaped and is shaping communities. Learning, knowledge and heritage ownership and awareness are among the focus of the heritage-led regeneration plans. Beyond this, RURITAGE recognizes digital heritage as an important tool for the sustainable development of rural communities, for today and for the future.

The Role Models have developed a total of 51 actions. These actions touch upon a wide spectrum of heritage. As illustrated in Fig.4, 51% of the actions included in the 13 Role Model plans addressed intangible heritage, while 39% are related with tangible and 10% with Digital. More specifically, as detailed in the chart in Fig.5, the following heritage has been considered: - *Tangible Heritage*: 23% Natural Heritage, 14% Built Heritage and 11% Artefacts - *Intangible Heritage*: 33% Knowledge and practices, 22% Social practices Rituals and festive events, 3% Performing Arts, 4% Oral traditions, and 2% Traditional Craftmanship - *Digital Heritage* 6%.

Figure 4: Classification of the actions in the Role Model Enhancement plans according with the three overarching categories of heritage

Figure 5: Classification of the actions in the Role Model Enhancement plans according with a more detailed classification of intangible heritage.

Besides heritage definitions, Role Models built their actions on own experiences and through an active exchange of ideas across the project. They learnt from each other through the RURITAGE Good practices and Lessons learned, based on the RURITAGE paradigm constituted by the 6 identified Systemic Innovation Areas (SIAs)- Pilgrimage, Local Food, Migration, Art&Festival, Resilience, Landscape. Although each Role Model was initially recognised for developing successfully within one main SIA, all of the Role Models included several SIAs as driver in their heritage-led strategy and actions (Fig. 6). Each action is related and builds on one or more Systematic Innovation Areas, as summarized in Fig. 6, the most common referenced SIA, with 27%, was the Local Food SIA. It was closely followed by Landscape with 24% and Pilgrimage with 19%. 16% of all actions referred to Art&Festivals as their SIA. The least commonly used SIA's were Resilience (8%) and Migration (6%).

Figure 6: RURITAGE SIAs included in the RMs enhancement actions

Even though RMs were building on already established heritage-led strategies, previously demonstrated as key to rural regeneration (see deliverable 1.1 and 1.2), the pandemic crises that struck during the development of the Enhancement plan for RMs, may have influenced RMS in the development of their enhancement actions. In this context, the RURITAGE project launched a call for so-called ‘resilience practices’ aiming at collecting actions implemented in rural areas to cope with the COVID19 pandemic (available on the RURITAGE website: https://www.ruritage.eu/resources/resilience_actions/). Moreover, RURITAGE held an online workshop in May 2020 with all project partners to discuss challenges and opportunities for rural areas beyond the pandemic. The outcome of this process are summarized in various outcomes: i) Del 7.5 Thinking beyond the COVID-19 crisis: heritage-based opportunities for rural regeneration, ii) a brochure summarizing the outcomes of the deliverable (available on RURITAGE’s website [here](#)) and iii) a scientific publication titled ‘The Covid-19 pandemic effects in rural areas’¹.

The discussion that took place is partially reflected in the RMs Enhancement plans today. For the RMs there is a comparably higher number of Pilgrimage (19%: compared to Rs: 8%), Local Food (27% compared to 20%) and Art&Festivals (16% compared to Rs: 13%) related actions. These three SIAs were highlighted as some of the sectors that were connected with the greatest challenges, but also the greatest possibilities of re-development due to the COVID-19 pandemic. On one hand, the cultural and creative industries (found with the Art&Festivals SIA), farming and food distribution (Local Food SIA), and the tourism and travel sectors (related to the Pilgrimage SIA) were particularly hit hard by the crisis, but on the other hand they present the biggest opportunities for development.

If properly planned and managed, pilgrimage and hiking routes can be considered amongst the safest tourism destinations in the current Covid-19 crisis, thanks to the intrinsic nature of such activities that can easily adapt to the current imposed social distancing rules and that naturally take place in open-air natural environment, thus facilitating their adaptation to the current challenge. Big opportunities are raising both for internationally

¹ de Luca, C., Tondelli, S., & Åberg, H. (2020). The Covid-19 pandemic effects in rural areas. *TeMA - Journal of Land Use, Mobility and Environment*, 119-132. <https://doi.org/10.6092/1970-9870/6844>

recognized pilgrimage and hiking routes, that could redirect their targets towards family and domestic tourists, and also for smaller and less known places that can claim for the re-discovering of local cultural and natural heritage, involving rural communities into long-lasting regeneration process. This is clear as some of the RMs are digging into their cultural roots and three RMs (RM10, RM11, RM13) will through their actions re-establish forgotten Pilgrimage routes. In addition, one RM (RM5) is working in particular on historic hiking paths. According to the tendencies seen in the Pilgrimage SIA, deliverable 7.5 also identified a huge potential in the development of green infrastructure, wellness corridor, and slow mobility infrastructure that can on the one side improve and restore natural ecosystem, but at the same time creating options for sustainable tourism that is also in line with the Landscape SIA. In line with this, some partners found opportunities to connect pilgrimage to other nature-related activities – i.e. open-air sports, fishing, etc. – that will support market diversification increasing the potential number of visitors of the area. This is clear in the case of RM11 that are re-establishing the St Olov Way while connected it to local orchards and historic fruit varieties as a way to market their local identity.

Concerning Art&Festivals, many art related activities went online during the pandemic (see Resilience actions collection), and given the RMs actions it is clear that there is a need for tangible art experiences and social exchange as a result of isolation and social distancing. The RMs already discussed during the workshop in 2020 that the demand for arts would maybe increase and offer more frequent opportunities for artists to perform and for locals to take part in performances. It was suggested that there could possibility to develop more flexible “menus” of art and festivals for communities, adapting to local needs, conditions and practices, a more sustainable rural cultural exploration may emerge. This can be seen through the lens of the refugee that travels around Lesbos (RM6) to capture the local heritage with her camera, the poet that reads poems while delivering food boxes (RM7) or local arts that is performed directly in the fields (RM3). The latter two are also a splendid example of how to bring different SIAs together, combining arts and Local food (SIA). As RM7 themselves express in their Enhancement plans “a local food system should build community, biodiversity, healing, social justice and wellbeing. This can be made more visible, promoted and celebrated through the arts”. In line with this, deliverable 7.5 claim that the reinforcement of the local scene can possibly enhance the local sense of recognition and further on interest in heritage. The restrictions may even allow local artists to gain greater appreciation and therethrough, lead to a regeneration of the local art scene and provide a catalyst for creative grassroots projects where the outcome might be a social meeting place for locals which creates a sense of belonging and pride within the rural communities.

Just like the arts, Local Food SIA can be seen as an embodiment of local history and traditions and symbolizes the cultural heritage of a territory. During the pandemic, there was an increase and development of new types of business models based on sustainable food from deliveries to online workshops and events. Besides that the RMs Enhancement actions have a higher percentage of actions focused on Food than the Replicators (27% compared to Rs: 20%) the RMs are also proving new ways to capture and build synergies between food and other SIAs. Two RMs (RM7 and RM3) have focused on ways of bringing arts together with the Local Food SIA (see above), while others are building on ways to create synergies with Resilience SIA. Following this example, RMs are creating innovative ways to increase resilience and local knowledge on food production. During the workshop in May 2020 there was a recognized need of developing local capacity and skills towards digital tools for advertisement, logistic and e-products, local authorities and relevant stakeholders – small farmers and local producer associations. This could build upon this new trend to boost the capacity of local farmers through on online training and educational tools as well as interactive webinars to spread knowledge. Along these lines, RM3, RM4 and RM7 and RM4 have developed actions through establishment of webinars and digital courses aimed at local food producers.

Even though there was a low number of recognized resilience actions, it is noticeable that Resilience became a transversal attitude during the pandemic period and it is now embedded in most of other SIAs, that focus on capacity building (e.g. RM3, RM4, RM10), social cohesion (RM5, RM7, RM12), nature-based and sustainable tourism (e.g. RM1, RM2, RM11, RM12, RM13 form (undertourism, slow and domestic tourism). Just like it was a crucial part of the response to the Covid-19 pandemic to make sure that all members of society have the information they need to stay healthy, RMs have built on making more vital information beyond the pandemic accessible. For example, RM10 included an action that aims at translating information for advising the whole

community around potential natural hazards.

6. RM enhancement plans

This section is composed by the 13 RMs enhancement plans developed by RMs, detailing fro each of them:

- Background information (Rural Heritage Hub, The reference SIA, Other relevant SIAs)
- Starting point summarizing RMs actions previously identified by RURITAGE in WP1 and briefly summarizing the main outcomes of the co-development workshop undertaken in each RM
- Objectives of the enhancement plan
- List of enhancement actions
- Operational Programme detailed to implement the action

RMs and their local stakeholders demonstrated a great engagement in the phase of co-development and showed a great interest for the possibility of implementing them within the context of RURITAGE. Moreover, due to the COVID-19 pandemic restrictions and lockdown, most of RMs saved part of their budget (mostly coming from travel costs) that could potentially support them in financing part of their enhancement plans. This proposal was carefully taken into consideration by the coordinator that agreed that RMs could implement their Enhancement plans during the project implementation. Task 3.4 was then extended until the end of the project to leave time to RMs to implement their plans. As described in detail in the operational programme, each RM will indeed use part of the RURITAGE resources for the implementation of the actions, while, in most of the cases, they will be co-funded by the same RM or their local stakeholders. For this reason, while a full monitoring of the implementation of RMs actions is not foreseen within the project, RMs will submit a progress report every 6 months (M42 and M48) to report on the activities they have been implemented. RMs will also have the occasion to showcase the results of the implementation of their actions at the final conference in Paris in 2022.

6.1 RM1 French Santiago Way through Castilla & Leon (FSMLRPH) Enhancement plan

Figure 7: This photo was a part of the RURITAGE photo contest. Photographer: Margarita Campos Chorva.

6.1.1 Background

The French Camino de Santiago de Compostela is a thousand-year-old pilgrim route. Also known as the Way of St. James, which, since the 9th century, it has transformed the “finis terrae” city of Santiago de Compostela into a meeting place of Western faith and thinking. Tradition is still alive and the continent’s spirituality still looks towards Compostela, as shown by the last Holy Years, which will undoubtedly be the case in the Jubilee year of 2021.

Rural Heritage Hub

The Camino de Santiago RURITAGE Hub created as part of the RURITAGE Project has been physically established in the Spanish province of Palencia (Castilla y León Community) at the Real Monasterio de San Zoilo. This Monastery, located in the Carrion de los Condes is a great centre of refuge for pilgrims. It is considered part of the UNESCO’s Humanity Heritage associated to the French Camino de Santiago (ref. 669bis - 2015). Built in 948 and originally pertaining to the Cluny Congregation, this Romanesque Monastery has been turned into a renowned hotel.

The Camino de Santiago RURITAGE Hub has been officially launch in July 2019 with the intention to facilitate the gathering of different agents involved in the Camino who could be interested in expanding the learnings and activities put together by the RURITAGE project. Furthermore, the Hub will serve to raise awareness in local areas about the community benefits from the involvement in the RHH and thus in the RURITAGE project. The participation in the HUB will facilitate stressing out the importance that the promotion of cultural and natural heritage could generate in their areas (see communication messages developed by ICLEI), in particular:

1. Improve quality of life of the residents of rural areas.
2. Contribute to social inclusion, economic growth and environmental balance in rural areas.
3. Make rural areas more attractive for sustainable business development.

The RHH also involves different types of stakeholders including local action groups, technology and research centres, local entrepreneurs, local administrations, individual citizens, associations.

All partners represent different sectors involved with the Castilla and León Community portion of the French Camino de Santiago in Spain.

The HUB is constituted in the Monastery of San Zoilo, where a relevant stakeholder is located. The monastery is an historical building closely related to the history of the Camino and now it works as a private shelter for pilgrims. This is the main space agreed between the assistants to the constitution meeting. Anyway, as three provinces are involved, there was another agreement on making the meetings in some other places of the Camino to give relevance to all the stakeholders involved.

The Reference SIA

Figure 8: Map of The Camino de Santiago Francés (Source: commons.wikimedia.org)

Figure 9: Monasterio de San Zoilo (Source: commons.wikimedia.org)

PILGRIMAGE

Pilgrimage: The Camino de Santiago has proved to be a driver for sustainable and economic growth for rural areas by securing sustainability in travel and tourism. It is a must to help develop less explored areas maintaining the core values of the pilgrimage route. It's the SIA where we belong.

Other relevant SIAs

LOCAL FOOD

Sustainable Local Food Production: Food, wine and gastronomy, and their “alternative” networks, in many cases, help improve the economic and environmental sustainability of both tourism and agriculture in rural locations. These traditional and local offerings add to the symbolism and culture of the destination.

RESILIENCE

Resilience: The ability of human settlements to withstand and to recover quickly from external shocks in times of crisis (and let’s agree COVID-19 is one such economic crisis) by working in a coordinated way will help not only to reduce risks and damage but also the ability to quickly bounce back to a stable state. Our HUB can be a facilitating resource for helping build resilience in the rural communities around the Camino de Santiago.

LANDSCAPE

Integrated Landscape management: By developing a common space of work between private and public organizations, we can help protect, conserve, and maintain the natural heritage promoting sustainable and eco-friendly practices.

6.1.2 Starting point

Code	Role Model Action name	Objective
RM1.1	Promote a governance model with the involvement of public and private bodies	The union of resources to manage the Camino de Santiago at local, regional and national level, and to improve the involvement of society in general terms
RM1.2	Develop Heritage innovation as Monitoring Heritage System	Ensure conservation and protection of heritage located in dispersed and depopulation rural areas. Develop and apply new technologies and innovation around heritage
RM1.3	Form a tourism body with the specific charter for developing these resources and attracting tourism	Attract tourism to less developed regions and localities and support new, more sustainable forms of development
RM1.4	Promote the restoration of old or unused buildings to offer them as	Convert heritage into a cultural and tourist resource of the first order and improve the state of the one associated with the Camino de Santiago

	temples, shelters, hotels, restaurants and shops for pilgrims.	
RM1.5	Study and research the historic traces of the pilgrimage routes and the traditions related to them (in literature, historic maps, art, etc.)	Increase awareness and knowledge of the area and its heritage
RM1.6	Digitalization of the pilgrimage - through websites, GIS maps, apps	Facilitate knowledge and access to information about the Camino, its history, route and resources, as well as improving its dissemination
RM1.7	Foster training and employment: schools workshop and internships	Offer professional training in the restoration of heritage for unemployed youth, support for groups in search of job opportunities and cultural training for those interested in art and heritage
RM1.8	Support local farmers in offering their products to the pilgrims	Promote, within and outside the country, brands and companies of quality agricultural and food products as a means of promoting the territory, many of them in the Camino de Santiago itinerary.

As part of the on-going efforts to keep the Camino de Santiago HUB alive, and after the outcome of the workshop held July 2019 where a group of local partners has got together and defined a series of objectives. Out of those objectives, a new series of best practices were proposed to be developed further are described in the following list:

- Improve the digital transformation of the Camino de Santiago
- Involving foreign pilgrims to a greater extent in the management of the Camino
- Give greater importance to intangible aspects and ethnographic heritage
- Update and increase the offer of services for people with disabilities
- Facilitate the settlement of new settlers (repopulation of the territory)

The 2019 workshop made evident some important facts to take into consideration:

- The stakeholders' agreement about the enormous potential that the Camino de Santiago has as a social resource to be developed due to its capacity to agglutinate and attract interests, initiatives, and economic resources, especially for small towns.
- The willingness of the different stakeholders to engage in joint actions, although very different sensitivities and conceptions emerged.
- The key agreement that the spiritual, humankind and religious value of the Way that cannot be substituted solely by the tourist aspects. It is our task to facilitate their coexistence.
- The need to improve the existing traditional "best practices".
- Despite its success, the Way faces some complicated challenges. Especially the French Way in Castilla y León, being the oldest and most traditional and due to the characteristics of the territory, it faces new difficulties without having resolved some old traditional contradictions.

Specific comments made by members of the Hub have been:

- Concern about the loss of values and the essence of the Way.
- Doubts about the involvement and real benefit for local populations.
- Encouragement to continue participating in the Hub concept.
- Lack of coordination about a multiplicity of agents involved.
- Confidence of its value as a resource for territorial development and exceptional human experience with a great potential to promote.

Unfortunately, COVID-19 got in the way and it was not until today that we can present the outcome of the efforts so far.

6.1.3 Objectives of the enhancement plan

The main objective of the Plan is to try to maintain the HUB beyond the end of the project, in order to become a common place to join necessities with opportunities.

Opportunities and/or open issues to address	Specific objectives
<p>To define and publish the common values of Camino de Santiago as a key resource for the rest of the activities of the Enhancement Plan.</p>	<p>O1 Attain a common definition of the values that define Camino de Santiago</p> <p>Put together the values around the pilgrimage in Camino de Santiago.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of coordinated actions that focus on fostering the sense of ownership of young people in the territories. Lack of knowledge about opportunities related with organic farming, arts, built heritage restoration. Lack of interest from local businesses. Urban trend and the apparent lack of opportunities to rural youth. Administrative and economic difficulties 	<p>O2 Promote the implementation of the RURITAGE project to improve its knowledge to impacted organizations and individuals.</p> <p>Enhance the knowledge of the population around the concepts of Camino de Santiago. Increase the relationship of the population around Camino de Santiago with the Pilgrim. Improve the involvement of local population in the conservation of values and ideals of Camino de Santiago. Improve the comprehension of the Camino Values among the local enterprises.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish the basis of a good emergency plan which ensures coordination among the different agents involved. Lack of interest of national and local administrations. 	<p>O3 Make the Camino de Santiago more secure.</p> <p>Improve the coordination among different involved agents during emergencies. Communicate population and pilgrims the security aspects along Camino de Santiago.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Need to improve services such as eco-mobility, Wi-Fi connection, tourism services (hostels, bar & restaurants), signals, maps, radio, etc. Need to expand the offer, promoting eco-tourism: link the pilgrimage route to other activities. Costs of the infrastructure in areas with very low density of population and ageing people. Lack of local services and resources. 	<p>O4 Elaborate a map with the real status of connectivity along the Camino.</p> <p>Ensure there is a thorough connectivity map both from a qualitative and quantitative perspective.</p> <p>O5 Achieve knowledge of the reliable flux along the Camino.</p> <p>Ensure that the measurements taken are consistent, common and flexible so that the information gathered can be of help for future improvements.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To listen to the real needs from local agents and determine how best can RURITAGE help them. Keeping RURITAGE legacy alive. Facilitate connection with residents with defined activities. Synergies to be created with local initiatives on cultural heritage. Promote a governance model with the involvement of public and private bodies and involving the end-users in the process of open innovation. 	<p>O6 Identify requirements from local population and entrepreneurs that can be covered by RURITAGE's best practices and offerings to keep the HUB alive.</p> <p>Ensure that the measurements taken are consistent, common, and flexible so that the information gathered can be of help for future improvements.</p>

6.1.4 List of actions

Enhancement action	Title of Enhancement action	Objective (please refer to section 1.2)
RM1.9	IDENTIFICATION OF THE CAMINO'S VALUES	O1
RM1.10	RURITAGE TASK FORCE	O2 – O6
RM1.11	EMERGENCY PLAN	O3
RM1.12	CONNECTIVITY MAP	O4
RM1.13	MEASUREMENT TECHNOLOGY	O4, O5

6.1.5 Operational programme

Code of the action	RM1.9
Title the action	IDENTIFICATION OF THE CAMINO'S VALUES
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage; Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature, Built, Artefacts Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Social practices Rituals and festive events, Oral traditions
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	New
Relevant RM/KFP involved	CARTIF
Brief description of the action	Facilitate and conduct meetings between the different partners involved in the HUB with the intention of creating a core set of values through a series of brainstorming sessions. The idea is to identify those common and agreed values that are considered, not only important for the population and stakeholders around the Camino but also to which all those who undertake the Camino de Santiago as a pilgrimage route should adhere to. The final product of this action will be a document of core values that will be published and disseminated.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM1.1
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Once the common set of values is determined and agreed upon, the intention is to publish a document which will be distributed different media (online, social media, local associations and institutions, both public and private). This chart will be also one of the main subjects of the RURITAGE Task Force, an action foreseen also by the enhancement plan. Target 1: 1 Chart of Values Target 2: Dissemination of the Chart among the population among a minimum number of 10 rural communities which will be visited by the RURITAGE Task Force (explained below).
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team definition: by identifying those stakeholders (HUB Partners) that are best suited to help define the values. • Brainstorming sessions to determine all potential values that identify uniquely the Camino: will be performed in a series of meetings held online. • Selection of key common values with a proper argumentation: once the common values are identified, each of them will be properly documented. • Presentation of the outcome of the activity to the rest of the HUB members. Prior to making the set of core values public, they will be presented to the rest

	<p>of the HUB members participating in the rest of the Enhancement plan Actions detailed in this document with the idea to build consensus.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publish and communicate the values: the document with the values will be published and distributed through different media channel to reach as many as possible.
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>ASOCIACIÓN AMIGOS DEL CAMINO: Miguel Pérez Cabezas A Deep knowledge of many of the Stakeholders of the Camino and a particular vision on the values. A lot of experience dealing with all kinds of situations around the route.</p> <p>EMPRESARIADO LOCAL: Eduardo Francés The point of view of a dedicated person to the Camino, former Major of Castrojeriz and owner of a business that is mainly supported by its pertinence to the Camino.</p> <p>HOSPEDERÍA SAN ZOILO: José Antonio Perrino A different perspective of a religious person, but also in charge of one of the most important pilgrimage places in Palencia and in the whole route.</p>
Beneficiaries	Pilgrims, Local enterprises and other organizations, HUB members
Timeframe	March 2021 – Sept 2021
Indicative costs	The expected cost involved regards the imprinting and publishing of the core value document (around 300 €).
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget

Code of the action	RM1.10
Title the action	RURITAGE TASK FORCE
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage; Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature, Built, Artefacts Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Social practices Rituals and festive events, Oral traditions
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM4-6 (Federation of Colombian Municipalities) and RM5-2
Relevant RM/KFP involved	CARTIF
Brief description of the action	<p>This is the main action within this Enhancement Plan. With the information gathered by the other actions and the original RURITAGE Project know-how, this Task Force will visit a number of selected rural communities along the Camino with a dual role: inform the local population and private entities about what the concepts around the Camino de Santiago are, what the RURITAGE project is, what the RURITAGE Hub is but, most importantly, collect their input on needs, ideas to improve the current experience around the Camino de Santiago.</p> <p>This will enhance the relationship of the population around Camino de Santiago with the Pilgrim and improve the local involvement in the conservation of values and ideals of Camino de Santiago.</p>
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM1.1
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>Prepare a robust content corpus and with the help of a local “TROUBADOUR” establish a series of meetings with local population, enterprises, and administrations to make known the best practices of the RURITAGE project and HUB. These meetings should also help gather local requirements and needs.</p> <p>Once all visits are complete, a lesson learned workshop will take place which will be</p>

	<p>retrofitting the HUB for future further actions.</p> <p>This action involves a number of targets (as mentioned before):</p> <p>Enhance the knowledge of the population around the concepts of Camino de Santiago.</p> <p>Increase the relationship of the population around Camino de Santiago with the Pilgrim.</p> <p>Improve the involvement of local population in the conservation of values and ideals of Camino de Santiago.</p> <p>Improve the comprehension of the Camino Values among the local enterprises.</p> <p>Target 1: Activities performed at least in 8 places. Reach 15 municipalities.</p> <p>Target 2: Reach 120 persons</p>
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team definition: by identifying the perfect communicators within FSMLR to perform the task. • Build a detailed strategical plan and corpus, establish a list of local contacts and a calendar plan of visits. • Execution of the visits according to the roll-out plan built. • After all visits have taken place and, with the information collected, a Lessons learned will be performed. • The results of the lessons learned session will be communicated to the rest of the HUB stakeholders.
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Municipalities of the selected places. Help us to organize the activities, with the selection of the places.</p> <p>Local Troubadour: engage locals to attract local population. It's better less public more interested than a huge amount of people but less interested.</p>
Beneficiaries	Pilgrims, Local enterprises and other organizations, local population, and HUB members
Timeframe	March 2021 – March 2022
Indicative costs	Estimated cost for this activity is planned for 4.600 €.
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget.

Code of the action	RM1.11
Title the action	EMERGENCY PLAN
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage and Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature, Built, Artefacts
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM2-1
Relevant RM/KFP involved	n.a.
Brief description of the action	<p>The intention of this action is to establish the basis of a good common emergency plan by ensuring the proper coordination among the different agents (police, firemen, hospitals, etc.) involved in the different provinces / communities with the idea of providing the pilgrim and local communities with an alert and action plan system in case of major catastrophes.</p> <p>The goal is to escalate this process to other areas of the Camino.</p>
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM1.1
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Improve the coordination among different involved agents during emergencies / catastrophes.

	<p>Communicate population and pilgrims the security aspects along Camino de Santiago.</p> <p>Target 1: Promote the elaboration of an Emergency Plan in Castilla y León.</p> <p>Target 2: Extend it to the whole Camino in Spain.</p>
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team definition: by identifying those stakeholders (HUB Partners) that are best suited to help define the values. • Risk Identification by a series of meetings to brainstorm about different situation to be taken into consideration. • These meetings should also help identify needs and opportunities in terms of the security along the Camino of Santiago. • Build a thorough Contact list with local administrations to define adherence. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ In case of interest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Collaborate in the preparation and execution of the Emergency Plan. • Perform a “lessonS learned” session to build up know-how for future HUB actions
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>CENTRO TECNOLÓGICO CARTIF - KPF: Francisco Barrientos Technological support</p> <p>ASOCIACIÓN AMIGOS DEL CAMINO: Miguel Pérez Cabezas A Deep knowledge on Security Issues around the Camino. Essential to focus the proposal on real needs.</p> <p>UGRECYL: Cristina Escudero Responsible for the Emergency Unit for Heritage in Castilla y León. Expert knowledge and support for the planning of the activity.</p>
Beneficiaries	Pilgrims, Local enterprises and other organizations, local population, and HUB members
Timeframe	March 2021 – December 2021
Indicative costs	Around 350 €
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget

Code of the action	RM1.12
Title the action	CONNECTIVITY MAP
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage; Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature, Built, Artefacts
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM2-1
Relevant RM/KFP involved	N/A
Brief description of the action	<p>Analyse the current connectivity situation in the Castilla and Leon portion of the Camino the Santiago with the help of existing information provided by telecommunication companies but also by a survey to be sent among the population of a set of rural communities identified.</p> <p>This will help understanding what the needs are not only for the pilgrim but the local population.</p> <p>Our findings will be documented in quantitative and qualitative connectivity maps.</p>
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM1.6

Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>Ensure there is a thorough connectivity map both from a qualitative and quantitative perspective.</p> <p>Collect information of local needs and communicate with telecommunication companies to determine how current situation could be improved.</p> <p>Target 1: A Connectivity Map</p> <p>Target 2: Contacts with administrations and communications companies to spread the map and so, the necessities.</p>
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team definition: by identifying those stakeholders (HUB Partners) that are best suited to help define the values. • Define how to gather information, who to contact and build a strategy plan. • Prepare the arguments to present to telecommunication enterprises. • Perform a series of survey and prepare a report with the findings. • With all the information collected thru statistical data and the surveys, elaborate the connectivity map. • Contact local and national administrations and telecommunication enterprises. • Communicate findings to the HUB members. • Perform a “lessons learned” session to build up know-how for future HUB actions
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>GRUPO DE ACCIÓN LOCAL DE CASTROJERIZ: Ángel Manso Local knowledge on the real needs of the population. Contacts with communication enterprises</p> <p>CENTRO TECNOLÓGICO CARTIF - KPF: Francisco Barrientos Technological support</p> <p>GRUPO ACCIÓN LOCAL SAHAGÚN: Esther Benito, Gonzalo González Local knowledge on the real needs of the population</p>
Beneficiaries	Pilgrims, Local enterprises and other organizations, local population and HUB members
Timeframe	March 2021 – December 2021
Indicative costs	400 €
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget

Code of the action	RM1.13
Title the action	MEASUREMENT TECHNOLOGY
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage and Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature, Built, Artefacts
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	New
Relevant RM/KFP involved	N/A
Brief description of the action	Improve the measurement methodology along the Camino de Santiago to count with reliable data through the promotion of the installation of digital equipment to collect relevant data of the use of the Camino.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM1-2
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Ensure that the measurements taken are consistent, common, and flexible so that the information gathered can be of help for future improvements.

	Target 1: To have counters at the beginning and end of each of the three provinces of Castilla y León.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team definition • Elaborate a proposal of better and common measurements. Definition of the parameters to measure, selection of the spots to place the sensors. • Present the proposal to different administrations to get adherence. • Lessons learned through the interpretation of the data gathered.
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	CENTRO TECNOLÓGICO CARTIF - KPF: Francisco Barrientos Technological support
Beneficiaries	Administration, Pilgrims, Local enterprises and other organizations, local population, and HUB members
Timeframe	March 2021 – October 2021
Indicative costs	400 €
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget

6.2 RM2 Via Mariae (HCC) Enhancement plan

Figure 7: This photo was a part of the RURITAGE photo contest.
Photographer: Tibor Steigerwald

6.2.1 Background

Our RM is located in Harghita county, Romania. Harghita is situated in the middle of Romania, at the eastern border of Transylvania, in the central part of the Eastern Carpathians. The county is predominantly a mountainous area, about 60% of the total surface is covered by mountains. There are over 2000 mineral water springs in Harghita county - utilized for therapeutic purposes. The forests cover more than 30% of the county's surface (about 228.614 hectares); the forests are mostly coniferous 73%, which is why Harghita county is called the "evergreen land".

Main economic activities in Harghita county are wood processing, food processing, garment production, agriculture, and tourism. 63% of economic agents are in urban regions. The rural is characterized by low number of active SMEs in rural regions, lower development of services in rural areas. 59,6% of the territory is used for agriculture; however the agricultural sector has relatively poor results compared to the potentials. The land is parceled in small lots, which generates a subsistence economy. In the last 10 years has emerged a very intense small scale farming and an active application tendency for agricultural EU support dedicated to farmers. In Miercurea-Ciuc monthly there is a local producers' market, several local food brands have been elaborated and introduced.

There are 17 tourism information centers in HR county; the number of structures for tourist reception grew with 10% in 2016 compared with 2015. 79% of the tourism accommodation offers are pensions and agropensions. The number of agrotourism pensions grew significantly in 2015, in total 175 new pensions have been recorded. The use of these capacities is still low, 16,5% in a year. Most of the tourists visiting HR county are Romanians, while most of foreign tourists come from Hungary. During 2010-2014 there was a constant increase in tourist arrivals, more significant in rural than in urban regions. The resources and opportunities of the area are represented by: mineral water springs, woodlands, eco-agriculture, active tourism, ecotourism, rural tourism, pilgrimage tourism. The latter is one of the oldest forms of tourism and the Via Maria pilgrimage route to Șumuleu Ciuc/Csíksomlyó is one of the most important Romano-Catholic pilgrimages. Tourists coming in the area are often interested and attracted by the cultural, religious, sporting and gastronomy events. The most widely known religious feast is the Pentecost Pilgrimage organized each year in Șumuleu Ciuc/Csíksomlyó, which attracts hundreds of thousands of pilgrims from all over the world.

In particular, the shrine of Csíksomlyó which consists – according to Franciscan friars' records – from several parts and elements such as the former Gothic church, the present Baroque church and its components. The most important item of the church is the statue of Mary, which is a Renaissance-style artwork, made of linden wood at the beginning of the XVI century. It is 2.27 meters tall, therefore is mentioned as the tallest Mary statue in the

Figure 8: Image courtesy of PRO EDU.

Figure 9: Photo courtesy of HCC (source: visitharghita.ro)

Figure 10: Photo courtesy of HCC (source: visitharghita.ro)

world. It represents the Woman Clothed with the Sun, having the moon under her feet while wearing a crown of 12 stars on her head. Mary's statue is the central element of the shrine.

The two organisations representing RM2 Via Marie are Harghita County Council (HCC) and the Association Pro Educationem Transilvaniensis (PRO EDU).

Harghita County Council (HCC) is the local public administration of Harghita County with one President - elected directly by the citizens for a mandate of 4 years - and 30 County Councillors, including the two Vice-Presidents of the county council. Our institution provides services for the residents and contributes to the local growth by means of development programs (infrastructure and public acquisitions, preservation of cultural patrimony and historical monuments, assistance and urbanism and construction certification; investments and economic development, international, EU funded and structural projects' management; development and implementation of county level programmes on several fields of interest, county level events organization and protocol, relation with mass-media, human resources, international relations and coordination of the local public authorities of the county).

Association Institutio Pro Educationem Transilvaniensis (Pro Educatione) is the network of 15 adult education provider organizations of Alba Iulia roman-catholic Diocese, Transylvania, Romania. The network joins the forces of these organizations, supports their work in spiritual, intellectual and material respects, and urges collaborations between members in order to realize synergies in Christian adult education. Network member organizations have significant adult education and training experience, and expertise in pastoral work (family and youth pastoral), spiritual counseling and retreats, supervision and mental health, home care and help of disadvantaged groups. Most of the adult education programs offered by the network target the education and training of adults from rural regions.

Figure 11: Photo courtesy of Jakob Antal House.

Rural Heritage Hub

The physical location of our HUB is the headquarter of Harghita County Council and the Jakob Antal Study House located at the well-known pilgrimage site Csíksomlyó/Sumuleu-Ciuc.

The Jakob Antal Study House, which is also the headquarter of the Association Pro Educatione and many of its network member organisations, is situated just 3 kilometers away from the center of Miercurea Ciuc, in the immediate vicinity of the Sumuleu-Ciuc Cathedral and the Franciscan monastery. The house was opened twenty years ago and since then it has offered accomodation and dining services for pilgrims and groups in an idyllic and peaceful environment, and has given place for several national and international conferences, cultural and spiritual events

Figure 12: Photo courtesy of Jakob Antal House.

The headquarters of the Harghita County Council where the other RHH is located is the largest building that houses a county council in Romania. It is situated in the centre of Miercurea Ciuc, the county residence city of Harghita county. Besides Harghita County Council's institution, the building hosts also other significant governmental institutions and organisations and due to its facilities, it is the ideal place to organize large scale meetings for a significant number of participants. It also has an Art Gallery that is open 24 h and hosts periodical

art exhibitions.

The reference SIA

PILGRIMAGE

RM2 Via Mariae is working in the Pilgrimage SIA, because of its rich pilgrimage heritage. The Via Mariae pilgrimage route to Şumuleu Ciuc / Csíksomlyó is one of the most important pilgrimage routes in Central and Eastern Europe. Mary's Way has the characteristic to be a pilgrimage that connects the States of Central Europe with historical, cultural or religious differences. The aim is to build up not only a unified pilgrim's way but also to create a network between these places. Mary's Way builds a connection in the East-West direction between the Austrian Mariazell, Budapest, Máriapócs and Şumuleu-Ciuc (Csíksomlyó) and in the North-South direction between Czestochowa, Esztergom, Budapest and Medjugorje. The pilgrimage route crosses Austria, Hungary, Romania, Slovakia, Poland, Croatia and Bosnia. By welcoming all types of visitors and offering a diversity of experiences, the way aims to be a bridge between religions and people connecting East and West, North and South.

The final destination of the pilgrimage route is the Franciscan Monastery and Church in Şumuleu Ciuc (Csíksomlyó), which is home to the famous statue of Virgin Mary.

The shrine Csíksomlyó consists – according to franciscan friars' records – from several parts and elements such as the former Gothic church, the present Baroque church and its components, the statue of Mary and the miracles happened at this shrine.

According to historical records franciscan friars built the first Gothic church in Csíksomlyó between 1442–1448, and dedicated the Visitation of Virgin Mary to Elisabeth. The church consecrated in 1448 remained in its original form until 1802, when a decision was taken to dismantle it. The materials of the former church were used in the construction of the new, Baroque style church started in 1804. Finished in 1876 the church was consecrated on the 20th of August.

The most important item of the church is the statue of Mary, which is a Renaissance-style artwork, made of linden wood at the beginning of the XVI. century. It is 2,27 meter tall, therefore is mentioned as the tallest Mary statue in the world. Represents the Woman Clothed with the Sun, having the moon under her feet while wearing a crown of 12 stars on her head. At the same time the statue presents Virgin Mary as queen, since she has a royal crown on her head, while she is keeping a sceptre in her right hand and her child on her left.

Mary's statue is the central element of the shrine. There have been several miracles happening by the statue during centuries, according to records lots of prayers have been listened

Figure 13: Photo courtesy of Via Mariae Association.

Figure 14: Photo courtesy of Via Mariae Association.

to by Mary. The marble slabs placed around the statue confirms these miracles.

The Franciscan monastery is another important element of the shrine. There has been a former monastery built together with the Gothic church, that was totally damaged during the tartar offence. This was the reason why a new monastery was started to be constructed around 1700.

„The Franciscan monastery of Csíksomlyó constituted an important spiritual-religious centre within the Csík region, and the shrine church was an important pilgrimage site already from ancient times. It is still an attractive site that draws large numbers of pilgrims who came with pleasure to this shrine” – says franciscan friar Erik Urbán in a brochure titled „The Message of Csíksomlyó”¹. Nowadays the central feast of Csíksomlyó is the Pentecost Pilgrimage, hundreds of thousands pilgrims join it year by year. There are, however, other Marian feasts to that further thousands of pilgrims come to, such as the Holy Name of Virgin Mary feast or the First Saturday Salutation to Virgin Mary pilgrimage. Each pilgrim program developed due to the significant respect and reverence for the Blessed Virgin Mary.

Figure 15: Photo courtesy of Via Mariae Association.

In this SIA we would like to use the experience of our Role Model partner RM1 Camino de Santiago.

Other relevant SIAs

ART & FESTIVAL

Arts & Festivals are important drivers for development of the local communities along the routes of Via Mariae. Promotion and support of local traditional activities would be used to increase visibility in order to increase the length of stay and reveal the history and potential of the localities, becoming a tool for economic revival and vitality.

In Harghita County, the professions inherited from our ancestors, dating back hundreds of years, have begun to decline in recent decades, and there is a risk that some of them can even disappear.

Perhaps one of the most popular crafts is the wood carving and within this the confection of the Szekler Gate, which is one of the outstanding symbols of the Szeklers, with traditional decorative motifs. In addition to woodworking, it also had a long tradition of processing almost all raw materials found in Szeklerland. Handicrafts products were also made of clay, wood, tinder, felt and wool. In the past, the tinder product confectioners were more popular, currently, only six families are engaged in this craft. Tinder, also known as wood mushrooms, can be used as a raw material for many products, they are also used to make bags and ornaments. Painted furniture has a long tradition even today, unique painting patterns and motifs varying from region to region, they still can be admired in several family houses. Weaving, spinning, sewing and lace blending are also present in the area and are even widespread household activities. Szekler characteristic is the thick woolen

Figure 16: Photo courtesy of HCC (source: visitharghita.ro).

blanket. Blankets were even made from corn husks. Not just blankets, but doormats, baskets, boxes, etc. also made of it. In addition to custom-made household items, it is also considered unique: the chimney cake, which is a popular and unique look sweet.

Traditional crafts, inherited from parents and grandparents, are kept or revived in increasingly more families of Harghita, who want to pass on the tradition of pottery, wood carving, weaving or husking and with the knitting.

In each village of Harghita, there are craftsmen doing this out of passion or because craft represents a lifestyle to them.

Harghita County Council also supports the keeping and promoting of crafts, financially backing various projects in this respect. Harghita County Council President Borboly Csaba believes traditions are resources that need to be kept, because they can bring about not only jobs, but can represent an opportunity for the youth to remain in these regions and can become tourist attractions.

Over the past few years, increasingly more people of Harghita prefer the traditional products made by the craftsmen in the county, the periodically organised fairs in the county becoming more popular. Those who prefer to decorate their home with handicraft objects or to use clay pots in their kitchen say it is more important to go back to traditions and to keep the true values left from the forefathers.

Furthermore, there many festivals organised in each year that support local arts, crafts and traditions.

- **The Pentecost pilgrimage in Şumuleu Ciuc/Csíksomlyó:** The Şumuleu Ciuc/Csíksomlyó Pentecost pilgrimage began in 1567, a vow of pilgrimage of szeklers for the protection of their Catholic faith, which has become the most significant pilgrimage of Hungarians since 1990. Each year hundred thousands of pilgrims arrive to this sacred religious event organized on Pentecost day and the place is visited by several pilgrims during whole year. The event offers a good opportunity for the local traditional food and craft products providers to valorize their goods for visitors.
- **The Day of the Thousand Szekler Girls:** The day of the Thousand Szekler Girls, organized on the first Saturday of July in Miercurea Ciuc, is a celebration of music, dance and the popular Szekler clothes, which offers an opportunity to present, preserve and popularize the values of the Szekler folk art and garments. The first edition of the festival was organized in 1931. The tradition was revived in 1990, keeping its original goal of preserving folk traditions. The event begins with a parade of the traditional costumes. Girls and boys dressed in traditional clothes march to the city center, dancing on folk music. The program continues on the ridge that links the two hills of Şumuleu, where, after a religious service, the folk groups gathered from all the corners of the Szeklerland are introduced to the public. Immediately after that, starts a true feast of the folk clothes, dance and songs.
- **Stuffed cabbage festival in Praid/Parajd:** The Stuffed Cabbage Festival is Szeklerland's and Romania's first gastronomic festival. Each year, it takes place on the 3rd weekend of September. A lot of teams, whose biggest desire is to show to the world their cooking skills, are gathering together for this festival in each year. Visitors can find all kinds of stuffed cabbages: tiny, little, big and huge. The program includes performances by folk dance ensembles, traditional costume shows and concerts.
- **The polenta festival in Valea Rece/Hidegség, Lunca de Jos/Gyimesközéplak:** The Csángó-Fatanyéros Guesthouse organizes the Csángó Festival of polenta with cheese in Valea Rece/Hidegség, Lunca de

Jos/Gyimesközéplak, in August each year. The purpose of the event is to protect and promote traditions. In addition to the polenta cooking, the organizers are waiting the interested ones with local products fair, concerts, exhibitions, sport events and folk music programs.

- **The potato festival in Miercurea Ciuc / Csíkszereda:** In 2001, when this event was organized for the first time, it seemed to be a simple gastronomic contest in which only potato stew boiled in most of the competing teams' pots. Over the years, however, this event has evolved into a true scene for all sorts of potato delicacies, but also an opportunity for community interaction. The participants take their role very seriously, turning every year a banal potato dish into a sophisticated and varied menu with different flavors, bringing the jury and the tasting audience to work. The festival is organized annually in the Central Park in Miercurea Ciuc/Csíkszereda and gathers potato lovers from all over the country and abroad. In addition to potato delights, the festival has a dedicated program for young people, creative and craft workshops, popular dances and other beloved community activities.
- **Sausage festival in Nicoleşti/Csíkszentmiklós:** Each year, in February is taking place the sausage festival in Nicoleşti/Csíkszentmiklós. A huge amount of traditionally made Szekler sausages, folk music and dances are welcoming visitors in this festival. Many local teams are participating in the competition, where is prepared the tastiest traditional sausage.
- **Onion festival in Siculeni/Madéfalva:** Each year, in mid-September is organized the onion festival in Siculeni/Madéfalva, with a varied offer of onion and local traditional products from the area and also local crafts and folk programmes are presented.
- **Fruit festival of Odorhei/Udvarhely region:** Since 2009, each year in September, the Fruit Festival of Odorhei/Udvarhely Region is organized. It has become a tradition in the Odorhei/Udvarhely Region that this month the village moves for three days in the city to celebrate and enjoy together the natural and cultural values. The purpose of the event, which has become a tradition in the Odorhei/Udvarhely area, is to support communities that cultivate and process local fruit varieties. During the 3 days of the festival, visitors could taste products such as jams and homemade syrups, natural fruit juices, dried fruits and various kind of cakes.
- **Plum days in Dealu/Oroszhegy:** Each year, at the end of August is organized the plum festival in Dealu/Oroszhegy, which takes several days and offers various programs for visitors and pilgrims, traditional products made of plum, craft presentations and folk programmes. In the springtime the same locality organizes the narcissus festival each year.
- **The raspberry festival in Vărşag/Székelyvarság:** In the first weekend of August is organized the raspberry festival in Vărşag/Székelyvarság, which is one of the most significant gathering events in the locality, that offers opportunity to join together, to participate in the cultural programmes and to taste local products.
- **The Straw Hat festival in Crişeni/Kőrispatak:** Each year in August takes place the straw hat festival in Crişeni/Kőrispatak, where an important collection of straw products is also presented in the local museum. The participants have the opportunity to get acquainted with the manufacturing process and to buy locally made straw hats.

In this SIA we will use all the knowledge we have learned from our project partner RM8 Visegrad.

LOCAL FOOD

Harghita county is a predominantly agricultural, rural region due to the economic activity among the county's rural population is agriculture. Harghita County Council considers as one of its most important duties to promote and preserve the rich culture, traditional cuisine, catering and peculiar handcraft products. In the course of its work one of the priorities falls on helping and supporting people living in rural territories and local producers, contributing by this means to the creation of jobs and the preservation of the rural tourism. For reaching the set goals and objectives regarding the mentioned priority, and taking into account the priorities set in Harghita County's Agricultural and Rural Development Strategy Harghita County Council initiated and developed the Szekler Product community trademark, efficiently representing and protecting the interests of local producers for their future well-being and promoting among citizens the benefit of consuming local and healthy food. Harghita County Council's initiative regarding the Szekler Product trademark is a good example of how people in a community can overcome unfavourable global processes by creating a common and unique trademark for the products produced at local level. With the introduction of the Szekler Product trademark, the Council of Harghita County wishes to serve and keep the rich and lively agricultural traditions, as well as to guarantee the market access of quality and healthy foods.

The Szekler Product Brand movement was initiated by the county council in 2008, based on a good practice known through a EU fund project carried out in partnership with Valle d'Aosta, Italy regarding the support of local products and over the years the implementation of activities was carried out by the Harghita County Council's Rural Development Association and later by the Development Agency of Harghita County.

Within this programme several local and traditional fairs are regularly organized each year and each month, as well as the local products are also brought to international fairs and exhibitions. In order to support the local producers in the process of selling products online, the website www.szekelytermek.ro was developed.

Due to this initiative, also the pilgrims have the opportunity to join this regularly organized traditional fairs along Via Mariae pilgrimage route.

In this SIA we have learned from the experience of RM3 Apulia.

6.2.2 Starting point

The RM actions we have already implemented are summarized in the table below:

Figure 17-18: Photo courtesy of HCC.

Code	Role Model Action name	Objective
RM2.1	Improve services: eco-mobility, Wi-Fi connection, tourism services (hostels, bar & restaurants), signals, maps, radio...	Creation of new business opportunities, involvement of local businesses, improvement of the signals and information sources, promotion activities
RM2.2	Expand the offer, promoting eco-tourism: link the pilgrimage route to other activities (outdoor sports, excursions...)	Creation of new program packages addressed to pilgrims and interested people
RM2.3	Create a set of guided tours or organized travels, tailored for different targets	Creation of guided tours along the pilgrimage way in order to diversify the offer
RM2.4	Pilgrim's passport: a fidelity card to involve local business into the project and create new business opportunities	Creation of new business opportunities, involvement of local businesses, active participation of the local stakeholders

6.2.3 Objectives of the enhancement plan

The overall objective of our Enhancement plan is to support and boost the valorisation of our local cultural and natural resources in order to work as an effective model for rural regeneration. To enhance growth through our rural heritage, our stakeholders have chosen two main actions during the co-development phase, considering that these two actions will generate positive and sustainable change in our rural communities. These actions target our need for making all our local assets more visible. The Enhancement plan tries to achieve the main objective through focusing on the tangible and intangible heritage of several rural communities in our area, specifically assets of built cultural heritage, traditional activities, handicrafts of the villages along the routes of Via Mariae in our territory, Harghita county.

With all these we would like to increase the sustainability of local communities, enable them to better safeguard their built heritage assets, support local craftsmen, enterprises which valorize local traditions, crafts, activities to offer their services to pilgrims which pass through their villages, through all these actions offering pilgrims a more memorable experience in our region, persuade to stay longer, show them all the potential our region has to offer, all in all, make local inhabitants more proud to live in this region and young people less likely to flee their villages.

Opportunities and/or open issues to address	Specific objectives	
Many unused, abandoned built heritage sites, buildings in rural areas	O1	Promote the renovation, conservation, repurposing, reuse of built heritage in rural areas to offer them as shelters for pilgrims.
		Inventory of the calls for proposals to find funding sources for the activity. Promote the mountain rescue shelters along the pilgrimage way.
Rich cultural heritage, a lot of traditional activities still practiced in villages - opportunity for offering a memorable experience for visitors to our rural areas	O2	Promote the rich cultural traditions of our rural areas and offer them as alternative programs for pilgrims passing through these villages - this represents an opportunity for them to get to know our region, history and culture

	Inventory of the calls for proposals to find funding sources for the activity. Promote the Szekler product program and the local traditional activities.
Foster training through workshops, internships, teaching classes, camps etc to promote and support local traditional handicrafts and their transmission from generation to generation as a way to create jobs	O3 Make locals, especially young people proud of their heritage and prevent them from fleeing their villages

6.2.4 List of actions

This section is dedicated to the specific actions of the enhancement plan. Minimum two actions are requested from each Role Model within the framework of RURITAGE. Please provide the link with the specific objectives stated in Section 1.2 and with the Role Model actions already implemented before RURITAGE, to understand if the actions part of the Enhancement plan are part of the same path/strategy already started in your territory, or it is brand new.

Enhancement action	Title of Enhancement action	Objective (please refer to section 1.2)
RM2.5	To identify unused buildings that can be transformed into shelters for pilgrims	O1
RM2.6	Transformation of an unused building owned by the Szent Gellért Foundation into a pilgrims' shelter	O1
RM2.7	Make an inventory of relevant crafts and traditional activities to be included it in the pilgrim offer for pilgrims	O2, O3
RM2.8	Include traditional local foods and farmers along the Via Maria pilgrimage route in the pilgrimage offer	O2, O3

6.2.5 Operational programme

Through our operational program we are planning to implement the following actions:

Code of the action	RM 2.5
Title the action	To identify unused buildings that can be transformed into shelters for pilgrims
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Built
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM 1.4. Promote the restoration of old or unused buildings
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM1 Camino de Santiago
Brief description of the action	In the frame of this action we would like to identify possible buildings in the villages along the routes of Via Mariae in Harghita county that could be transformed into shelters and make a list of these buildings including a comprehensive description of their current condition and potential.
Previous RM action to	

enhance (if any)	
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	O1 Target: - identify at least 3 unused buildings that can be transformed into pilgrims' shelters in the upcoming 2 years - organise at least one event to meet all stakeholders involved (at least 80 people involved)
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • identify potential old and unused buildings • on site visit and discussions • reflect together with owners on how to find resources to do the renovation, repurposing • organize one conference/meeting involving stakeholders to discuss common plans – VIA Mariae Conference workshop, RHH Jakab Antal House, October 2021
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Via Mariae stakeholders, local authorities, local parishes
Beneficiaries	Local communities, pilgrims, visitors, local authorities
Timeframe	April 2021– April 2022
Indicative costs	to be evaluated
Indicative funding sources	PRO EDU: 600 EUR from RURITAGE Own resources of stakeholders, private donations, governmental programs

Code of the action	RM 2.6
Title the action	Transformation of an unused building owned by the Szent Gellért Foundation into a pilgrims' shelter
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Built
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM 1.4. Promote the restoration of old or unused buildings
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM1 Camino de Santiago
Brief description of the action	In the frame of this action we would like to turn an unused building owned by one of our stakeholders, the Szent Gellért Foundation into a shelter for pilgrims. Our stakeholder partner, the Szent Gellért Foundation works with disabled children and elderly people in Szentegyhaza, Vlahita, Harghita county. They own an unused building the foundation that could be potentially turned into a pilgrims' shelter. This way the Via Mariae pilgrimage route would have a reference pilgrims shelter in Vlahita -Szentegyháza, and the donations, symbolic revenue coming from the accomodation use, would be a great help for the foundation and its programs.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	n.a.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	O1 Target: - by the end of the project the building should be able to welcome pligrims at least during summer months (preparing bedrooms and bathroom, installing heating system is a further step, we are not able to ensure this by the end of the project) - at least one event to be organised (at least 20 people involved)
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • identify steps that have to be taken to transform the building into a shelter • identify needed resources and ways to attract them • promotion of building as pilgrims' centre, shelter • organising one event designated for stakeholders, involving the Szent Gellert

	community – Pro Edu networking meeting, October 2021, RHH Jakab Antal House
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Szent Gellert Foundation, Via Mariae Association
Beneficiaries	Local communities, pilgrims, visitors, local authorities
Timeframe	April 2021– April 2022
Indicative costs	to be evaluated
Indicative funding sources	PRO EDU: 1100 EUR from RURITAGE Own resources of stakeholders, private donations, governmental programs

Code of the action		RM 2.7
Title the action	Make an inventory of relevant crafts and traditional activities to be included it in the pilgrim offer for pilgrims	
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art&Festivals	
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Traditional Craftmanship	
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM8.2. Promote and support local traditional activities	
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM 8 Visegrád	
Brief description of the action	The purpose of this action is to get a comprehensive overview of the most important traditional activities practiced in the rural areas of Harghita county, that would have a potential to be promoted as programs, attractions for pilgrims, visitors in the area	
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	n.a.	
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	O2, O3 Target: - identify and make an inventory of the existing traditional crafts along the 2 main sections along the Via Mariae pilgrimage route in Harghita county - organise at least one event (involving at least 10 people)	
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • identify most important crafts, local traditional activities in villages • find craftsmen, organisations, local enterprises who practice it • include traditional activities in Via Mariae online maps, programs, • developing Via Mariae website in order to make crafts visible • promote the activities for pilgrims along the routes through signals • support the transmission of crafts from old generations to younger generations through a camp, training, workshop involving traditional activity of a village) • In case any other potential buildings are identified that can be transformed in the frame of our project during Action RM2.5, other actions will be included for these as well. • support the transmission of crafts from old generations to younger generations through a camp, training, workshop involving traditional activity of a village) 	
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Local stakeholder group members: NGOs, local public authorities, churches, entrepreneurs from tourism sector, local people	
Beneficiaries	Local communities, local producers, craftsmen, enterprises, pilgrims, visitors	
Timeframe	April 2021 – April 2022	
Indicative costs	HCC: 500 EUR for webpage development from Travel budget PRO EDU: 400 EUR for events	
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE project	

Code of the action		RM 2.8
Title the action	Include traditional local foods and farmers along the Via Maria pilgrimage route in the pilgrimage offer	
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art&Festivals; Local Food	
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Social practices Rituals and festive events	
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM8.2. Promote and support local traditional activities	
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM 8 Visegrád RM3 Apulia	
Brief description of the action	The purpose of this action is to include local foods and food producers, service providers along the Via Mariae pilgrimage route in Harghita in all the information and communication materials of Viae Mariae in order to assure a better promotion and valorization of these local products to the pilgrims, visitors in the area using the Szekler product (EN), Székely termék (HU), Produs secuiesc (RO) brand database	
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	n.a.	
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	O2, O3 Target: -identify and make an inventory of the existing local foods and food producers along the 2 main sections along the Via Mariae pilgrimage route in Harghita county - positioning signals along Via Mariae pilgrimage route (approximately on 20 km)	
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • identify most important traditional local foods and food producers in Harghita county using the Szekler brand inventory • make these products, producers visible along the pilgrimage route through signals • webpage development to make local products visible • include traditional foods in Via Mariae online maps, programs etc • promote them and assist their valorization 	
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Local stakeholder group members: NGOs, local public authorities, churches, entrepreneurs from tourism sector, local people	
Beneficiaries	Local communities, local producers, craftsmen, enterprises, local authorities, pilgrims, visitors	
Timeframe	April 2021 – April 2022	
Indicative costs	HCC: 4500 EUR for signals PRO EDU: in case budget left to be allocated here	
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE project	

6.3 RM3 Agro-food production in Apulia (DARE) Enhancement plan

Figure 19: This photo was a part of the RURITAGE photo contest. Photographer: Evangelos Karalis

6.3.1 Background

RM 3 – DARE Apulia is located in the Apulia Region. Apulia is a region of Italy, located in the southern peninsular section of the country, bordering the Adriatic Sea to the east, the Ionian Sea to the southeast, and the Strait of Otranto and Gulf of Taranto to the south. The region comprises 19,345 square kilometers (7,469 sq miles), and its population is about four million. It is bordered by the other Italian regions of Molise to the north, Campania to the west, and Basilicata to the southwest. Its capital city is Bari.

Figure 20-, 21, 22-, 23: and 24: Photo courtesy of DARE/Vazapp.

DARE, although it operates in all the south of Italy, it is located in Foggia, which is a province in the Apulia (Puglia) region of southern Italy. This province is also known as Daunia (after Daunians, an Iapygian pre-Roman tribe living in the territory) or else Capitanata, originally Catapanata, because during the Middle Ages it was governed by a catepan, as part of the Catepanate of Italy. Its capital is the city of Foggia. The province of Foggia can be divided in three parts: one centered in its capital Foggia called Tavoliere, another sided along the Apennines named Daunian Mountains and the third one representing the spur of the boot-shaped Italian peninsula called Gargano.

The Tavoliere is an important agricultural area: grapefruit, olives, durum wheat and tomato are the chief products. It is also called "the granary of Italy" because of its important production of wheat.

Daunian Mountains lie along the border with Molise and Campania. Scattered with small villages only, the mountains are mostly covered by forests and pastures, with the main produce being hams and caciocavallo

cheese. Faetar, a francoproveçal dialect, is spoken in two villages: Faeto and Celle di San Vito.

The Gargano is a peninsula partly mountainous and partly covered by a forest, Foresta Umbra with vegetation typical of Central Europe, the only lasting part in Italy of the ancient Black Forest. Allegedly [weasel words] its name comes from the word ombra (shadow) because of its thickness that prevents the light to enter in contrast with the typical flora. The coast of Gargano is rich in beaches and touristic facilities. In the north are two major salt lakes Lesina and Varano. It is also important for the production of olives, olive oil and both mountain and sea typical food products.

Although less important than once before, the agricultural sector remains the mainstay of Foggia's economy, so much that its area is nicknamed the "granary of Italy". The few industries present are mostly devoted to food processing. Almost every peeled tomato in Europe comes from the province of Foggia in southern Italy. Every year, two million tons of tomatoes are produced but the farmers get only eight cents per kilo. In order to survive in the free market economy most tomatoes-farmers recruit illegal immigrants.

Rural Heritage Hub

Figure 25, 26 and 27: The DARE RHH. Photo courtesy of DARE/Vazapp.

The RHH is located in historical centre of the City of Foggia. It is characterized by coworking area, a meeting room, two offices and its interior replicate the design of the main events and images of the activities of rural regeneration of the territory. At the moment the main activities are project meetings, funding opportunities and communication.

The RHH also involves the team of Vazapp, the University, more than 500 farmers and food producers. In addition, the participation to RHH is offered to diversified and skilled young people such as designer, artists, communicators, journalists, photographers in order to have a contamination environment.

The reference SIA

The area of RM3 is characterized by one of the largest flat land of Italy and is very relevant for the production of

local food. Mainly, durum wheat for pasta production and tomatoes are the most important cultivations. In addition, the territory offers a very large biodiversity thanks to the Parco Nazionale del Gargano. The local food production is characterised by a large variety of products due to the biodiversity as well the ancient history and tradition evolved thanks to the contamination over time of our population with others. DARE activity is considered as relevant for the SIA because it promotes the actions of the Vazapp team, oriented at the regeneration of the rural territory, at the dignity of the local production and farming life, and the restoration of relationships within the rural communities thanks to the implementation of social innovation initiatives.

Other relevant SIAs

RESILIENCE

The role of intangible and tangible heritage is of great strength when increasing awareness regarding survival of natural hazards. Throughout history, this has been traditionally done through storytelling. Today, DARE contributes to the dignity of the community and acts as promoter of resilience throughout its actions.

ART & FESTIVAL

DARE with Vazapp team has the potential to act as a focal point for creativity and communication about a very different way of doing business around local food, for the significant benefit to the rural community. A local food system should build community, biodiversity, healing, social justice and wellbeing. This can be made more visible, promoted and celebrated through the arts. Bringing local arts and food together will build capacity within the local arts sector by providing new performance, festival and celebratory opportunities and engaging with local audiences and participants. This will help to bring significance to what we mean by community cohesion and resilience and help us adapt creatively to what will be a new 'normal' in all our lives.

6.3.2 Starting point

Code	Role Model Action name	Objective
RM3-1	Support local farmers and producers in innovation projects	Creation of new business opportunities, involvement of local businesses
RM3-2	Identify, prioritize and monitor technologies, resources, and skills in the agro-food production of the area	Generating a technological transfer between research and production
RM3-3	Definition of marketing and communication strategies for the products	Generating a new dignity to local food producers through different communication actions
RM3-4	Definition of standards of quality for the selected products	Increasing the added value of production through reputation, branding and packaging
RM3-5	Promote the environmental sustainability of the agro-food production, packaging and selling	Increaseing the public awareness of local consumers in order to assign more value and choose sustainable productions

RM3-6	Social innovation ideas	Generating formats to increase the social capital, one of these is the experience of contadinner, which aims at gathering farmers and speed date them to start up a mechanism of cooperation based on trustworthy relationships
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Local Stakeholders have been involved in the discussion session through-out a focus group approach. The main objectives of the discussion have been centred on the role of DARE, through RURITAGE project and vision, on the rural regeneration of the territory. The discussion has been set after a clear explanation and narration of the actions of other RMs and Rs. The main idea was to integrate in our local strategy, other consortium partners action to enhance the local strategy. Local stakeholders have discussed about a pre-selected number of actions and have been asked about their expectations and how they could imagine those actions in our territory. The moderation role of DARE has consisted in identifying and translating stakeholders' discussion in actual strategies to be included in the enhancement plan.

Finally, the discussion has produced several alternatives to be included in the enhancement plan. The contamination with other RMs best practices found deep interest towards art, rural architecture, and training practices. The main belief of local stakeholders is the diversification of local regeneration strategies through contamination with creative industry and design in rural areas.

6.3.3 Objectives of the enhancement plan

Several open issues characterize the Apulia territory, more specifically, marginality of rural areas, reducing income, increase age of entrepreneurs in local food business, migration of young and skilled people are the most relevant socio-demographic dynamics happening in the last two decades. In addition, there are important psychological and sociological aspects to be considered, such as the downgrade of the perception of rural living as well as the closure and numerical reduction of the local communities, leading to a reducing positive perception of rural areas and working in local food system.

Opportunities and/or open issues to address	Specific objectives	
Stimulating the cross-contamination between creativity and local food in order to generate a new relationship between city and countryside	O1	Introducing art to connect people with countryside Introducing art performances into fields in order to attract people for harvesting or other farm operation in order to bring city people into the rural territory
Generating a new dignity of productive areas through a different narrative that enhance the positive perception and identity of rural areas.	O2	Generating a new narrative of the territory through architecture and design Developing a manual and guidelines for a new narrative of territory through "tactical ruralism", a new approach to use history and design for the narrative of the territory
Stimulate the contamination with new professions in the local food production in order to give new opportunities to young and skilled people and have them stay in the territories	O3	Meeting skilled and young professions Delivering a series of webinar that connect local food producers to young and skilled professionals, where the latter deliver webinars and solutions to local food, the former take part as audience.

6.3.4 List of actions

Enhancement action	Title of Enhancement action	Objective (please refer to section 1.2)
RM3.7	Art in the fields	O1
RM3.8	Tactical ruralism manual	O2
RM3.9	New services for local food system innovation	O3

6.3.5 Operational programme

Code of the action	RM3.7
Title the action	Art in the fields
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Local Food; Art&Festivals
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Performing Arts
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM7.4
Relevant RM/KFP involved	Take Art
Brief description of the action	Introducing art performances into fields in order to attract people for harvesting or other farm operation in order to bring city people into the rural territory
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM 3.3
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Stimulating the cross-contamination between creativity and local food in order to generate a new relationship between city and countryside Performance indicators: number of people participating (200); number of followers on social media (2000); number of performances (min 2)
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programming social innovation activities that will host art in the fields • Defying the role of art in the activity • Involving local performers • Defying the program of the activities • Defying and implementing the communication strategy • Develop the initiative • Implement the performance(s)
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Vazapp group, local art performers, local food producers actively participating
Beneficiaries	Local food producers receiving their products and territory promoted, local community
Timeframe	May 2021 – April 2022
Indicative costs	€ 10'000 (€ 5000 from RURITAGE fundings)
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE fundings (services) and ticketing and private fundings

Code of the action	RM3.8
Title the action	Tactical ruralism manual
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Local food; Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Knowledge and practices

Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM 8.4
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM8 - Visegrad, RM13 - WESTBIC
Brief description of the action	Developing a manual and guidelines for developing a new narrative of the rural territory through “tactical ruralism”, a new approach to use history and design for the narrative of the territory. The manual is intended to deliver a methodology of “tactical urbanism” applied to rural territories. The target of the manual are professionals, local stakeholders at EU level since it is going to be produced both in English and Italian and delivered online, as free/open access document, and in hardcopy versions. The manual is going to be both theoretical and it is going to present documentation about real cases developed as experiments.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM 3.6
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Generating a new dignity of productive areas through a different narrative that enhance the positive perception and identity of rural areas. The target of the manual are professionals, local stakeholders at EU level since it is going to be produced both in English and Italian and delivered online, as free/open access document, and in hardcopy versions (no. 2 manuals, no. of downloads min 50).
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting with professionals (Architects supporting the development of the manual) • Defining the concept of the guide • Defying the graphical layout • Writing and draft editing • Publication in two languages (Italian and English) • Dissemination though a press-release, publication online as free access and as hardcopy
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Vazapp group, local architects and designers
Beneficiaries	Local food producers, local community, all EU and also worldwide designers and rural regeneration stakeholders, architects and designers working for rural territories, professionals, local stakeholders at EU level
Timeframe	May 2021 – April 2022
Indicative costs	€ 5000
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE fundings

Code of the action	RM3.9
Title the action	New services for local food system innovation
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Local food
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Knowledge and practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	Smart Rural Living, Pennela (16.2)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM 16
Brief description of the action	Delivering a series of webinar organized in a calendar that connect stakeholders to young and skilled professionals, where the latter deliver webinars and solutions to local food, the former take part as audience. Seminars are going to be about market analysis, communication, packaging, selling, hospitality in farmlands, social innovation.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM 3.1

Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Stimulating the contamination with new professions in the local food production in order to give new opportunities to young and skilled people and have them stay in the territories. The target group of the actions are local food producers, local community, academics and enthusiasts. The quantitative objectives are: min no. 3 series of webinars, no. 50 participants, no. 150 followers
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting with professionals that could support and deliver sections of the seminars • Defining the concept of the webinars • Defying the organization and the targeted audience and organizing the calendar of webinars • Defying and implementing the communication and the invitation • Webinars
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Vazapp group, local young and talented professionals selected based on their contribution to the development of innovative ideas for local food
Beneficiaries	Local food producers, local community, academics, enthusiasts
Timeframe	May 2021 – April 2022
Indicative costs	€ 3000
Indicative funding sources	€ 3000 from RURITAGE fundings

6.4 RM4 Colombian coffee UNESCO cultural landscape (FCM) Enhancement plan

Figure 28: This photo was a part of the RURITAGE photo contest. Photographer: Santiago Sierra Durán

6.4.1 Background

The Federación Colombiana de Municipios was founded in 1989, currently representing the 1102 municipalities and their authorities, who belong to the entity in its own right, as well as the nearly forty (40) Associations of Municipalities existing in the country. Throughout its 31 years of existence, the FCM has focused efforts on contributing to development, well-being and peace, through the strengthening of local government as a key part of the decentralization and territorial autonomy built by Colombia, as well as on formulating, managing and implementing projects of public interest for its representatives, which contribute to generating stable conditions for peace, the well-being of communities and sustainable development. Achieving the Federation's objectives in "Strengthening local capacities through actions of broad coverage and impact on municipal development.

Rural Heritage Hub

The FCM decided to establish two different physical RHHs to be able to cover the whole case study area that was selected in RURITAGE; specifically two municipalities have been selected: Salento and Palestine.

Palestine is located in the coffee heart of Colombia, with the municipalities of Chinchiná and Manizales forming the most important coffee triangle in the department. Salento is an Andean city in Colombia, is in the west of Bogotá. It is known for its coffee farms and the surrounding vegetation. To the east is the Valle del Cocora, where the wax palms a national symbol.

For the RHH of the municipality of Salento, Quindío, the Town Hall was chosen. It is a building of approximately 150 years, which was built with the characteristic of the architecture of the Antioquia Heritage of the colonial era. The Town Hall is the place where the administrative decisions of the municipality are made, and it is in the main square of the urban area, located at the municipal plaza. It is freely accessible to the entire population and has capacity for approximately 50 people. All the decisions related to the activities of the Coffee Cultural Landscape of the municipality are taken from the Major's office, since it is where the municipal cabinet is located, as for example, the Secretary of Planning, Secretary of Tourism, Culture and Sport.

Figure 29, 30 and 31: Photo courtesy of FCM.

For the RHH of the municipality of Palestina, Caldas, the House of Culture of the municipality was chosen. It is a construction with more than 100 years old. It portrays the colonial cultural heritage of the municipality for its cemented bahareque architecture and roof with clay plates. With capacity for approximately 40 people, art courses are held at the House, and it is the place where the officials of the Ministry of Culture work with the community and the Municipal Ministry of Culture for the Coffee Cultural Landscape issues. It has recently been renewed, however, it maintains the old infrastructure. The House of culture is surrounded by a variety of infrastructure with the same architectural finishes that represents the cultural value of the municipality.

Figure 32, 33 and 34: Photo courtesy of FCM.

Throughout the project’s advance, we have faced some issues related to local stakeholders which have made hard to follow the steps of co-development, mostly due to the restrictions imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic. Anyhow, from previous consultation it clearly emerged the need of further building local capacities regarding marketing and sustainability issues, because not all the local communities have access to higher education. For instance, within the tourism sector we can find people who have only taken an elemental education and at the same time, people with postgraduate degrees. From this, it has been somewhat difficult to generate a cohesive view of the future and development from them. Therefore, the Enhancement plan is intended to strengthen the technical capacities of local communities and, from there, to promote a joint vision of the territory.

The reference SIA

LOCAL FOOD

The heritage of the municipalities of Salento and Palestina located in Colombia corresponds to a close relationship between the territory, culture and nature. Landscapes, flora, fauna and fields of food crops of these municipalities are part of each of its inhabitants. However, economic challenges and migration to larger cities by younger population led to rethink how locals can thrive economically whilst preserving heritage. Currently, the Federación Colombiana de Municipios has achieved that actors such as young people, local producers, among others, feel immersed in global dynamics by acting locally. Thus, by building capacities, promoting local production and product specialization, a higher sense of belonging to the heritage surrounding the coffee production activity in the municipalities would be generated.

Other relevant SIAs

LANDSCAPE

Colombian Cultural Coffee Landscape – PCCC (as in Spanish) was declared by UNESCO in 2011 and it comprises specific areas in 47 municipalities in Colombia. These 47 municipalities share some features regarding culture, landscape and biodiversity that represent the heritage related to coffee in Colombia. In order to promote this heritage, both nationwide and globally, several local tourism operators have appeared throughout the years to showcase the particular assets in the region. Federación Colombiana de Municipios, alongside with other entities will be providing tools and training to local tourism promoters as well local producers to promote local sustainable tourism that would set the PCCC in top of mind of people all around the world.

6.4.2 Starting point

Code	Role Model Action name	Objective
RM4.1	Promote cooperation and relationship between universities, public entities, and local producers, through joint workshops.	Frame private and public actor surrounding the Colombian Cultural Coffee Landscape
RM4.2	Develop virtual training courses	Provide training to small coffee producers to add value to Colombian coffee production
RM4.3	Create a complete and didactic manual of each tourist place both rural and urban of each municipality.	To collate the tourism information of the municipalities in order to promote tourism.
RM4.4	Creation of inventories of the CNH characteristics.	Unify all characteristics regarding Natural Cultural Landscape of Cultural Coffee Landscape.
RM4.5	Define an action plan for the communication of the biodiversity of the area.	Promote sense of belonging towards Colombian Cultural Coffee Landscape through biodiversity dissemination
RM4.6	Generate synergies with existing programs that focus on fostering the sense of ownership of young people in the territories.	Promote sense of belonging in younger generations towards Colombian Cultural Coffee Landscape
RM4.7	Identify and create an inventory of the access routes to rural areas where coffee is produced.	Promote learning about coffee culture through tourism in Cultural Coffee Landscape
RM4.8	Participate in a minimum of two national events of the FCM with the interested parties involved, for the socialization and promotion of the project. Both public and private entities, as well as most local mayors attend these events.	Articulate National, Regional and Local Government Entities along with project's results in order to promote local investment
RM4.9	Promote the tourist offer of both municipalities through the design of a tourist route that specifies the restaurants, hotels and shops.	Promote local tourism through territorial marketing strategies
RM4.10	Design a calendar of each fair of folk heritage and festivals and fairs to promote tourism.	Promote tourism in Colombian Cultural Coffee Landscape through cultural and natural heritage

At the very beginning of the project, local workshops were held locally in order to identify necessities that would be aligned with the previous actions that were implemented before. This articulation was intended to continue the strengthening of local capacities. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the difficulties that FCM faces since RHH are located in rural areas, participation and consultation with local stakeholders and beneficiaries, i.e. mostly farmers, had not been successful. Instead, FCM has been working directly and remotely with local governments and through them all the processes are being conducted.

6.4.3 Objectives of the enhancement plan

The overall objective of the plan is to promote the capacity building at local level in order to guarantee a sustainable linkage between agricultural and tourism sector, through the capacity-building initiative in Local Economic Development, which impacts both sectors of the municipal economy.

Opportunities and/or open issues to address	Specific objectives
Build a vision of joint territory that	O1 Promote innovation and teamwork activities in order to

collects all sectors (tourism and agriculture). The open issue to address is the lack of articulation among the different actors present in territory, which does not allow local development in a comprehensive way		encourage the creation of local productive projects
		The overall objective is to promote the creation of local projects that allow producers to compete against the large traders in the territory.
	O2	Strengthening local capacities for Local Economic Development
		The overall objective is to generate and build capacities and skills in local producers to help them to improve local economy.

6.4.4 List of actions

Enhancement action	Title of Enhancement action	Objective (Please refer to section 1.2)
RM4.11	Promotion of local product innovation and place marketing	O1
RM4.12	Capacity building and training to promote local integration in local heritage related activities	O2

6.4.5 Operational programme

Code of the action	RM4.11
Title the action	Promotion of local product innovation and place marketing
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Local food
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Knowledge and practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM16-2 “Promote innovation and research development to create new services, products and business opportunities in the rural context”
Relevant RM/KFP involved	PENELA (RM16), DARE (RM3)
Brief description of the action	Currently, coffee producers in municipalities do not have their own or recognized brand or product that allows them to expand the range of their offer. Therefore, it is intended to make an accompaniment in the creation of its own brand or product specialization, which can be marketed on a large scale in a long period of time.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM4-6 Generate synergies with existing programs that focus on fostering the sense of ownership of young people in the territories According to Lessons learned – Identity and Branding
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	From this action FCM aims to provide local producers within municipalities a business model that focuses on product innovation, product development, product specialization or place marketing. Target: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of business model and local brand fitted to local needs. • At least one local producer’s association participating in the business plan’s building process. • At least one local government participating the business plan’s building process. • At least 20 local producers involved in the presentation of the study
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify local needs from the experience acquired by FCM’s partners (municipalities) to select the best option to develop a new local brand or

	<p>promote product specialization. This information will be collected through phone calls, meetings, among others.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a feasibility study for the development of local brands or product innovation for local producers (external support) • Presentation of the study to the interested local producers and local government • Collaborate with local government in identifying beneficiary population for the plan
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Local governments (Secretary of Rural Development and Tourism), local producers
Beneficiaries	Farmers and local producer 'associations
Timeframe	01.08.2021 – 01.06.2022
Indicative costs	5000 EUR
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE Project resources

Code of the action	RM4.12
Title the action	Capacity building and training to promote local integration in local heritage related activities
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Local food
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Knowledge and practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM3-3 “Definition of marketing and communication strategies for the products”
Relevant RM/KFP involved	DARE (RM3), Penela (RM16)
Brief description of the action	<p>Regarding the existing inequity in terms of access to education and training among the stakeholders, this action will provide them the opportunity to develop their skills. Thus, in order to achieve so, FCM will provide a virtual course in Local Economic Development which will focus on economic promotion, place branding and collective work.</p> <p>Alongside National Knowledge Service (SENA as in Spanish), FCM will offer courses to local producers, local tourism operators and members of local civil society organizations in topics related to sustainable tourism, circular economy and innovation projects for local development to complement the process that RURITAGE has started in the municipalities.</p>
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM action 4-2 FCM Develop virtual training courses (Capacity building)
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>It is intended to continue strengthening the capacities of the producers and beneficiaries of the project. To this end, a virtual course aimed to building the capacities of these people will be launched.</p> <p>This virtual course will be provided in FCM’s online training platform SIVIFOM and is aimed to reach at least 40 people amongst local food producers and local tourism operators.</p> <p>Target</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- One online course in local economic development implemented 2- At least 40 local actors trained in local economic development after course implementation
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual course content update. Update contents for the course in the

	<p>following topics: local economic development, place marketing, economic axis articulation, branding to promote a shared vision of local development.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online virtual course launch in FCM's SIVIFOM. • Course implementation through synchronic and asynchronous session with beneficiaries in order to guarantee knowledge appropriation. • Identification of learned experiences after course implementation in order to promote public – private collaboration for implementation.
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Local governments (Secretary of Rural Development and Tourism)
Beneficiaries	Local producers, coffee growers' associations, local civil society organizations, tourism operators.
Timeframe	01.06.2021 – 31.12.2021
Indicative costs	5000 EUR
Indicative funding sources	Project resources

6.5 RM5 Migrants hospitality in Asti Province (PIAM) Enhancement plan

Figure 35: This photo was a part of the RURITAGE photo contest. Photographer: Alessia Bertuca

6.5.1 Background

PIAM (Project for the Integration and Welcoming of Immigrants) is a non-profit organization based in Asti, formed in 2000 by Italian and immigrant social operators. Specialized in assistance and support to women victims of trafficking, over the years it has developed professional competence also on the subject of reception, representing a replicable model for the integration of refugees and asylum seekers. Always proposing to create virtuous projects that unite different people, to transform vulnerability into opportunities. All in the name of local development, promoting sustainable hospitality and integration models, useful also to the territories that are hosting.

Figure 36: Villa Quagliana from above. Photo courtesy of PIAM.

Rural Heritage Hub(s)

Villa Quagliana

Villa Quagliana is the former Seminary of the “Oblati di San Giuseppe” religious order in Asti. A beautiful villa of the last century surrounded by greenery, with an adjoining farmhouse and surrounding park of six hectares of arable land, no longer used for years. In 2014, the COALA Consortium and PIAM onlus gave new life to this complex, starting the reception of refugees and asylum seekers. It is in this context, starting from hospitality, that the project to enhance and preserve Piedmontese agro-food excellence was born and developed.

Lago Stella

Lago Stella is a park dedicated to the theme of biodiversity, designed to educate on environmental sustainability through playful activities and to support people in difficulty through participatory and inclusive activities. A park managed by PIAM Onlus in partnership with various local entities, aimed at restoring the area to public use, enhancing natural resources and social inclusion.

Figure 38: Photo courtesy of the RURITAGE project. Photographer Alessia Bertuca.

The reference SIA

MIGRATION

PIAM Onlus is an association that operates in migration for more than 20 years old. All the activities listed in this plan are inevitably linked to this SIA, and in everyone, there is a role planned for the migrants to enhance their integration in the community. We intend to implement the lessons learned in all these years of activity. We figured that one of the keys to success is to apply shared planning between the various actors (civic engagement) so that the reception of migrants becomes an engine of development for the community and creates growth opportunities not only for the migrants but also for the territory itself. Also, we keep particular attention to local families and vulnerable groups, with inclusive initiatives for children and teenagers.

Other relevant SIAs

PILGRIMAGE

With the opening of our new RHH, the Lago Stella facility, we are now partner and founder of a project that wants to create a network of walking paths in this area. The project is called “Otto – Basso Monferrato”. “Otto” is the Italian for 8, that is the rough shape of the network of paths that appeared on the map after a first recognition, and “Basso Monferrato” is the name of this area. So we are looking forward to getting an experienced overall view from our partners in RURITAGE that operates in this SIA.

LOCAL FOOD

The cultivations in our RHH in Villa Quagliana are going fairly well, and the structure itself is getting better every year as a venue for different occasions of meetings (theatre, music festivals, social dinners, etc..). We think that it is now time to transform this temporarily available service into a legit tourist facility with a typical “trattoria” and a small local food shop.

LANDSCAPE

Fostering the tourist turnout into a relatively “untouched” environment as the northwestern rural area of the Asti province, could not be done without taking into account its varied natural heritage and landscape. This relevant factor has quickly become one of our main concern in the planning of these activities. And with the help of some local associations, already stakeholders in this project, and the experience of the lessons learned of our partners in RURITAGE, we aim to take particular care of this subject.

6.5.2 Starting point

Code	Role Model Action name	Objective
RM5.1	Restoration of old and unused buildings to give hospitality to the migrants (in the future could be converted in facilities for tourists)	To convert unused buildings in habitable refugee centres
RM5.2	Capacity building activities: Training to migrants and residents related with organic farming, arts, built heritage restoration, traditional crafts and trades, etc.	To boost job opportunities for migrants within local businesses
RM5.3	Selection of stakeholders in the Rural Hub related with the local agro-food chain and the creative industries and agreements with such stakeholders to support the integration of migrants.	To seek for technical advisors on specific tasks and to improve efficiency on project activities and investments
RM5.4	Facilitate connection with residents with defined activities: FOOD migrant catering-ethnic cuisine catering ART traditional dance, music performance. Synergies to be created with local initiatives on cultural heritage	To foster the integration process with local communities

RM5.5	Internship for migrants in local businesses, farms, tourism related activities	To boost job opportunities for migrants within local businesses
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Departing from these actions, we have discussed possible enhancement opportunities with various stakeholders of the territory, specifically with the municipalities that are already collaborating with PIAM on SIA projects for the reception and integration of migrants, with local cultural and sports associations, food producers and other cooperatives that are operating in social inclusion and/or local development activities in this area.

Two workshops took place between 2019 and 2020, where we discussed with stakeholders the main opportunities that could raise from tailoring RURITAGE Good Practices in our territory. Specifically, since the opening of our new RHH, the Lago Stella facility, we have foreseen the opportunity to work towards the pilgrimage SIA, to create a network of walking paths in this area. At the same time, discussing with representatives from the CIA (confederation of Italian farmers), from the social-oriented ARGO cooperative, from wine producer Cantine Bava and local food producer Agricoltura Indigena, we understood that there was a big possibility to further enhance food-related actions, keeping involving refugees and asylum seekers.

Last, we identified the great need for our projects to be better communicated and disseminated, to reach a broader audience and to create alternative storytelling regarding migrants integration and their potential role in rural areas.

6.5.3 Objectives of the enhancement plan

Opportunities and/or open issues to address	Specific objectives
The overall objective is to improve the touristic offer in the north-western rural territories of the Asti province and the activities related to the local cultural and natural heritage. The Asti province has an established tradition in hospitality, and the northwest area hidden potential of cultural and natural heritage could very well be the main factor in favouring a virtuous and ethical model of promotion for these rural areas.	O1 Tracing and digitalization of the touristic routes in north-western Asti territories To promote the north-western territories in the Asti province by slow and sustainable tourism, developed through a network of paths accessible on foot, bicycle or horseback. This network already exists, we called it "Otto – Basso Monferrato", and we intend to trace and digitalize all these routes along with maps and POI to make them available to the visitors.
	O2 Creation of an infopoint in our RHH (Lago Stella) The RHH at the Lago Stella facility is one of the starting points of the "Otto – Basso Monferrato" network of paths. The creation of an info point, along with a catering area and small local food shop, is beneficial to offer better access to its services and to promote the activities of the RURITAGE project in the area.
With the cultivations in Villa Quagliana, our RHH, we aimed at promoting and enhance the territory in which we live, with the desire to contribute to local development. They allow us to offer an ethical product. Because it is cultivated with natural and organic methods, and because it respects the work of those who produce it. Since they have been appreciated by many chefs, we want to make them available to the public and also improve visitors turnout in our RHH.	O3 Start-up of a restoration point in our RHH (Villa Quagliana) Start a new "trattoria" in the RHH, a social enterprise (startup) involving migrants hosted in the reception facility. Identify this restaurant with food directly linked to the territory and partly self-produced (cultivated in the fields of Villa Quagliana). Working refugees and asylum seekers have the opportunity to emancipate themselves, contribute to the development of the territory and continue the tradition.
All the activities need a communication strategy to be acknowledged by the public,	O4 Communication and dissemination on the upcoming activities and events in our RHHs

whether that is located near or far away from the facilities involved. The objective here is to go to a professional to take care of this aspect in the most efficient way.

Create a communication strategy in collaboration with a professional agency to increase the visibility of the local cultural, historical and environmental heritage-related activities within the RHHs.

6.5.4 List of actions

Enhancement action	Title of Enhancement action	Objective (please refer to section 2.2)
RM5.6	Improve the visibility and accessibility of the local hiking paths	O1
RM5.7	Creation of an infopoint and support of the RHHs visibility	O2 - O4
RM5.8	Startup of a restoration point and support of the RHHs visibility	O3 - O4

6.5.5 Operational programme

Code of the action	RM5.6
Title the action	Improve the visibility and accessibility of the local hiking paths
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage; Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Digital Heritage
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM 1.6
Relevant RM/R/KFP involved via DRRH and/or mentoring and learning visits	N/A
Relevant RM/KFP involved	UNIBO and POLITO
Brief description of the action	Tracing and digitalization of the touristic pathways in north-western Asti territories, namely the “Otto – Basso Monferrato” network of routes working with GPX files, streetmap and openstreetmap platforms.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM5.3
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>The main objective of this action is to improve the visibility and accessibility of the local hiking paths located in the area of the Otto – Basso Monferrato</p> <p>Specifically, the following targets will be reached:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One digital maps of the path • Online publication of the map, first on the "Otto - Basso Monferrato" institutional website, and then on tourist promotion websites of the local territory as well as hiking sites. • 300 people reached with organised events using digital mapping
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Routes tracing • POI (Points of Interest) indexing

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maps comparisons and data transfer on digital formats • Results dissemination • Organization of events through digitally shared data
Capital involved	Human - Social - Cultural - Environmental
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	PIAM Onlus - organization ARGO cooperative – routes maintenance BEWOOD association – tracing and digitalization Municipality of Chiusano and network of municipalities involved in SAI (former SPRAR) projects - logistics La Cabalesta cultural association – cultural advisors
Beneficiaries	Local population, tourists
Timeframe	May - October 2021
Indicative costs	Euro 500,00
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE

Code of the action	RM5.7
Title the action	Creation of an InfoPoint and support of the RHHs visibility (Lago Stella)
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage; Landscape; Local food
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Intangible – Knowledge and practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM3.3 + RM14.2
Relevant RM/R/KFP involved via DRRH and/or mentoring and learning visits	N/A
Relevant RM/KFP involved	UNIBO and POLITO
Brief description of the action	Creation of an info point, along with a refreshment area and small local food shop, in the RHH and a communication campaign to boost the visibility of its current and upcoming activities.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM5.1 – RM5.2 – RM5.3 – RM5.4 – RM5.5
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The main objective of this action is to boost the visibility of current and upcoming activities of the RHH located in Lago Stella. Specifically, the following targets will be reached: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of one info point and a small local food shop • Reaching 600 followers on dedicated Facebook social profile • Reaching 250 followers on dedicated Instagram social profile • A new section on our institutional website dedicated to RHHs activities • N. 5 publication of articles in local, national and international newspapers • N. 3 public events reaching 100 people
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set-up of an on-site info point • Set-up of an on-site local food shop

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set-up of an outdoor catering and event area • Involvement of a communication agency • Launch and dissemination of a promotional campaign • An inaugural event for the new info point and outdoor catering area • Organization of various public events
Capital involved	Human - Social - Cultural - Environmental
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	PIAM Onlus - organization ARGO cooperative – maintenance of the facility and catering management Municipality of Chiusano and network of local municipalities involved in SAI (former SPRAR/SIPROIMI) projects - logistics Otto Basso Monferrato partners – events management
Beneficiaries	Local population, tourists
Timeframe	May 2021 - June 2022
Indicative costs	Euro 7.500,00 (+ Euro 15.000,00 SociAL Foundation)
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE FONDAZIONE SOCIAL

Code of the action	RM5.8
Title the action	Start-up of a local restaurant and support of the RHHs visibility (Villa Quagliana)
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Local food; Migration
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Intangible – Knowledge and practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM3.3 + RM14.2
Relevant RM/R/KFP involved via DRRH and/or mentoring and learning visits	N/A
Relevant RM/KFP involved	UNIBO
Brief description of the action	Creation of a typical “trattoria” along with a small local food shop, in the RHH and a communication campaign to boost the visibility of its current and upcoming activities.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM5.1 – RM5.2 – RM5.3 - RM5.4
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>The main objective of this action is to enhance action 5.3, creating a local restaurant integrating migrants into the activities of the restaurant.</p> <p>Specifically, the main targets will be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N. 3 job opportunities (1 kitchen staff, 2 floor staff) for migrants hosted in our projects • Reaching at least 50 people through an inaugural event for the new trattoria and local food shop • Reaching 300 followers on dedicated Facebook social profile • Reaching 200 followers on dedicated Instagram social profile • A new section on PIAM institutional website dedicated to RHHs activities

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N. 5 publication of articles in local, national and international newspapers
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set-up of an on-site typical “trattoria” • Set-up of an on-site local food shop • Set-up of an outdoor catering and event area • Involvement of a communication agency • Launch and dissemination of a promotional campaign • Organization of public events
Capital involved	Human - Social - Cultural - Environmental
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>PIAM Onlus - organization</p> <p>ARGO cooperative – catering services and products sales</p> <p>Municipality of Asti involved in SAI (former SPRAR/SIPROIMI) project – logistics and publicity</p> <p>Agricoltura Indigena (local producer) – local food supplier</p> <p>Azienda Agricola Bava (local producer) – local wine supplier</p>
Beneficiaries	Local population, tourists and migrants hosted in the structure
Timeframe	May 2021 - March 2022
Indicative costs	Euro 3.500,00 (+ Euro 12.000,00 SAI project)
Indicative funding sources	<p>RURITAGE</p> <p>PIAM</p> <p>SAI (former SPRAR/SIPROIMI) project</p>

6.6 RM6 Migrants integration in Lesvos Islands Global UNESCO Geopark (NHMLPF) Enhancement plan

Figure 39: This photo was a part of the RURITAGE photo contest. Photographer: Athina Kritikopoulou

6.6.1 Background

The island of Lesvos is located in the northeastern Aegean Sea. Lesvos Island is characterized by a rich natural and cultural heritage and is widely known for the Petrified Forest, a unique natural monument comprising fossilized standing and lying tree trunks, remnants of a subtropical forest 20 million years old, its volcanic landscapes, hot springs, rich biodiversity, and the unique olive grooves.

The island presents a very rich history and was know as a place for culture even since ancient times. As the birthplace of important figures in the arts and literature and an area full of archaeological monuments, medieval castles, ancient villages, and Byzantine monasteries, It offers a broad historical and cultural experience. The rich cultural heritage is never the less, the result of a rich geological and natural environment, that led to its recognition as UNESCO Global Geopark.

Figure 40: Map showing the location of Lesvos Island Unesco Global Geopark. Image courtesy of NHMLPF.

Rural Heritage Hub

The hub is located at the premises of the Natural History Museum which include the main museum building and its facilities in Sigrí in Western Lesvos and the Information Center in the city of Mytilene. The Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest is also the operator of the Lesvos Island UNESCO Global Geopark and all its premises have already a function as gathering

points in the Geopark. The main building of the Natural History Museum in Sigrí is accessible and already well-

Figure 41: Key elements of the natural and cultural heritage of the Lesvos Island Unesco Global Geopark. Photo courtesy of NHMLPF.

established as a multi-purpose venue offering a conference hall and laboratories among other things. The hub

offers all necessary facilities to gather local stakeholders successfully. The museum also has all the necessary equipment to facilitate digital meetings with its stakeholders.

The RHH involves various types of stakeholders representing the local communities of the island. Among its stakeholders there are representatives of the local authorities (North Aegean Administrative Region, Municipality of Mytilene, Municipality of Western Lesvos), teachers and educators of the Primary and Secondary Education of the island, regional tourism associations professionals and businesses of the tourism sector, NGOs, athletic organizations and groups of the island, museum and cultural professionals of the various museums and cultural institutions of Lesvos, local women’s cooperatives e.t.c

Figure 42 - 43: The RHH located at the Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest in Sigri. Photo courtesy by NHMLPF.

The reference SIA

By enhancing its rich history, its cultural and natural heritage, Lesvos is fostering a heritage based sustainable

MIGRATION

regeneration process through migration. In the last couple of years, migrants have arrived at Lesvos from near situated Turkey. Lesvos has, therefore, developed integration and information programmes and initiatives for the newly arrived, as well as the local population. Their aim is to create awareness of the cultural and natural heritage of the island, promoting intercultural dialogue and giving migrants a sense of place.

Figure 44 - 45. Information programmes for refugees, held at the premises of the Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest in Sigri and at the Museum’s Information Center in Mytilene. Photo courtesy of NHMLPF.

The Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest organizes a variety of activities and events aiming to the support of the refugees and migrants arriving on the Island. Guided tours at the Museum, educational activities, photo exhibitions and athletic events with the participation of refugees and immigrant groups are organized at the Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest and in the sites of interest and landscapes of the Lesvos Island UNESCO Global Geopark, aiming to boost mutual understanding and integration with the local population.

Figure 46, 47, 48 and 49: Implementation of a variety of activities (educational programmes, athletic events, photo exhibition) relevant to the RMG's SIA, Migration. Photo courtesy of NHMLPF.

Other relevant SIAs

RESILIENCE

The Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest has a great experience in the field of Natural Disasters and Risk Mitigation. Since Greece is a country where natural disasters occur frequently, the museum has developed various programmes regarding disaster risk reduction and disaster risk management. Every year, it organizes and implements educational programmes for school groups of all ages, seminars for teachers and educators, field trips for university students and lectures for the general public in order to raise awareness on natural risks prevention, preparedness and protection measures. The museum also participates in the Inter-institutional Postgraduate Programme “Natural Hazards and Disaster Mitigation”.

LOCAL FOOD

The Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest collaborates with local authorities and local businesses towards a sustainable local economic development. For this reason, it supports local women’s cooperatives by displaying and promoting their traditional food products in its premises and organizing events specifically designed to promote local gastronomy. Understanding that local food could also serve as a key factor for touristic development, it tries to connect the natural and cultural heritage of the island with its gastronomic tradition and promote it as an alternative form of tourism.

ART & FESTIVAL

The Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest participates in many local festivals, usually held during the summer months all over Lesvos Island Unesco Global Geopark, by hosting various cultural events in its premises in Sigri and mainly at its outdoor theater. Studying the best practises of the relative SIA, it aims to use them in order to organise gastronomic events within the framework of a local food festival and further develop and promote its athletic events held around the island’s natural heritage sites.

LANDSCAPE

Lesvos Island Unesco Global Geopark is recognised for its significant geological value, the variety of geosites and its rich flora and fauna. The Lesvos Petrified Forest, part of the Geopark, is a unique monument of natural heritage and has been declared a Protected Natural Monument of Greece. The mission of the Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest is the study, research, promotion, exhibition, conservation and protection of the Petrified Forest. As the operator of the Lesvos Island Geopark, its activities and programmes expand to the protection and promotion of the natural wealth and the biodiversity of the whole island.

6.6.2 Starting point

Code	Role Model Action name	Objective
RM6.1	Developing integration and information programmes for migrants and citizens.	Smoothing and boosting the integration process.
RM6.2	Educational programmes and guided tours, specifically tailored for migrants to make them aware of the CNH of the territory. Developing temporary exhibitions on the island's CNH.	Making the migrants familiar with the new territory by using its CNH.

The Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest organised four participatory workshops with different types of stakeholders in order to discuss the current challenges and difficulties local communities are facing, effective possible solutions to deal with them and furthermore various opportunities that could be taken into consideration during drafting the enhancement plan. All the workshops were held digitally due to Covid-19 restrictions. The main point of all the discussions was the successive social-economical crises that Lesvos is facing over the last years (Economic recession, Migration, Unemployment, Natural Disasters, COVID-19 pandemic) and their dramatic impacts on the tourism sector and thus the local economy. Emphasis was also given to the marginalization of refugee population and social polarization that was intensified during the last year. The participatory workshops was an ideal opportunity to bring together representatives from local authorities and people from local communities in an open discussion, talking about all these difficulties and local problems, exchanging ideas and making suggestions on how natural and cultural heritage can be used as a driving force for local regeneration. All stakeholders agreed that the key driver for action is taking advantage of the island's natural and cultural wealth. It was decided to put a focus on the development and promotion of sustainable tourism and especially of alternative forms of tourism as a solution to reboot and boost local economy. Actions concerning the smooth integration of refugee populations and dealing with the social polarization were also considered essential. Last, but not least the issue of the latest natural hazards (earthquakes, floods) that hit the island and North Aegean in general came up, as well as the need to inform local communities regarding how they should react and respond in case of a natural disaster.

6.6.3 Objectives of the enhancement plan

E.g.: The overall objective of the plan is to support the rediscovering of our area in all its aspects, through the development of our natural and cultural heritage resources. Our natural and cultural heritage is an essential element of our territory that should be valorised.

Opportunities and/or open issues to address	Specific objectives
The wider social-economical crisis that is even more pressing after the covid-19 pandemic and its impacts on the local communities.	<p>O1 Development of a recovery and reboot plan for the day after the covid-19 pandemic.</p> <p>Collaboration with local authorities, representatives of the main economic sectors and local communities for a joint strategic plan based on the natural and cultural heritage resources, that will lead the way to recovery and reboot of the local economy. Identification and promotion of opportunities for sustainable local economic development through analyzing current strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>Involvement of local communities in the decision-making.</p> <p>Response to covid-19 pandemic through Resilience building.</p>

High rate of unemployment, especially among young generations.	O2	Development of a wider strategy that fosters new economic opportunities for the region.
	Creation of new business opportunities and support to local business, cooperatives and startups. Design of training opportunities for professional development to the young population.	
Refugee crisis, marginalization of refugee population and social polarization, intensified due to the destruction of the Moria refugee camp.	O3	Revision and improvement of refugee integration strategies.
	Boost of mutual understanding, intercultural dialogue and integration with the local population through organising heritage-led activities. Making refugees feel welcome in the new and unknown territory through activities targeted to their familiarity with its natural and cultural heritage.	
The dramatic effects of refugee crisis and covid-19 pandemic on the tourism sector, one of the island's main source of income.	O4	Development of a dynamic, community-based model of sustainable tourism.
	Collaboration with local authorities, tourism associations, professionals of the tourism sector, hotel owners, tourism businesses, travel agents to develop a common strategy for rebooting and boosting the tourism sector, that will be based on promoting alternative forms of tourism.	
Crisis in the cultural sector due to the closure of museums and cultural institutions during the covid-19 pandemic.	O5	Support of the local cultural sector.
	Development of a network of local museums and cultural institutions to form synergies in order to face current challenges and co-design activities (exhibitions, events, seminars, educational programmes...)	
Natural hazards and climate change adaptation.	O6	Development of Resilience plans and strategies.
	Public awareness and training on natural risks prevention and protection measures. Support of resilience building activities.	

6.6.4 List of actions

Enhancement action	Title of Enhancement action	Objective (please refer to section 1.2)
RM6.3	Redesign and further develop natural and cultural heritage activities for migrant integration taking into account experience, knowledge and evaluation data gathered during past activities.	O3
RM6.4	Develop Resilience building activities regarding natural hazards and climate change.	O1, O6
RM6.5	Organise local food festival-gastronomic events.	O1, O2, O4
RM6.6	Further develop and promote athletic events held around the island's natural heritage sites.	O1, O3, O4

6.6.5 Operational programme

Code of the action **RM6.3**

Title the action	Redesign and further develop natural and cultural heritage activities for migrant integration taking into account experience, knowledge and evaluation data gathered during past activities.
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art & Festivals, Migration
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature, Built, Artefacts Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Social practices Rituals and festive events, Oral traditions
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM5.4 Facilitate connection with residents with defined activities: FOOD migrant catering- ethnic cuisine catering ART traditional dance, music performance. Synergies to be created with local initiatives on cultural heritage R3.4 Educational material for language skills supporting migrants’ understanding of natural and cultural heritage R3.6 Increasing the awareness of cultural and natural heritage by cultural landscape interpretation R3.8 Strengthening the bonds between migrants and residents through creative land art and forest art work
Relevant RM/KFP involved	R3
Brief description of the action	The action will continue the development of a variety of activities and initiatives that the RM has already launched in the framework of its broader plan to make refugees feel welcome in the island and contribute to their integration. After evaluating activities and programmes organised during the last years, the RM will take into account its successes and failures in order to redesign and improve its heritage-led activities for refugee population.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM6.1 Developing integration and information programmes for migrants and citizens. RM6.2 Educational programmes and guided tours, specifically tailored for migrants to make them aware of the CNH of the territory. Developing temporary exhibitions on the island’s CNH.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The main objective is to improve the heritage-led activities the RM implements specifically for refugee populations. A revision and improvement of its initiatives aiming to refugee integration is essential as the marginalization of refugee population and social polarization has been intensified. Quantifiable target: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> designing 2 educational programmes specifically tailored for refugees (estimated number of participants: 30) organising the photo exhibition of the refugee photographer Amir Ali, “Lesvos with my eyes” in the Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forst in Sigri (estimated number of refugee visitors: 80, estimated number of visitors of local communities: 300, estimated number of tourists and visitors: 600) organising a joint photo exhibition based on the exhibition of the refugee photographer Amir Ali, “Lesvos with my eyes”, in collaboration with Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark-R3 and UNESCO WHS Messel Pit in Germany (estimated number of visitors: 400)
Specific activities	Design and implement 2 educational programmes for refugee population. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> review of the relative activities already implemented during the last years to spot the successes and failures. round table with NGOs that the RM has already collaborated in order to seek expertise and have a better understanding of the target audience.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • call NGO representatives to co-design the educational programmes according to the needs of the target audience. • drafting the various activities and the structure of the programmes • testing the programmes at a small number of participants and finalization • contacting various NGO's working with refugees in order to communicate the programmes and further organise logistics of the refugees' participation • implementation of the programmes and evaluation <p>Organise the photo exhibition of the refugee photographer Amir Ali, "Lesvos with my eyes" in the RM's hub in Sigri of Western Lesvos.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • redesign the exhibition for the temporary exhibitions hall of the Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest • setting up of the exhibition and organising the opening event with Amir Ali at the museum • informing NGOs working with refugees and UNHCR in order to ensure their visit at the exhibition • organising complementary events in the framework of the exhibition <p>Co-organise a joint photo exhibition based on the exhibition "Lesvos with my eyes" in collaboration with Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark-R3 and UNESCO WHS Messel Pit in Germany.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • digital meetings with the partners in Germany to discuss the organization of a joint exhibition in Germany and co-design the new format of the exhibition • visit at Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark to clarify all the final details for the exhibition • organising the transport and the set up of the exhibition in Germany • organising the opening event of the exhibition • set a communication and dissemination plan for the exhibition (press releases, social media posts, media interviews)
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professionals (project managers, educators, social workers etc.) working in NGOs and UNHCR and serving as the main point of contact between the RM and the refugee population. • Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark-R3 (Dr. Jutta Weber, geologist MS, geoscientific coordination, public relations management) • UNESCO WHS Messel Pit (Dr. Marie-Luise Frey, Business Director)
Beneficiaries	Refugee population, local communities, tourists of Lesvos Island Unesco Global Geopark Refugee population, immigrants and local communities of Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark
Timeframe	May 2021-May 2022
Indicative costs	€10.000
Indicative funding sources	Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest annual budget, Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark-R3, UNESCO WHS Messel Pit

Code of the action	RM6.4
Title the action	Develop Resilience building activities regarding natural hazards and climate change.
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Resilience, Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Intangible – Knowledge and practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM9.1 Organizing training - also using informal education methodology- to improve the resilience of local people HIGH (children, adults and elderly people, professionals, public authorities etc..

	<p>RM9.2 Develop interactive exhibitions to attract a broader audience.</p> <p>RM9.3 Development of toolkit for resilient citizens.</p> <p>RM9.5 Support the definition of guidelines for risk assessment and mitigation actions</p> <p>RM10.2 Promote a participative process in order to create a cohesive resilient community (educational activities and event, monitoring and rescue teams, etc.)</p>
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM9, RM10, R3
Brief description of the action	The RM will develop Resilience building activities and initiatives that aim to enforce the flexibility, adaptability, and perseverance of local communities when facing challenges following natural disasters and climate change.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	N/A
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>Based on its experience and previous research in natural hazards risk mitigation, as well as climate change and its impacts on natural environments, the RM aims to raise public awareness on natural risks prevention and protection measures and to promote actions that prepare the public to be able to adjust to both the current effects of climate change and the predicted impacts in the future.</p> <p>Quantifiable target:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> organising an educational programme on biodiversity and climate change adaptation (estimated number of children participating: 250) organising 2 training webinars for educators and teachers on natural hazards prevention and protection measures and on climate change adaptation (estimated number of participants 120) organising an exhibition on past climate changes in partnership with Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark-R3 (estimated number of visitors: 1000)
Specific activities	<p>Design and implement an educational programme on biodiversity and climate adaptation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Choose the age of target audience (primary and secondary education children) and adapt the programme to their needs, previous knowledge and school subjects Drafting the various activities and the structure of the programme Resting of the programmes at a small group of school students in collaboration with a specific school. Contacting regional schools to inform them of the programme and invite them to participate Implementation and evaluation of the programme <p>Organise 2 training webinars for educators and teachers on natural hazards prevention and protection measures and on climate change adaptation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop the structure of the webinars Contacting various experts and university professors to participate as guest lecturers Set a date and clarify further details in collaboration with Primary and Secondary Education of Lesvos Communicating the event through press releases, social media posts, personal invitations and notifications <p>Develop an exhibition on past climate changes in partnership with Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark-R3 and UNESCO WHS Messel Pit:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meetings with the partners to co-develop the exhibition Design the exhibition for the specific exhibition space in Bergstraße-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark, choose the exhibits, write the exhibition texts and

	<p>translate them</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further meetings with the partners to clarify all the details of organising the exhibition and schedule the specific dates • Organising all the logistics for the transport of all the exhibition materials in Germany and the staff' s traveling arrangements • Staff visit at Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark • Set up of the exhibition in the exhibition space of Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark • Set a communication and dissemination plan for the exhibition (press releases, social media campaign, media interviews, publicity material) • Organising the opening event in Germany
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary and Secondary Education of the island (A. Strataki-Head of Directorate of Primary Education of Lesvos, T. Theofanellis-Head of Directorate of Secondary Education of Lesvos) • Enviromental Centers (E. Galinou-Responsible of the Kalloni Enviromental Information Center, E. Kaldelli-Responsible of the Evergetoula Enviromental Education Center) • Directorate of Civil Protection of North Aegean (D. Malliaros-Director) • Organization for Earthquake Planning and Protection (A. Kourou-Head of the Directorate of Social Earthquake Defense of the Organization for Earthquake Planning and Protection) • Experts on biodiversity and natural hazards from the University of the Aegean • Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark (Dr. Jutta Weber, geologist MS, geoscientific coordination, public relations management) • UNESCO WHS Messel Pit (Dr. Marie-Luise Frey, Business Director)
Beneficiaries	Local communities, educators, teachers and school groups of local schools Local communities of Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark
Timeframe	May 2021-May 2022
Indicative costs	€25.000 [€8.000 from RURITAGE for transport of the exhibition to Germany, exhibition materials (banners, display stands), promotional materials (leaflets, posters e.t.c.) of the exhibition] +travel costs to Germany
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE, Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest annual budget, Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark-R3,UNESCO WHS Messel Pit

Code of the action	RM6.5
Title the action	Organise local food festival-gastronomic events.
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art & Festivals, Food
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Social practices Rituals and festive events
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	<p>RM1.8 Support local farmers in offering their products to tourists.</p> <p>RM8.1 Creation of a set of tourists packs,composed by FOOD related activities ART, NATURALISTIC Activities, etc.</p> <p>RM 3.1 Support local farmers and producers in innovation projects.</p> <p>RM3.3 Definition of marketing and communication strategies for the products.</p> <p>RM7.4 Marketing events in partnership with local villages to attract audience and facilitate greater community wellbeing and inclusion.</p>
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM1, RM8, RM3, RM7
Brief description of the action	In an attempt to face the crisis in the touristic sector and contribute to the reboot and recovery of local economy, the RM will promote alternative forms of tourism (agrotourism) through supporting local food professionals and local businesses.

	Events like these could be organised within local festivals.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	N/A
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>The RM aims to engage with local food producers and sellers sharing RURITAGE principles based on local food as part of local heritage and as a mean to promote local tourism and reboot local economy. It will especially try to establish partnerships and collaboration with local women's cooperatives.</p> <p>Quantifiable target:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> displaying local products from various local women's cooperatives of the island in Sigri Hub (Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest) all summer long organising an opening-launching event of the festival (estimated visitors: 100) organising various events (3-5) on local food in collaboration with local women's cooperatives (estimated visitors/participants at each event: 500)
Specific activities	<p>Organise a local food festival in Sigri Hub (Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest) that will be held during the summer months</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> setting up display and promotion stands with local products from various women's cooperatives of the island all summer long in the Museum's entrance hall organise meetings with the local women's cooperatives and establish a network of partners set a calendar together that will include various gastronomic events to take place in the framework of the festival (food testing, cooking demonstrations, cooking classes e.t.c.). Each one will be hosted by another women's cooperative and focus on the special products and recipes of each village co-decide and develop the type and structure of these events clarify the role and the contribution of each women's cooperative <p>Organise an opening-launching event of the festival with all the women's cooperatives involved, a fest to promote and market their products together and to launch the separate events that will take place</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> set a communication and dissemination plan for all the above (press releases, social media campaign, media interviews, publicity material), that could be incorporated into a larger touristic promotion campaign gathering relative information for all the women's cooperatives and their products and displaying them on the websites of the Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest and the Lesvos Island Unesco Global Geopark meeting with local authorities and tourism associations to seek for support and dissemination of the festival Implementation of the gastronomic events organise further meetings to discuss various ways of collaboration and potential synergies
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local authorities: North Aegean Administrative Region (N. Nyxtas-Vice Governor of Tourism), Municipality of Western Lesvos (A. Vati- Deputy Mayor of Tourism, Z. Ioakim-Deputy Mayor of Education and Culture) Local women's cooperatives: Agra women's cooperative (A. Bougioukli), Messotopos women's cooperative (E. Pitsa), Agia Paraskevi women's cooperative (E. Giannaki), Gera women's cooperative (D. Konstantelia), Asomatos women's cooperative (M. Kontara), Methymna women's cooperative (I. Stypsianou), Parakoila women's cooperative (M. Giavasi), Petra women's cooperative (E. Chioti), Polichnitos women's cooperative (E. Karatzanou), Schalochori women's cooperative (M. Katsaba) Regional tourism associations of Lesvos: Molyvos Tourism Association (N. Molvalis), Eressos Development and Promotion Association (P. Mantzoros)
Beneficiaries	Local communities

	Local women's cooperatives Local businesses Visitors and tourists of the island
Timeframe	May 2021- September 2021
Indicative costs	€5.000
Indicative funding sources	Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest annual budget

Code of the action	RM6.6
Title the action	Further develop and promote athletic events held around the island's natural heritage sites.
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art & Festivals, Migration, Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Intangible –Social practices Rituals and festive events
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM 2.2 Expand the offer, promoting eco-tourism: link the pilgrimage route to other activities (outdoor sports, excursions...). R3.1 Organizing a Mountainbiking Event with tech-courses and forest-teaching by rangers for migrants.
Relevant RM/KFP involved	R3
Brief description of the action	The RM will continue its series of various athletic events all over the island, all year long. The athletic events will be held at natural heritage sites and geosites of the island, promoting its natural wealth and establishing Lesvos as an alternative travel destination. People from the local communities, refugees and tourists are invited and encouraged to take part in these athletic events.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	N/A
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The objective of this action is double. From one hand, the further development and promotion of athletic events held in the island supports athletic and adventure tourism, attracting a specific target audience and establishing the island as an alternative tourism destination. From the other hand, these athletic events aim to contribute to migrant integration and boost mutual understanding since refugees compete side by side with people from local communities. Quantifiable target: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> organising 4 MTB Races in Agiasos, Gera, Sigri and Schalochori (estimated number of participants in each race: 120) organising 4 Mountain Running Races in Agiasos, Anemotia, Eressos-Lava Trails, Amali (estimated number of participants in each race: 120) organising 2 International Races, Lesvos Relay and Triathlon Race (running, swimming, cycling (estimated number of participants in each race: 150)
Specific activities	Organise MTB Races, Mountain Running Races and 2 International Races <ul style="list-style-type: none"> event planning meeting with all the partners-stakeholders involved set the dates, the natural sites that the events will take place, their route and duration, the number of participants, the different categories and the level of difficulty organise meetings with local authorities to ask for support meeting with all partners involved to arrange everyone's role and contribution open call for participants (develop a web registration form and set a final date for registrations) gather all registrations and contact all the participants for the events' details final meeting with all partners to clarify logistics set a communication and dissemination plan for the events (poster, leaflets, press releases, social media posts) implementation of the events and evaluation
Main stakeholders involved and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local authorities: North Aegean Administrative Region(N. Nyxtas-Vice Governor

their roles and contribution	<p>of Tourism), Municipality of Western Lesvos (A. Vati- Deputy Mayor of Tourism, Z. Ioakim-Deputy Mayor of Education and Culture)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Athletic Organizations and groups of the island: Lesvos Ride Races (T. Chatzelis), Lesvos Cycling Club (I. Laskaridis), Lesvos Running Club (I. Pattakos) • Regional tourism associations of Lesvos: Molyvos Tourism Association (N. Molvalis), Eressos Development and Promotion Association (P. Mantzoros)
Beneficiaries	Refugee population, local communities, local businesses, tourists
Timeframe	June 2021-May 2022
Indicative costs	<p>€25.000</p> <p>[€5.000 from RURITAGE for t-shirts, bags, medals and promotional materials (banners, leaflets, posters e.t.c.)]</p>
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE, Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest annual budget

6.7 RM7 Touring professional arts in rural areas (TAKE ART) Enhancement plan

Figure 50: This photo was a part of the RURITAGE photo contest. Photographer: Michael Chant

6.7.1 Background

Take Art is a Somerset-based charity that delivers a high-quality arts programme with a local, and growing national and international, focus. We do this by providing opportunities for people of all ages, backgrounds and abilities experience, participate and work in the arts.

Our Rural Touring Scheme is a cornerstone of our work. Bringing the highest quality live performance to a network of rural communities across Somerset, we offer extraordinary and memorable arts experiences to thousands of people each year.

In 2019, in partnership with local active members, we co-created and launched our Rural Heritage Hub, now known as CULTIVATE.

Figure 51: Example of a rural touring show. Photo courtesy of Take Art.

Rural Heritage Hub

CULTIVATE brings local food, arts & communities together in South Somerset. It is a creative partnership between the local arts and food sectors for the benefit of people, communities and the natural environment in, and around, Crewkerne, South Petherton, Ilminster and Chard. Rather being situated in one place (physically or online), Cultivate moves around the geographical area, offering:

- social spaces where people can meet and exchange ideas, practices and experiences;
- innovative spaces where local food and arts led strategies are co-created and implemented;
- vibrant spaces where we can deliver activities that help to build stronger and closer communities;
- dynamic spaces where we are aware of our environmental impact and responsibilities.

Figure 52: Take Art's office. Photo courtesy of Take Art.

Local Context

South Somerset is a local government district in Somerset, UK, covering an area of 370 square miles (958 km) ranging from the borders with Devon, Wiltshire and Dorset to the edge of the Somerset Levels. It has a population of approximately 158,000.

South Somerset enjoys a thriving, diverse economy, matched by the quality of life afforded by the area's outstanding rural environment. Residents and visitors are never far from beautiful countryside.

Figure 53: Map of South Somerset with the Cultivate Hub area defined by the yellow dots. Image courtesy of Take Art.

Figure Figure 54: Crewkerne; Figure 55: Chard; Figure 56: South Petherton; Figure 57: Ilminster. All image courtesy of Take Art.

With a population of 7,000, the market town of Crewkerne has its origins in Saxon times; the 15th Century parish church, St Bartholomew's, was built with the wealth of the flourishing medieval wool industry.

Surrounded by fields and hills, the town has a range of cafes, pubs and restaurants; supermarkets and small shops; and a swimming pool and gym facilities.

Chard is the southernmost town in Somerset. Lying on the A30 near the Devon and Dorset borders, it has a population of approximately 13,000. South Somerset District Council is currently working with partners to develop an ambitious strategy that will bring significant changes to Chard and the community, including proposals to boost business in the town, support events and revitalise the market.

Once enjoying great strategic importance on the Fosse Way, South Petherton is now a small town with a population of 4,500.

Ilminster takes its name from the River Ile and the Minster church dating from 1450, around which the town developed. It has a population of approximately 5,800.

The Cultivate area also covers several villages and hamlets, including Lower Stratton, Yeabridge, Misterton, North Perrot, Lopen, Seavington St Mary and Dowlish Wake. It has a wide range of assets (human, natural and capital). Cultivate engages with local Active Members (stakeholders), a diverse representation across the four communities including local residents; education; health; voluntary sector; local food; arts; governing bodies; research; service providers; and potential investors.

The Reference SIA

Our Reference SIA is 'Arts and Festivals' and our 'Role Model Good Practices' focus on the development and delivery of the Rural Touring Scheme.

The Enhancement plan will build on this work this work by bringing local food, arts and communities together.

ART & FESTIVAL

Cultivate has the potential to act as a focal point for creativity and communication about a very different way of doing business around local food, for the significant benefit to the rural community. A local food system should build community, biodiversity, healing, social justice and wellbeing. This can be made more visible, promoted and celebrated through the arts.

Bringing local arts and food together will build capacity within the local arts sector by providing new performance, festival and celebratory opportunities and engaging with local audiences and participants. This will help to bring significance to what we mean by community cohesion and resilience and help us adapt creatively to what will be a new 'normal' in all our lives.

Other relevant SIAs

LOCAL FOOD

There is a global, growing interest in local, rural food production, partly due to the long-term impact of COVID-19 which is precipitating a review of 'normal' practices. Now, more than ever, is the time to re-evaluate our relationship with food.

The local food sector constantly fights the pressures, generated by a prevailing and predominant food system, that focus on producing cheap food for the consumer. This is frequently at the expense of the environment, health and wellbeing of many players in the long supply chain. There is a need for increased understanding of these complex issues, and a commitment from policy makers and consumers to support an alternative model of food production and distribution that focuses on health, wellbeing and the environment.

6.7.2 Starting Point

CODE	ACTIONS	OBJECTIVES
RM7.1	Develop an innovative rural touring network as a way of bringing high quality, professional performing arts experiences to rural communities in community spaces.	Provide local venues in rural communities across Somerset systematic opportunities to host high quality professional touring performances; Provide opportunities to tour into rural areas and reach new audiences; Provide rural communities with access to high quality cultural events.
RM7.2	Provide opportunities for all ages and abilities to experience, participate and work in the arts within a predominantly rural context.	Actively engage individuals and groups of all ages living in rural parts of Somerset in a cultural programme in venues local to them; Give equal access to culture to rural communities as much as their urban counterparts, meaning there is equality of opportunity.
RM7.3	Develop public and local earned income funding strategies to sustain the rural touring ecology.	Secure mid and long term existence of Take Art within a combined public and private funding formula; Provide a secure base to support a rural touring infrastructure in Somerset through Take Art.
RM7.4	Marketing events in partnership with local villages to attract audience and facilitate greater community wellbeing and inclusion.	Make a broad cross section of audiences attend to rural touring events within an agreed target framework.
RM7.5	Promote rural touring opportunities to artists and companies.	Provide an economically attractive and high quality culturally diverse touring package to touring companies and artists.
RM7.6	To increase social capital and resilience by developing informal education resources for volunteer promoters and information for artists.	Make more confident and skilled promoters hosting performing arts events successfully; Make possible to companies and artists successfully coping with the logistical and technical challenges of rural touring while enjoying its benefits and opportunities.
RM7.7	Collaborate with other theatres, arts centres and arts programmers in the area to provide a joined up cultural offer.	Provide a co-ordinated collective offer to companies and artists to tour across Somerset and the wider SouthWest; Make touring in Somerset and the South West appealing to high quality established companies and artists with a proven track record.

When we established the Cultivate Hub in May 2019, we set up a Steering Group (14 people) comprising people who are part of our wider Active Members (stakeholders). Meeting quarterly, the Steering Group has co-created a draft Strategic Framework for the Hub, including cross-cutting themes; geographic focus; mission; vision; guiding principles; aims; outcomes; challenges and opportunities.

This work has been informed by our collective knowledge of the area and local government priorities, the impact of Covid-19 as well as consideration of the six RURITAGE SIAs and the other Role Models and Replicators.

With a particular focus on the relationship between local food and arts and festivals, which was a clear and natural progression for us, the key outcomes of this process include identification of three priority themes (sector integration; community benefit and communication) which align with the development of our Enhancement Plan's Objectives and Actions below.

6.7.3 Objectives of the Enhancement Plan

The Enhancement plan will provide a natural, and dynamic development of Take Art's current Role Model Actions (that focus on touring professional arts in rural areas) by bringing **local food, arts and communities** together in South Somerset.

As we developed the plan, we explored the opportunities and challenges it could address. Three themes emerged: opportunities for greater **arts and food integration** to benefit both sectors; capacity to support **community cohesion and resilience**; and the potential for the arts to **communicate and raise awareness** about health, wellbeing and environmental priorities.

As a result, **CULTIVATE** has adopted **three priority themes and objectives** and **five actions** that provide a framework for the Enhancement Plan.

Opportunities and/or open issues to address: our three PRIORITY THEMES	Specific Objectives and Description	
1. SECTOR INTEGRATION	O1	Develop more local opportunities for arts and food integration
	by responding creatively and flexibly to local needs and interests for the mutual benefit of both sectors	
2. COMMUNITY BENEFIT	O2	Creatively support community cohesion and resilience
	by using local food and arts integration to bring significance to what we mean by 'community': addressing inequalities, supporting social justice, building healing and wellbeing	
3. COMMUNICATION	O3	Promote and celebrate an alternative model of food production and distribution
	by using the arts as a resource to raise awareness about health, wellbeing and environmental priorities	

6.7.4 List of Actions

Enhancement action	Title of Enhancement action	Objective (please refer to section 1.2)
RM7.8	Bring people together through the sharing and enjoyment of local food and high-quality arts	O1, O2
RM7.9	Offer opportunities for people to learn about, and participate in, activities that lead to better health, wellbeing and environmental outcomes and generate a sense of ownership and pride	O2, O3
RM7.10	Exchange knowledge, learning and experience between the local food and arts sectors for mutual benefit in developing social innovation projects	O1, O3
RM7.11	Promote the environmental sustainability of agro-food production, packaging and selling	O1, O3
RM7.12	Disseminate good practices	O3

6.7.5 Operational Programme

Code of the action	RM7.8
Title of the action	Bring people together through the sharing and enjoyment of local food and high-quality arts
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art&Festivals; Local Food
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Social practices Rituals and festive events, Performing Arts
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	New, internal action & informed by COVID-19 brainstorming actions
Relevant RM/KFP involved	N/A
Brief description of the action	Creating new performance, festival and celebratory opportunities will offer innovative ways for people to experience the mutual benefits of bringing local food and arts together.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM7.1: Develop an innovative rural touring network as a way of bringing high quality, professional performing arts experiences to rural communities in community spaces.
Objective of the action (by the end of the project)	Produce 'Cultivate Commissions', a portfolio of artist commissions and projects that tell the local food story, delivered through a flexible, hybrid programme of 'live' and 'online' performance and participatory opportunities.
Links with other actions	The Community Participation Activity will be delivered as part of RM7.8 The digital documentation activity will be delivered as part of RM7.12 Opportunities for performance will be partly-delivered as part of RM7.11
Target of the action (by the end of the project)	Targets include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 x pilot commissions developed • 8 x pop up commissions delivered through 32 performance opportunities • 4 x event commissions delivered through 16 performance opportunities
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot Commission Development • Pop up Commissions • Event Commissions • Community Participation Workshops • Digital Documentation
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers, Growers and Producers confirmed to host and promote events and workshops include: Somerset Farmers' Markets; North Perrot Farm; Yeabridge Farm; ARK at Egwood; Flaxdrayton Farm; Somerset Local Food. • Local Artists and Companies confirmed for commissions and workshops include: aKa Dance Theatre; Wassail Theatre; Tor Theatre; Bluebirds Theatre; Carolyn Lefley (visual artist); James Bamford (dancer); Natasha Rand (visual artist); Somerset Art Works. • Local Authority Strategic support: South Somerset District Council (plus funding tbc). • Other representatives from local food & arts sectors; education & community groups; health sector; and local government will be confirmed once additional funding from Arts Council England is confirmed. We have already produced a list of potential partners, events and activities.
Beneficiaries	Local Food Sector (primary & local food producers; distribution; retailers; caterers; and consumers); Arts (individuals & organisations); Community (individuals & groups)
Timeframe	April 2021 to August 2022
Indicative costs	c. €58,000 (£50,000) spread across RM7.8, RM7.9 & RM7.12. Costs include artists' fees and travel expenses; workshop costs; marketing and access costs.
Indicative funding sources	These are spread across RM7.8, RM7.9 & RM7.12: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation Budget: c. €12,500 (£10,750) from consumables & other goods (direct costs); • Arts Council England Project Grant: c. €39,800 (£34,255) (application submitted 26-03-21). • South Somerset District Council: tbc.

Code of the action		RM7.9
Title the action	Offer opportunities for people to learn about, and participate in, activities that lead to better health, wellbeing and environmental outcomes and generate a sense of ownership and pride	
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art&Festivals; Local Food	
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Social practices Rituals and festive events, Performing Arts	
Reference RM Action/s(code and name)	New, internal action & informed by COVID-19 brainstorming actions	
Relevant RM/KFP involved	N/A	
Brief description of the action	Creative collaboration between the local food and arts sectors will help to bring significance to what we mean by community cohesion and resilience and raise awareness about health, wellbeing & environmental outcomes.	
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM7.2: Provide opportunities for all ages and abilities to experience, participate and work in the arts within a predominantly rural context. RM7.4: Marketing events in partnership with local villages to attract audience and facilitate greater community wellbeing and inclusion.	
Objective of the action (by the end of the project)	Develop a Community Participation Workshop Programme that enables people to connect with the local food story and appreciate its relationship to health, wellbeing and the environment.	
Links with other actions	Elements of this action include the Community Participation Workshops described in RM7.8 as part of 'Cultivate Commissions'	
Target of the action (by the end of the project)	Targets include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 x community workshops delivered by 5 practitioners 	
Specific activities	Community Participation Workshops eg <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doorstep Arts • Development of Apple Art • Schools' workshop programme • Farm to Fork workshops • Chard Banner Project (Somerset Art Works) • Arts, Health & Wellbeing workshop programme (hospital, health care & community settings) • Innovation challenge (see RM7.10) 	
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers, Growers and Producers confirmed to host and promote events and workshops include: Somerset Farmers' Markets; North Perrot Farm; Yeabridge Farm; ARK at Egwood; Flaxdrayton Farm; Somerset Local Food. • Local Artists and Companies confirmed for commissions and workshops include: aKa Dance Theatre; Wassail Theatre; Tor Theatre; Bluebirds Theatre; Carolyn Lefley (visual artist); James Bamford (dancer); Natasha Rand (visual artist); Somerset Art Works. • Local Authority Strategic support: South Somerset District Council (plus funding tbc). • Other representatives from local food & arts sectors; education & community groups; health sector; and local government will be confirmed once additional funding from Arts Council England is confirmed. We have already produced a list of potential partners, events and activities. 	
Beneficiaries	Local Food Sector (primary & local food producers; distribution; retailers; caterers; and consumers); Arts (individuals & organisations); Community (individuals & groups)	
Timeframe	April 2021 to August 2022	
Indicative costs	c. €58,000 (£50,000) spread across RM7.8, RM7.9 & RM7.12. Costs include artists' fees and travel expenses; workshop costs; marketing and access costs.	

Indicative funding sources	These are spread across RM7.8, RM7.9 & RM7.12: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation Budget: c. €12,500 (£10,750) from consumables & other goods (direct costs); • Arts Council England Project Grant: c. €39,800 (£34,255) (applications submitted 26-03-21). • South Somerset District Council: tbc.
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Code of the action	RM7.10
Title of the action	Exchange knowledge, learning and experience between the local food and arts sectors for mutual benefit in developing social innovation projects
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art&Festivals; Local Food
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Social practices Rituals and festive events, Performing Arts
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	New, internal action combined with RM3.1
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM3: Agro-food production in Puglia, Italy
Brief description of the action	Based on the notion that social innovation, inspiration and collaboration help to reduce marginalisation and strengthen opportunities for development in rural areas, people working in the local food and arts sectors will be actively involved in this action: bringing their own products; sharing their stories; and building friendships, trust and professional relationships.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	N/A
Objective of the action (by the end of the project)	Develop a network and Community of Practice (CoP) that will lead to collaborations and co-operation projects.
Links with other actions	Elements of this action link to activity described in RM7.11
Target of the action (by the end of the project)	Targets include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 x Farmer's Lunch at The Pig Pen attended by <30 people; • 1 x network & Community of Practice developed providing regular events for <20 local food producers & artists. • at least 1 x new social innovation project developed.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a network (small community of practice) based on Community of Practice methodology • Farmers' lunch (Pig Pen) • Farmers' dinners / inspiring talks programme (local, regional, national, international) • Innovation challenge with local students (based on Hackathon methodology) • Other potential social innovation projects (eg field / drone idea)
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers, Growers and Producers confirmed to host and/or participate in events and workshops include: The Pig Pen; Somerset Farmers' Markets; North Perrot Farm; Yeabridge Farm; Flaxdrayton Farm; Somerset Local Food. • Local Authority Strategic support: South Somerset District Council (plus funding tbc). • Other representatives from local food & arts sectors; education & community groups; health sector; and local government will be confirmed during the implementation and as the network grows.
Beneficiaries	Local Food Sector (primary & local food producers; distribution; retailers; caterers; and consumers); Arts (individuals & organisations);
Timeframe	Phase 1: Apr to Dec 2021 (Implementation Budget) Phase 2: Jan to Aug 2022 (NTL Community Fund) Phase 3: Sep 2022 to Dec 2025 (NTL Community Fund)

Indicative costs	c. €200,000 (£175,000) over 3 years spread across RM7.10 & RM7.11. Costs include venue hire; catering; marketing; speakers' fees; materials for social innovation projects. Costs from Sep 2022 onwards will include the above, plus management and co-ordination costs to run the Hub.
Indicative funding sources	<p>These are spread across RM7.10 & RM7.11:</p> <p>Implementation Budget:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c. €3,500 (£3,000) reallocated from travel & subsistence to consumables & other goods (direct costs); • c. €5,000 (£4,275) reallocated from sub-contracts to direct costs; plus reallocation from personnel costs tbc; • c. €175,000 (£150,000) The National Lottery Community Fund: Growing Great Ideas; • South Somerset District Council: tbc.

Code of the action	
Code of the action	RM7.11
Title the action	Promote the environmental sustainability of agro-food production, packaging and selling
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art&Festivals;Local Food
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Social practices Rituals and festive events, Performing Arts
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM3.5
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM3: Agro-food production in Puglia, Italy
Brief description of the action	The perception of a high-quality product is linked to appropriate packaging and interpretation of consumers' need. Image and aesthetics are fundamental for asking a premium price for a product. Adding value to the consumer experience through linked arts activity will help to address the false economy of buying cheap food (environmental impacts) and support a more sustainable local economy.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	N/A
Objective of the action (by the end of the project)	Use the arts to enhance the buying/selling experience, marketing and consumer satisfaction by telling the product's story to build support local business, connection, loyalty and emotional engagement.
Links with other actions	Elements of this action include the commissions described in RM7.8 as part of 'Cultivate Commissions'
Target of the action (by the end of the project)	Targets include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 x open farm family event at Yeabridge Farm; • 1 x performance picnic at Ham Hill; • 1 x 'Cultivate Live' mini festival.
Specific activities	Activity at Farmers' Markets; local food festivals; farm shop car parks etc Mini festivals & gatherings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • performance picnics, e.g. at Ham Hill • mini family food festival • evening food garden Activity based on sites where food is produced eg Yeabridge Farm; North Perrott, TEALS
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers, Growers and Producers confirmed to host and/or participate in events include: The Pig Pen; Somerset Farmers' Markets; North Perrot Farm; Yeabridge Farm; Flaxdrayton Farm. • Local Artists and Companies to perform at events include: aKa Dance Theatre; Wassail Theatre; Tor Theatre; Bluebirds Theatre. • Local Authority Strategic support: South Somerset District Council (plus funding to be confirmed). • Other representatives from local food & arts sectors; education & community groups; health sector; and local government will be confirmed during the implementation as the Hub's active members grow.
Beneficiaries	Local Food Sector (primary & local food producers; distribution; retailers; caterers; and consumers); Arts (individuals & organisations); Community (individuals & groups)
Timeframe	Phase 1: Apr to Dec 2021 (Implementation Budget) Phase 2: Jan to Aug 2022 (NTL Community Fund) Phase 3: Sep 2022 to Dec 2025 (NTL Community Fund)
Indicative costs	c. €200,000 (£175,000) over 3 years spread across RM7.10 & RM7.11. Costs include venue hire; catering; marketing; speakers' fees; social innovation projects materials. Costs from Sep 2022 will include the above, plus management and co-ordination to run the Hub.

Indicative funding sources	<p>These are spread across RM7.10 & RM7.11:</p> <p>Implementation Budget:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> c. €3,500 (£3,000) reallocated from travel & subsistence to consumables & other goods (direct costs); c. €5,000 (£4,275) reallocated from sub-contracts to direct costs; plus reallocation from personnel costs tbc; c. €175,000 (£150,000) The National Lottery Community Fund: Growing Great Ideas; South Somerset District Council: tbc.
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Code of the action	RM7.12
Title of the action	Disseminate good practices
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Arts & Festival Local Food
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Social practices Rituals and festive events, Performing Arts Digital Heritage
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM15.5
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM 15: Smart Rural Living Lab, Portugal
Brief description of the action	Celebrating, and being proud of, the local food and arts sectors working collaboratively is a vital part of the project; something that Somerset often underplays in this respect. This action cross-cuts all the others and will use a range of digital resources to share the story of the project and advocate its impact more widely.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	N/A
Objective of the action (by the end of the project)	Raise public awareness and share stories of Cultivate’s impact of locally, regionally, nationally and internationally through a range of offline and online events, distribution channels and advocacy tools. As this action will start later than the others, further activity (in addition to that cited below) will be confirmed during the implementation period.
Links with other actions	Elements of this action include the Digital Documentation described in RM7.8 as part of ‘Cultivate Commissions’
Target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>Targets include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> digital resource that captures, assembles, curates and shares stories that reflect the project’s activity and impact
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital Storytelling of project (Cultivate Commissions) Other Digital activity and advocacy tools to be developed
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital artists: Richard Tomlinson (confirmed) & Simon Plant (tbc) As this action focuses on disseminating good practices from across the whole project, it will potentially involve all the previously mentioned active members in contributing to telling their stories of success and impact as well as local, regional and national media.
Beneficiaries	Local Food Sector (primary & local food producers; distribution; retailers; caterers; and consumers); Arts (individuals & organisations); Other RURITAGE Partners; wider food and arts sectors; local government
Timeframe	Sept 21 to Aug 2022
Indicative costs	c. €58,000 (£50,000) spread across RM7.8, RM7.9 & RM7.12. Costs include artists’ fees (for digital storytelling); travel expenses; digital materials and resources; marketing.
Indicative funding sources	<p>These are spread across RM7.8, RM7.9 & RM7.12:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation Budget: c. €12,500 (£10,750) from consumables & other goods (direct costs); Arts Council England Project Grant: c. €39,800 (£34,255) (application submitted 26-03-21); South Somerset District Council: tbc.

6.8 RM8 Visegrád: The Town of the Living Middle Ages (VVO/EMI) Enhancement plan

Figure 62: This photo was a part of the RURITAGE photo contest. Photographer: Szónyi István

6.8.1 Background

Visegrád is located in Pest county next to the Danube surrounded by mountains. Due to the great location and strategic role of Visegrád, it has always been a popular residential area. The oldest settlement marks are from the end of the New Stone Age, Early Copper Age. The town of Hungarian kings and home town of European dynasties (Luxembourg, Anjou), was the royal center of the medieval architecture at a time of medieval Hungary. Numerous monuments (castle, lower castle and residential tower, castle walls, royal palace) can be found in the area.

The village is part of the Danube-Ipoly National Park, a protected area, which is connected to protected areas along the Danube. It includes the Danube Bend, which is one of the unique landscapes and natural value of the Danube. Visegrád is extremely rich in natural values and heritage which provide excellent opportunities in the city area for recreational and cultural tourism.

The city has protected its landscape, natural resources and heritage, since this target area is of national importance as well. A typical indicator of economic competitiveness is tourism. Providing accommodation and catering services are the main economic driving force of the tourism of Visegrád. In 2014 there were 36 restaurants and 1398 places for commercial accommodation.

Figure 63: Danube bend. Photo Source: Google Earth

Figure 64: Launch of the HUB. Photo courtesy of EMI.

Rural Heritage Hub

The Rural Heritage Hub of Visegrád is located at the Tourist Destination Office in Visegrád next to the Danube. Workshops took place in the HUB where local stakeholders (service providers, restaurant and hotel owners, participants and organizers of the International Palace Games) and citizens participated. The discussions mainly focused on the strength, challenges, opportunities and weaknesses of Visegrád and the International Palace Games and also brainstorming about the possible development paths for the city and the region.

Figure 65: Participatory workshop. Photo courtesy of EMI.

The reference SIA

ART & FESTIVAL

Visegrád is part of the Arts and Festival SIA due to the most significant local traditional activity: The International Palace Games which was first organised in 1985. One of the most significant historical events of the city has been chosen to be the theme of the events. This event was the 1335 Meeting of Kings in Visegrád when for the entire month of November 1335 in Visegrád the meeting of the Central-European kings took place: the Hungarian king Charles Robert, king of Bohemia John of Luxembourg, his son Charles, the margrave of Moravia and actual governor of the Kingdom, Polish king Casimir the Great and the plenipotentiary of the Great Master of the Teutonic Order in Prussia, as well as a number of dukes. As a result of their consultation a real golden age has started in Middle-Europe with a significant economic uplift. Visegrád is a good example of the bottom-up collaboration, because in the first year only fifty seats were enough for the audience, but the festival was so successful that within the next year the number of the audience grew to twenty times as big as in the first year.

Figure 66: Early Palace Games. Photo courtesy of Municipality of Visegrád.

In 1990. after the regime change the Municipality of Visegrád started to organize the historical festival contributing to the development of the event. In 1992. the viewing area was built for 2600 persons after that the organization of the television broadcast brought an international fame to the festival. It is essential that the local Municipality take a leading position in organizing a new festival because without this the sustainability of the festival cannot be maintained.

During the 2000s the number of the visitors coming for the Visegrád Castle games were over 30 000-40 000 and the international position was significant. The performers were mostly from Middle-Europe and on an international level from Belgium, France, Spain, Germany, Finland and the UK. Nowadays approximately a 1000 performer from 10 countries are part of the games.

Figure 67: Actors at the Palace Games. Photo courtesy of Municipality of Visegrád.

Visegrád is part of several festival associations (International Association of Historical Games (C.E.F.M.H.), also the International Palace Games is in the classified festivals of the European Festival Association (E.F.A.) and the Hungarian Festival Association) and continuously networking with other festivals and cities.

Figure 68: Young Knights. Photo courtesy of Municipality of

Other relevant SIAs

Landscape is also a relevant SIA for Visegrád, since the town is located in a rich natural landscape in the Danube bend surrounded by mountains and forests. The area is also part of the Danube-Ipoly National Park. The city and the natural areas around it provide excellent opportunities for recreational and cultural tourism.

6.8.2 Starting point

Code	Role Model Action name	Objective
RM8.1	Creation of a set of tourist packs, composed by FOOD related activities (i.e. "Middle Age Menus"), ART (i.e. Middle Age poetry performance), NATURALISTIC Activities	Empower the consciousness of the unique historical and natural heritage. Promote and increase local and regional food production Promote outdoor activities supporting the development of eco-tourism. Enhance artistic activities at historical venues (Royal Palace, Citadel)
RM8.2	Promote and support local traditional activities (branding, high quality standards, clustering, internationalization,...)	Strengthen the brand of the International Palace Games and create a complex brand for the settlement itself combining and symbolizing all the values which our town offers
RM8.3	Networking with other Festivals on the same topic: possibility of joint actions (i.e. Festival passport)	Enhance the collaboration with other similar historical festivals and enable guests to visit several events easily
RM8.4	Enhance the narrative of the place and promote the discovering of the territory through history: guided tours, thematic excursions, games, re-	Further develop the heritage-based facilities and activities to be able to offer a real one-of-a-kind experience to all visitors

	enactment	
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Municipality of Visegrád and ÉMI together held the first stakeholder workshop (Practices Repository WS) on 04.03.2019. in the local RHH. The participants all shared their connections and experiences related to the Palace Games and Visegrád. Some of them were participants of the Palace Games, and some of them were regular visitors but they all agreed, that the Palace Games is a high quality, unique and successful international event, which they are all very proud of. It was mentioned that in Hungary Visegrád was the first town to organise such an event and since then a lot of other Hungarian towns started to replicate the festival with their relevant, local historical event. One of the most important key success factor is the bottom up organisation of the event and the commitment of locals despite of the lack of stable financial resources. All participants agreed in the importance of raised topics: creation of tourist packs, promote local activities, networking with other festivals and enhance the narrative of the place.

The launch of the HUB was held 18.05.2019. Citizens also showed interest in the aims of RURITAGE, however it is important to provide them with clear information about how they and their region can benefit from the results of the project.

The participatory workshop was held on 16.12.2020. The stakeholders attending the workshop were enthusiastic and had a lot of ideas and comments. It was a fruitful discussion, every participant had opinion and comments related to the RM actions and raised new ideas as well. The workshop helped clarifying the pathway through the development of Visegrád. One of the main achievement is that participants mainly agreed in the strategic actions need to be done in order to enhance the development of Visegrád.

The elective workshop was held on 29.03.2021. The main success of the event was the agreement between participants related to the proposed actions (described in the draft Enhancement Plan). Some of the stakeholders, service providers are actively engaged in the process. Regarding the actions the proposed platform and the trainings to be held are supported by all stakeholders.

Visegrád keeps in touch with its stakeholders and include them in the process. The success of the Palace Games is the result of a bottom-up process and collaboration of different stakeholders, therefore their engagement in the co-development phase was evident.

6.8.3 Objectives of the enhancement plan

The aim of the enhancement of Visegrád is to define the strategic actions need to be done in order to enable the development of Visegrád. It is important to note that Visegrád needs to be connected to other cities of the region: Vác, Szentendre, Esztergom and the whole region should be developed together since these cities are all part of the Danube-bend. Visegrád is rich in natural and cultural heritage and has a strong bottom-up collaboration. With its many opportunities and strength, the city has a great potential in developing further.

Opportunities and/or open issues to address	Specific objectives
Accessing Visegrád and the surrounding towns and providing suitable services and touristic options can be a great challenge due to the lack of adequate knowledge about the local movements of people and visitors.	<p>O1 Improving the knowledge of the local territory</p> <p>The main aim is to establish a data gathering system covering the area of Visegrád and the surrounding cities making local cultural and natural heritage more visible and accessible for inhabitants and visitors</p>

In Visegrád and the other communities in the region the bottom-up community-based collaboration produced many great achievements including the International Palace Games. This opportunity can be further strengthened	O2	Increase collaboration through the local RHH
		The potential in the different communities could be further exploited and collaboration with citizens could be further improved and strengthened.

6.8.4 List of actions

Enhancement action	Title of Enhancement action	Objective (please refer to section 1.2)
RM8.5	Data gathering and digitalization for increasing competitiveness	O1, O2
RM8.6	Collaboration within the Rural Heritage HUB – training for the entrepreneurs of the region	O2

6.8.5 Operational programme

Code of the action	RM8.5
Title the action	Data gathering and digitalization for increasing competitiveness
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art&Festivals; Pilgrimage; Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature, Built, Artefacts Intangible – Social practices, Rituals and festive events Digital Heritage
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM1.6 Digitalization of the pilgrimage through websites, GIS maps, apps
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM1
Brief description of the action	The action aims to improve the knowledge of the spatial and economic trends of the region in order to strengthen the current traditions and activities and to further foster new attractions in the area. By creating a digital platform gathering data not only for Visegrád, but nearby rural areas in the region which all have connecting activities to offer, activities and services such as sustainable transport and cultural and leisure activities will be improved and emphasized in a sustainable way. The platform can function as a data collection and visualisation for the local RHH members and the associated entrepreneurs. The content will be decided by the RHH members, focusing on sustainable transport, tourism and cultural heritage activities, leisure activity options (including hiking routes, horse riding, etc.) and programmes. This would provide an easy tool for the RHH members for their strategy to plan and tailor their wider activities in Visegrád and the region since tourist usually visit the nearby cities also when they come to Visegrád.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM8.1 and RM8.4
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The main idea is to create a platform connecting the cities and heritage of the region and collect and offer all their relevant tourist attractions and services through a user friendly platform. The following targets are intended to be reached: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging at least 3 settlements in the region • Gathering information about more than 20 variables of the main 5 topics: accommodation, leisure activities, transportation, cultural activities, festivals and events.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One year long operation of the data earning platform • Summary and evaluation of the earned data of the platform annually <p>The platform will be a useful tool for Visegrád and the other cities' entrepreneurs and tourist services in the region involved in the action, giving the possibility to analyse the collected information and better tailor and plan adequate services for visitors. The sustainability of the platform will be provided after the project with a modest fee applicable to the platform users.</p>
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define the subjects of the data gathering (eg.: number of visitors, number of accommodations rented, use of activities) and the available sources. The main topics of the platform will be accommodation, leisure activities, culture, natural routes, programmes/festivals/specific events, transportation. • Engaging stakeholders, service providers from the region and agree with them on the established data gathering framework • Defining roles and tasks in order to achieve set targets • Gather information related to previously defines subjects, service providers will be involved also in the data gathering. • Upgrading the data gathering about the International Palace Games festival, and it's all year follower events by gathering more data about the visitors (demography, interests, time spent in Visegrád, activities tried, services used, indicator of satisfaction, etc.) as described above. These can be done by using the platform with registration forms and feedback surveys. • Providing more real time, or at least detailed digital information on sustainable transport to the region from Budapest and other cities. Gathering data on the platform about type of transportation used, destinations, time spent traveling, etc. • Detailed data collection and visualisation on cultural and leisure activities. On the platform visitors can indicate what type of activities they took part in, which would provide summarized information about the preferences of the visitors. • Regularly update the data collected and maintenance of the platform.
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TDM Visegrád (Visegrád Tourist Association) • Pro Visegrad Nonprofit Ltd. • St. George Order of Knights • MAHART PassNave Ltd. • Hotel Visegrád Ltd. • Visegrád Tours Ltd. • MNM King Matthias Museum of Visegrád
Beneficiaries	<p>The first beneficiaries are the RHH members mainly the service providers, not only related to the organization of the Palace Games, but other service providers as well including accommodations, restaurants, museums, tour guides. They can gain more accurate and detailed information about the important activities in the region. It will be also a base for an information platform in a later stage for the visitors of the area. Other beneficiaries are the visitors who receive better services and the inhabitants that can be affected by more sustainable tourism</p>
Timeframe	Start of the action – end of the action April 2021 – August 2022
Indicative costs	€12.000
Indicative funding sources	<p>15 760 €: RURITAGE budget – VVO (implementation of activities within the RHH) 7.000 €: additional funds provided by TDM Visegrád (Visegrád Tourist Association) and VVO The funding source from the RURITAGE budget (15 760 EUR) of VVO.</p>

Code of the action	RM8.6
Title the action	Collaboration within the Rural Heritage HUB – training for the entrepreneurs of the region

Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art&Festivals; Landscape; Local Food
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Social practices Rituals and festive events
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM13.3 Local Economic and Community Plan developed for the region
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM13
Brief description of the action	This action aims to establish a collaborative environment within the Hub by organizing a series of trainings. These sessions will be tailored for the local entrepreneurs working in diverse fields e.g., the touristic sector. The trainings will focus on the most critical topics affecting the region and can benefit from the improved knowledge provided by the previous actions. The most relevant fields for the trainings are the following: sustainable transport; cultural and rural tourism; local food generation and distribution; and sport and active leisure promotion.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM8.2 and RM8.4
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>This action intends to exploit the cultural, human and economic potential present in the eight settlements of the rural region by providing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A better understanding of the State of the Art derived from the data platform and visualisation (action RM 8.5) • Organising better overview and common understanding of the key success factors of the economic development • Improving the knowledge and skills of the local stakeholders by 4 half day special trainings in the 4 most interesting aspects of the economic enhancements • Sharing best practice approaches towards the citizens engagement and citizen participation through 2 best practice workshops • Enhancement of the RURITAGE Local Rural Heritage HUB by training the members and joining entrepreneurs • A better overview and strategy about the economic activities in the area • A better cooperation with the citizens • Engaging at least 50 participants for the planned 6 trainings (2 workshops and 4 half day trainings)
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging stakeholders in participating in the process • Defining the specific subject/topics, length and date of the trainings and meetings. • Organizing regular (quarterly) meetings with the main stakeholders regarding the topics identified and the trainings organization. • Organizing special half day trainings in four areas: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - conscious, sustainable and effective transport to and inside the region - extended local food production and distribution - enhancements in organisation of cultural and nature-based programme packages, improvements on Palace Games and it's side events - attractive and well-advertised leisure and sport activities • Organizing 2 best practice workshops on citizen engagement and citizens' involvement by picking up experiences from the RURITAGE RMs (RM1, RM11, RM13). • Summarizing the results and participant's feedback of the meetings, training and workshops.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TDM Visegrád (Visegrád Tourist Association) • Pro Visegrad Nonprofit Ltd. • St. George Order of Knights • MAHART PassNave Ltd. • Hotel Visegrád Ltd. • Visegrád Tours Ltd. • MNM King Matthias Museum of Visegrád

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local food manufacturers and distributors • Citizens
Beneficiaries	The eight local governments in the regions, entrepreneurs, service providers and citizens.
Timeframe	April 2021 August 2022
Indicative costs	€3.400
Indicative funding sources	3400 €: RURITAGE for external trainers Venue and necessary equipment (overhead, flipcharts) provided/sponsored by the TDM Visegrád (Visegrád Tourist Association)

6.9 RM9 Resilience in Crete Psiloritis UNESCO Global Geopark and NHMC (UOC) Enhancement plan

Figure 69: This photo was a part of the RURITAGE photo contest. Photographer: Eleana Kazila

6.9.1 Background

The Natural History Museum of the University of Crete Greece is representing in RURITAGE the area of Psiloritis UNESCO Global Geopark. The Psiloritis UGG is located in central Crete, Greece, very close to the bigger city of Heraklion and nearby to another big city, that of Rethimno. Both towns are having harbor facilities, whereas at Heraklion the main airport of the island is located. The area of geopark is semi mountainous to mountainous and is totally rural; only some small towns, that do not host more than 5.000 inhabitants do occur.

The highest mountain of the island Psiloritis (2456m) locates at the center of geopark whereas, small plateaus and depressions can be found in between mountains, where small areas with cultivated land exists. It has a great geodiversity with a large variety of rock types and landscape formations. Biodiversity is also very rich with many endemic species of flora and fauna. 56% of the geopark area is included in the Nature 2000 network. Similarly, very important archaeological, historical and religion sites are to be found in the geopark, some coming since the Minoan era.

In the area of the geopark which extents over 1272 Km2 exist 8 municipalities and 96 settlements. The total population is 46324 inhabitants (Greek Census 2011), 23.599 being female and 23.979 male. 37% of the inhabitants are considered as economically active, working on livestock raising and agriculture. About 24% of inhabitants are 65+ in age, while in National Level this percentage is 22% (Hellenic Statistic Service 2019). Just a few hundred migrants exist in the area working mainly on agricultural activities. About 30 young boys from Pakistan though are hosted at Anogia at the Youth Foundation of Greece, receiving Greek language courses and training for more than 20 years.

Psiloritis geopark was established as Nature Park in 2001 and in 2015 became a UNESCO Global Geopark. The Natural History Museum of the Univ. of Crete is the scientific coordinator of the geopark, while AKOMM Psiloritis

Figure 70: Map over the Psiloritis UNESCO Global Geopark. Image courtesy of UOC.

SA is the Management body. Through the NHMC the Geopark has developed and implemented several actions to strengthen local and visitor's resilience against nature induced disasters.

Rural Heritage Hub

The Rural Heritage HUB of Psiloritis is located at the facilities of the exhibition of the Natural History Museum of the University of Crete, which is located at the S. Venizelou Av., at the coastal zone of the town of Heraklion.

The exhibition is hosting displays on the Natural Environment and evolution of the Eastern Mediterranean with special emphasis on the protection against catastrophes. It hosts a modern earthquake simulator, special displays and exhibition. Exhibition hosts also laboratories, room for open talks, and educational activities. It is located just few hundred meters away from the town center, on a walking distance from all main attractions of the town.

Actions and meetings so far are spread between the geopark area and the nearby NHMC. The geopark includes several villages among them Anogia, where the geopark headquarters occur, with facilities to host and train people and similarly, the NHMC hosts facilities, exhibitions, tools and displays that cover all needs for training. The two places are very close to each other, just one hour drive and thus do not induce much travelling and transportations.

The activities of the Hub are thus hosted at the NHMC exhibition, but in several special cases activities were and will be organised at the Headquarters of geopark, at Anogia village, too.

Figure 71-72: The RHH of Psiloritis. Image courtesy of UOC.

The RHH of Psiloritis is supported by several type of stakeholders, including the Region of Crete, the local municipalities, local and villages' cultural organisations, Social Cooperative Enterprises, NGOs, Local Volunteer groups, Anogia Environmental Education Center, and the Cultural Institutions of Peiraeus Bank of Greece.

The reference SIA

Psiloritis hosts an impressive and varied natural heritage, the main reason for its declaration as UNESCO Global Geopark. Due to the high risk in respect to nature induced disasters it has developed with its partner, the Natural History Museum of the University of Crete several initiatives and projects aiming at raising awareness against disasters, mitigating the risk and increasing local resilience. Due to that reason, it participates as Role Model for Resilience under RURITAGE.

Other relevant SIAs

LANDSCAPE

The area of Psiloritis is dominated by the highest mountain chain of the island, the Psiloritis or Ida (ancient name) mountains. Deep valleys, mountain plateaus, gorges and steep cliffs characterise both the mountain and the lowland area, where the main agricultural activities take place. Livestock raising is the dominant activity in the mountainous area where a rich flora and fauna are concentrated; many of them being endemic of the mountains and the island of Crete. More than half of the geopark area is under the Nature 2000 network and several other smaller areas are protected due to their aesthetic and natural beauty. Strong pressures are imposed though on the landscape and natural environment, which need to be managed in a sustainable way to contribute to the local sustainable development.

LOCAL FOOD

Based on the landscape, climate and traditional procedures and practices, the people of Psiloritis produce products of superb quality related with food, knitwear, pottery, and arts. Visitors can enjoy these goods in the small villages of Psiloritis and from small shops scattered all around the area. Geopark has established a Local Quality Agreement with enterprises and local producers to further improve product quality and promote their activities. More than 60 local enterprises participate in the agreement that is further supported by other initiatives like the Friends of Psiloritis, a redeeming program for visitors of the area. A better marketing and support of local products and goods is a main target of geopark.

PILGRIMAGE

The cultural asset is also similarly or even more profound. Many archaeological sites from the Minoan to Roman period can be found with the most famous and important being the Idaion Andron Cave, the Axos, Tylissos, Monastiraki and Sivritos Minoan towns, the Zominthos laboratory and the Ancient Eleytherna town.

Similarly, a great number of religious sites are also located in the area, with many Byzantine monasteries and churches and the well Known Arkadi monastery, related to the deliberation of Crete from Ottomans. A considerable pilgrimage tourism is developing in several places related to these monuments.

ART & FESTIVAL

A great number of cultural events are organised every year, almost in every village related with traditions, religion, ethics and product delivery. However, these events are miss-connected to each other, not following similar standards and not promoted well. Many of the above-mentioned activities are very intense in some periods, and due to the lack of an overall management and consideration, they add pressure both to the landscape, ecosystems and also living environment.

After the Participative and Co-development meetings the stakeholders of the Psiloritis RHH have highlighted as of

great importance for the local rural sustainable development three other SIA's in which the present Enhancement plant seeks to envisage. These are mainly the **Landscape**, **Local Food** and **Arts & Festivals**, but it also intends to strengthen local **Resilience**, the SIA under which the geopark is acting as Role Model, especially due to the pandemics, and support **Pilgrimage** activities.

6.9.2 Starting point

Code	Role Model Action name	Objective
RM9.1	Organizing training - also using informal education methodology - to improve the resilience of local people (children, adults and elderly people, professionals, public authorities etc..)	Increase the knowledge level in respect to disasters through training
RM9.2	Develop interactive exhibitions to attract a broader audience	Create visitor's friendly tools for disaster risk mitigation
RM9.3	Development of toolkit for resilient citizens	Increase personal resilience of citizens in small communities
RM9.4	Participative mapping of the Heritage Features at risk	Safeguarding of natural and cultural heritage through participative activities
RM9.5	Support the definition of guidelines for risk assessment and mitigation actions	Better understanding of local risks and mitigation actions

During the **co-development phase**, several meetings were organised at the RHH. Aims of the first meetings were

- To inform and present some of the program's data to representatives of local authorities and stakeholders,
- to present and discuss examples on best practices of other SIAs
- to discuss on which and what kind of actions and best practices could be transferred to our territory.

Most partners also expressed interest on other SIAs, especially on rural food, art/festivals and pilgrimage. Many questions/interests arose on how they could be helped to transfer and apply practices from other SIAs.

Due to the Pandemic the **final participatory workshop** took place digitally in several steps. An online questionnaire was set to help stakeholders identify from the information they have already received, the main SIAs and best practices of other partners that could help rural development of Psiloritis. Following the results of these questionnaires, a final discussion took place which refined the interest of the area.

Among the SIAs presented the participants gave priority first in the Landscape management (8), then in Local Products (6) and finally at Art and Festivals (4). The same was depicted at the best practices that appeared attractive and suitable to them. Although we had already chosen since February some actions, these were further enriched and were send in advance to all participants including action from one Additional RM. One further action was added in discussions.

In total 15 actions were finally presented and discussed and these were presented in the online google form, where each of the participants had to assess how useful/relative it was on a scale from 1(no) to 5 (very much). After assessment 7 of the actions were chosen by the majority of the participants (receiving 13, 11, and 9 votes). After collecting these data, B2B meetings were organised with some crucial stakeholders who are dealing with territorial planning and implementation and training. The results of all meetings were then analysed revealing the necessity to engage if possible, actions related at least to the two more favourable SIAs, i.e. Landscape Management, Local Food and Arts and Festivals, and if possible actions on Pilgrimage and Resilience.

After these B2B meetings the final table of most preferable actions that should be engaged in the Enhancement

plan of Psiloritis was determined, including the three more favourable actions (RM12-1, RM13-3 and RM3-4) and several more as candidate too (RM8-4, RM10-2, RM18-2).

6.9.3 Objectives of the enhancement plan

The area of Psiloritis UNESCO Global Geopark in collaboration with its partners has established a strong attitude on local resilience mainly against natural induced disasters. Although it is located in one of the most touristic islands of Europe and hosts a rich natural and cultural heritage, local development is not at the level it deserves to be. Local authorities and partners seek under this Enhancement plan to enhance and promote local natural and cultural heritage, together with the excellent quality products, and transform them into a strong and recognizable development tool, that will raise local proud and improve well being of inhabitants and visitors.

Opportunities and/or open issues to address	Specific objectives	
<p>In Psiloritis wealth natural environment coexists for thousands of years with human presence, adding particular value to its landscape. Though, the natural environment facies certain pressure from modern human activities, whereas its potential to support local sustainable development has not been totally exploited. Being a UGGp Psiloritis has great opportunities to invest on its intact natural landscape to support better living conditions for its inhabitants and better and safer experiences to its visitors.</p>	O1	State here your first objective
		<p>Develop better living conditions for inhabitants and provide safer and more enriched experiences to the visitors by conserving natural environment and promoting Psiloritis unique landscape.</p>
<p>The area of Psiloritis located in the mountains and in a very rich natural environment produce superb quality local products (agricultural, diary, cultural) that do not receive the value they deserve and also are not promoted and supported properly. This fact influences considerably the local income and economy.</p>	O2	State here your second objective
		<p>The support of local sustainable development through the identification, valorisation, enhancement and marketing of local agricultural, diary and cultural products.</p>
<p>Long lasting history and traditions in the area of Psiloritis are expressed through uncountable local events and activities, spread all over the seasons, and covering all topics of history, religion, and social relationships. However, as they are not coordinated, lacking certain quality standards, not promoted properly, and not participating in tourism packages, these events are an unexploited treasure.</p>	O3	State here your third objective
		<p>Reveal and exploit the value and development potential of culture and social life of Psiloritis by raising quality and improve management of cultural and social events.</p>
<p>The COVID-19 pandemic induced several risks and considerable impacts on the operation and economy of Psiloritis area.</p>	O4	State here your fourth objective
		<p>Increase local resilience in respect to pandemics and other non-</p>

Main sectors affected were the visitors' centres and entrance points, the local products and services, and public activities. However, it is possible that pandemics in future might induce new risks not identified yet.	identified threats
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6.9.4 List of actions

Enhancement action	Title of Enhancement action	Objective (please refer to section 1.2)
RM9.6	Use modern technologies (Virtual maps, tours and VR) to enhance and promote natural and cultural heritage of Psiloritis	O1, O2, O3, O4
RM9.7	Establish local participative processes to manage and conserve local landscape and heritage	O1, O3, O4
RM9.8	Public events to strengthen local identity and proud based on the natural and cultural values of the area	O1, O2, O3, O4

6.9.5 Operational programme

Code of the action	RM9.6
Title the action	Use modern technologies (Virtual maps, tours and VR) to enhance and promote natural and cultural heritage of Psiloritis
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage, Food, Landscape, Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature, Built, Artefacts Intangible – Knowledge and practices Digital Heritage
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM12-1: Promote joint actions (also through PPP) to enhance heritage resources and create an internationally recognized brand RM3-4: Definition of standards of quality for the selected products RM8-4: Enhance the narrative of the place and promote the discovering of the territory through history
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM8, RM3, RM12, R2(?) / TECNALIA, UNIBO, Savonia UAS
Brief description of the action	The action will take benefit from existing databases and digital products to further promote local natural and cultural environment through the production of new 360o Digital Panoramas, development of thematic story telling maps (one for geosites, one for Byzantine churches and one for local products), produce at least on VR panorama and develop layouts, posters and images for promotional needs at social media. Virtual tours are expected to serve the promotional and marketing needs in case of lockdowns. It will be developed in three phases: Data collection and elaboration; Product development; Assessment and monitoring.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation of GEOIN project, creation of an Interactive Geopark Map. Psiloritis Friends Initiative with local producers and services providers.

Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>Better and more efficient promotion of cultural and natural heritage, as well as products of Psiloritis through the innovative digital tools and means that will serve to overcome obstacles induced by pandemics.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a strategy for digital promotion • Development of at least 3 story telling maps (geosites, churches, local food producers) • Development of at least 1 VR tour along Psiloritis • Production of at least 300 posters/layouts and print a few of them
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a local strategy for the digital promotion of the geopark • Develop virtual tours for geosites, local churches, local products • Develop a VR tour for Psiloritis landscape • Develop promotional material for social media use
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p><u>NHMC-UoC</u>: development of whole actions with project hours plus additional own working hours,</p> <p><u>AKOMM Psiloritis SA</u>: with additional working hours, collection of and offer of data and communications with local stakeholders,</p> <p><u>Psiloritis Friends Network</u>, <u>Local Municipalities</u>, <u>ANDROIDUS</u> project, <u>Cultural and other local associations</u>: Offer of information and data</p>
Beneficiaries	Domestic and foreign visitors, children and youngsters, schools, people with kinetic disabilities
Timeframe	<i>Start of the action – end of the action</i> 3/2021-2/2022
Indicative costs	TOTAL Budget: 1300,00 €
Indicative funding sources	<u>RURITAGE</u> and own resources

Code of the action	RM9.7
Title the action	Establish local participative processes to manage and conserve local landscape and heritage
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Landscape, Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	<p>RM10-2: Promote a participative process in order to create a cohesive resilient community (educational activities and event, monitoring and rescue teams, etc.)</p> <p>RM13-3: Local Economic and Community Plan developed for the region</p> <p>RM18-2: New well-functioned cross-sectoral partnerships created working with multi-problem-oriented approaches</p>
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM10, RM13, RM18 / Consulta Europa, Uni. Plymouth,
Brief description of the action	In collaboration with local communities, schools and authorities the action will develop policies, strategies, and activities for the better management and conservation of the landscape with emphasis on geoheritage, Nature 2000 areas and waste management, whereas a risk assessment revision will be contacted to identify threats and risks, to living and non-living environment, even in cases of pandemics
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategy of integrated development of UNESCO designations in Crete • Psiloritis Friends Initiative with local producers and services providers.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Conserve and manage local landscape and heritage based on local practices and state of the art methodologies.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 3 exchange/virtual visits in other RMS • Organisation of at least 3 local participatory workshops with local stakeholders, producers etc., Expected participants 3 X 20 = 60 • Revision of existing risk assessment study • Campaign to raise awareness on waste disposal and proper use of local materials (traditional means vs plastic) • Design and implementation of at least 10 Green Waste points at local schools • At least one educational product for local and visiting schools
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchange visits to other RMS • New risk-assessment study under the threat of pandemics • Organisation of local participatory meetings with inhabitants, local farmers, tourism operators • Raise awareness on waste management along geopark area • Design and establish pilot Green waste collecting points in local schools • Educational programs for local schools
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p><u>NHMC-UoC</u>: organisation and implementation of most actions with project hours and other costs, plus additional working hours</p> <p><u>AKOMM Psiloritis SA</u>: co-organisation of participatory and communication actions with own working hours</p> <p><u>Anogia Environmental Education Centre</u>: co-organisation of school activities and educational project with own working hours</p> <p><u>Local Municipalities, local Schools, Psiloritis Friends Network, Municipalities, Cultural and other local associations Local Farmers</u>: Support in implementation and participation in most actions</p>
Beneficiaries	Local residents, Visitors of geopark, Municipalities, Cultural and other local associations
Timeframe	<i>Start of the action – end of the action</i> 6/2021 – 8/2022
Indicative costs	Total Budget: 12600,00€
Indicative funding sources	<u>RURITAGE and own resources</u>

Code of the action	RM9.8
Title the action	Public events to strengthen local identity and proud based on the natural and cultural values of the area
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Food, Arts & Festivals, Landscape, Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Social practices Rituals and festive events
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM12-1: Promote joint actions (also through PPP) to enhance heritage resources and create an internationally recognized brand RM8-4: Enhance the narrative of the place and promote the discovering of the territory through history
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM12, RM8, PM6 / Consulta Europa, ICLEI, CRS
Brief description of the action	Organisation of public events to raise awareness, increase knowledge and inform inhabitants and visitors on the value of natural and cultural heritage of Psiloritis area, as well as on natural and non-natural induced risks.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a temporary and mobile exhibition on Psiloritis geopark. • Organisation of European Geoparks Week

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geopark and Municipal summer public events, • Geopark's annual EGN Week, • Geopark Sport events developed by stakeholders, • Promotional material of Geopark developed by AKOMM
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>Raise awareness on the value of local heritage and strengthen local identity and proud through public events and activities, as well as increase resilience of local inhabitants and producers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a local strategy for heritage enhancement and promotion • Organisation of at least 20 public events, for each event more than 50 participants are expected. • Implementation of Serious Game in at least three Municipalities • Organisation of two public exhibitions about geopark • Organisation of at least 6 field trips for local inhabitants in various places in geopark with 6 X 30 = 180 participants • Organisation of common events with other geoparks (at least two)
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a local strategy to enhance and promote local cultural, social and sport events • Public talks, events and demonstrations on local heritage and local resilience • Implementation of Serious game in several villages • Public exhibitions • Organisation of field trips for inhabitants in special geosites of geopark. • Public and digital events to promote local sustainable development in Greek Geoparks
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p><u>NHMC-UoC:</u> organisation and implementation of most actions with project other costs and additional own working hours</p> <p><u>AKOMM Psiloritis SA:</u> co-organisation of dissemination and outreach actions with own working hours and means (exhibition, poster, printed material)</p> <p><u>NIDEA Cooperative:</u> co-organisaiton of publica events with support, participation and own working hours</p> <p><u>IDAION Network, Local Municipalities, Psiloritis Friends Network, ANDROIDUS Project, Cultural and other local associations:</u> Co-organisation, support and participation in most outreach actions and public events</p>
Beneficiaries	Local Inhabitants
Timeframe	<i>Start of the action – end of the action</i> 6/2021 – 8/2022
Indicative costs	Total Budget: 7200,00€
Indicative funding sources	<u>RURITAGE and own resources</u>

6.10 RM10 Human Resilience in South Iceland Katla UNESCO Global Geopark (KATLA) Enhancement plan

Figure 73: Photo courtesy of Katla Geopark.

6.10.1 Background

Katla is a UNESCO Global Geopark situated in central south Iceland, covering the area of the three municipalities of Skaftárhreppur, Mýrdalshreppur and Rangárþing-eystra. The Geopark's geography is varied, being surrounded by black volcanic beaches in the south and highlands in the north. Ice-capped active volcanoes, palagonite mountains and black beaches are some of the features attracting many tourists yearly. This unique area with its high geographical diversity of great geological heritage presents high risks related to various natural hazards, such as volcanic eruptions, earthquakes, glacial outburst floods and severe storms.

Figure 74: Map showing the location of Katla Geopark in Iceland and the area that the Geopark covers. Image courtesy of Katla Geopark.

Rural Heritage Hub

The hub was initially located at the venue of Kirkjubæjarstofa in the village of Kirkjubæjarklaustur. It was however moved last year to Katla centre, located in the village of Vík. Katla centre is fully equipped with all necessities and as an already established gathering point for local networks it is a well-suitable hub. Further benefits of having the hub in Katla centre are that it has a meeting space and a lecture space, it hosts the Katla Geopark educational exhibitions, has a maritime museum and serves as the history museum for the Municipality of Mýrdalshreppur. Furthermore, as it is located within the old town of Vík, it is perfectly located as the old town is both a gathering point for the locals as well as tourists. Having the Hub in Vík also comes with benefits, as it is located almost in the centre of the Geopark, with about one hour driving time from the other two towns within the Geopark. The RHH also involves five types of stakeholders including the municipalities, local food producers, tourist companies, individuals, and state-run agencies.

Figure 75- 76: Pictures of the RHH located within Katla centre. The picture on the left shows the building of Brydebud, which houses the RHH and Katla centre, and the one on the right shows the meeting space for the RHH. Image courtesy of Katla Center.

The reference SIA

RESILIENCE

The role of intangible and tangible heritage is of great strength when increasing awareness regarding survival of natural hazards. Throughout history, this has been traditionally done through storytelling. Today, Katla UNESCO Global Geopark has established a network with municipalities and governmental agencies to provide guidance and assistance to local population and tourist on how to protect themselves and cooperate with rescue squads during and after a disaster event. This is done with the same principles as the traditional way, with the help of storytelling.

Other relevant SIAs

LOCAL FOOD

Agriculture has been the main industry within the Geopark for centuries. Most of the farms have been small sheep farms and/or dairy farms, with many having other farm animals as well, such as poultry and pigs. In the most recent year, other types of food production have started. These other types include farm grown salmon, honey, grain, rapeseed and rapeseed oil, barley ext. These producers are usually small, and it can be difficult for them to get their products on the market and/or market them to the locals and tourists.

PILGRIMAGE

Pilgrimage, or more precisely in Katla Geopark's case, old traveling routes, play a large role in the intangible heritage of the region. Traditionally, the area has been very difficult to traverse, and it was not until after the middle of last century that the whole region was connected by roads. The reasons for the difficulty are the numerous glacial rivers that flow from the glaciers in the highland and down to the lower areas in the south. The rivers change their paths frequently and glacial outburst floods occur every few years, often destroying roads and bridges. Before bridges were built over the rivers, during the middle and latter part of the 20th century, these rivers were crossed using horses, a tradition that is now disappearing and the heritage of those types of river crossings needs to be preserved. Other routes that are disappearing are for example many regional and local paths farmers used to travel between farmlands and grazing areas and where farmers went to gather sheep from the highlands in the autumn. The knowledge of these routes is preserved in the minds of people who lived through these times, a generation that is getting older, and the need to preserve this knowledge for the future is paramount.

LANDSCAPE

Landscape plays a large role in everyday life within Katla Geopark and is a precious commodity due to tourism. In the past, the landscape has been both a friend and a foe, as some landscapes have offer protection against the elements, while others have caused exposure to the elements or are the cause of geohazards. Three main

landscape units are within Katla Geopark, Highlands, lowlands and the boundary area between the highlands and the lowlands. The preservation of these landscape units is paramount, as they are threatened by climate change, increased industry, and over-tourism, but the importance to educate people about them and their history is also important.

MIGRATION

Due to increased tourism in Iceland in the recent years, migration of workers has increased greatly in Iceland. The three municipalities that make up the Geopark have now high number of immigrants and migrants, many of whom do not speak Icelandic and some not English. The increased foreign population has brought a lot of good things, such as different cultures, cuisine, and way of thinking. The problem, however, is that Icelandic society did not respond to the growing population as fast as the growth was. Therefore, vital information's on several topics, for example geohazards, are not readily available for those who do not speak Icelandic and only partially available in English. It is therefore important, for the safety of everyone who lives within the area, to make vital information more readily available for all.

6.10.2 Starting point

Code	Role Model Action name	Objective
RM10.1	Discover and diffuse the traditional storytelling and superstitions as means to understand the natural environment and to promote the place ownership.	Gather the information and make available. See if it is possible to determine if the stories and legends preserved and facilitated transfer of vital knowledge leading to increased resilience. To implement this information into various existing and ongoing projects.
RM10.2	Promote the awareness of the natural features acting as hazard barriers.	Spreading the knowledge of natural barriers and landscapes, how to recognize your immediate surroundings and use them in case of hazard. To implement a method to educate visitors and inhabitants on how to do the same and simultaneously teach them to respect the nature and to take mitigating actions in case of naturally occurring hazardous situations (including weather).
RM10.3	Foster the knowledge and awareness of the link between the traditional construction techniques and the natural environment.	Map unsuitable areas for new construction and vice-versa. Determine how communities and government within our area are mitigating the risks related to new construction and the natural environment. To get an overview of barrier constructions and other mitigative measures that have been implemented.
RM10.4	Promote a participative process to create a cohesive resilient community (educational activities and events, monitoring and rescue teams, etc.).	The action is well implemented already country wide. Our aim would be to figure out how/why it developed and if there is a way to explain it in a way that others might start facilitating their own process or adapt selected actions or methods. Ideally, we would like to offer

		education on natural hazard mitigation in our soon-to-come information and educational center located under the Eyjafjöll mountains at Thorvaldseyri.
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The co-development phase for Katla Geopark started in August 2020 when the Geopark selected 10 Role model actions from which the Geopark’s stakeholders could choose from to implement in the Enhancement Plan. The phase consisted of two workshops and three more once the actions had been selected.

The first workshop, the repository workshop, was held online, due to COVID-19 crisis, on the 7th of October 2020. The aim of the workshop was to familiarize then current stakeholders to the RURITAGE project and to introduce it to new and potential stakeholders. The ten actions that the Geopark had selected were also introduced on the workshop and discussion on what could be done with each action took place.

The second workshop, the participatory workshop was held on the 14th of October. The workshop was also held online on Zoom due to COVID-19. The workshop started out with a discussion about each chosen action and once the discussions were over the stakeholders voted on which actions to implement in the Enhancement Plan. Four actions received the strongest vote, with three actions being selected to have in the Enhancement plan and to include the fourth one in one of the three actions that were chosen. The three actions that were chosen were RM10.7 Research and preserve old travel paths within the Geopark, RM10.8: increase the knowledge and preparedness of individuals for natural hazards within the Geopark, and RM10.9: create a common vision for local businesses and producers. The fourth action, to create themed trails through the Geopark, was included in RM10.7.

Once the three actions were chosen, an online round table workshop has been held for each action, where stakeholders discussed what to implement in each action and how to implement it.

6.10.3 Objectives of the enhancement plan

Opportunities and/or open issues to address	Specific objectives	
Flow of information and respond to natural hazards and disaster is one of the strengths of the area. There are however a few weaknesses within the current system that need to be addressed. Those weaknesses are lack of flow of information in other languages than Icelandic. The information exists but people who move to the area either do not know it exist or do not know where to find the information.	O1	Increase flow of information about geohazards to the public and tourists within the Geopark
	The overall objective is to increase the flow of already made information for both locals and tourists about potential natural hazards in the area and how to respond to them.	
The need for localized training in responding to emergencies is also a weakness. Trainings are held every few years and about 10% of the population has ice-Sar training, but due to high turnover of people within the Geopark, many people miss those trainings. Evacuation plans are available but not accessible. Information for tourist does not exist, but is being made, and it needs to be guaranteed that that information reaches tourists.	O2	Increased training for the public
	The overall objective is to increase the readiness of the local people to respond to natural hazards. The respond focus is both people’s readiness when and if a natural hazard occurs and how to respond to it. The objective is also to find ways to facilitate evacuation of areas, especially those who have many tourists, by having better information, higher visibility of evacuation plans, local respond to help the Ice-Sar units and so on.	

<p>Evacuation plans are available but not accessible. Information for tourist does not exist, but is being made, and it needs to be guaranteed that that information reaches tourists. There is a need to guide people, especially tourists, who do not know what to do in case of an emergency, for example where to go, how to react and so on.</p>	O3 Find a way to help with the evacuation of tourists to pre-determined places in case of an eruption in Katla	<p>The overall objective is to increase the readiness of the local people to respond to natural hazards. The respond focus is both people's readiness when and if a natural hazard occurs and how to respond to it. The objective is also to find ways to facilitate evacuation of areas, especially those who have many tourists, by having better information, higher visibility of evacuation plans, local respond to help the Ice-Sar units and so on.</p>
<p>Governmental and local agencies work well together, as well as most companies within each community. There is however often a lack of cooperation between companies in different communities and often with the Geopark and the companies themselves.</p>	O4 Increase the co-operation within the Geopark	<p>The overall objective is to get the companies to work better with each other and with the Geopark on common policies and goals. To try to link the companies better with the Geopark and to ensure companies are represented by the Geopark in the right way. Also, try to get manufactures and tourist companies to represent the Geopark in their products and service, and in return the Geopark will represent their products and service.</p>
<p>Preservation of the cultural heritage of the area is a strength, but the less known cultural heritage often gets overlooked. One example of them are old travel paths that are not part of the old "highway" system. The area needs new ways to be discovered and ways to keep people in the area over longer period.</p>	O5 Mapping lesser-known heritage features	<p>The overall objective is to try to preserve the knowledge about any travel paths that were in use within the Geopark during the early 20th century. The preservation consists of gathering stories, information, photos, and mapping of these paths. The paths can be any kind of paths, used for any activity, but the focus is on smaller paths, not the main "highways", as they have already been mapped.</p>
<p>There are several hiking paths within the Geopark, but many of them are outdated and made before tourism started in the area. There is a need to make new hiking paths and themed trails, preferably with link to natural and/or cultural heritage.</p>	O6 Create new hiking paths or themed trails in the Geopark	<p>The overall objective is to select certain routes, that had been researched in objective 5, and prepare the material about them for publication so it can be used for hiking paths and/or themed trails.</p>
<p>There is a need for new recreational opportunities within the Geopark to keep people longer in the area</p>	O7 Create new recreational activities, or educational recreational activities.	<p>The overall objective is to create new recreational opportunities within the Geopark, other than new hiking paths and themed trails. The goal for these new recreational opportunities is that they will be educational as well.</p>

6.10.4 List of actions

Enhancement action	Title of Enhancement action	Objective (please refer to section 1.2)
RM10.5	Research and preserve old travel paths within the Geopark	O1, O2, O3
RM10.6	Increase the knowledge and preparedness of individuals for natural hazards within the	O4

	Geopark	
RM10.7	Create a common vision for local businesses and producers	O5, O6, O7

6.10.5 Operational programme

Code of the action	RM10.7
Title the action	Research and preserve old travel paths within the Geopark
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage, landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Intangible – Knowledge and practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM1-5, RM2-3, RM8-4, RM11-1
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM1, ACIR
Brief description of the action	The action will try to gather information about old travel paths within the Geopark. The travel paths can be any paths used by people, such as paths leading between two farms, to the highlands for sheep herding, to the water well for farms and so on. They do not need to be major travel paths. This knowledge is not collected during archaeological mapping nor it is a part of “örnefnaskráningu” (place names and why they are named that way has been collected from all Icelandic farmsteads). This information will therefore disappear soon if it is not preserved, as this knowledge almost only exists with the elderly generations living within the Geopark, farmers and former farmers. The action goal is therefore to collect the information, stories, locations, and other information, from the local population and map the routes. Once that has been done, that information might prove useful in implementing other actions, such as mapping of lesser known-heritage sites connected to the travel paths, new hiking paths and new themed trails through the Geopark. Another aspect of the action is to create new recreational activities within the Geopark, that can have a link to old travel paths.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM10.1 and RM10.3.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The first objective of the action is to preserve the knowledge, cultural heritage if you will, about paths and routes that were used before the modern age in Iceland and road construction started. Document stories and descriptions of these routes and paths, take photographs of them and collect the data in a database. The third objective is to create new recreational activities within the Geopark, such as to create three new hiking paths and two themed trails, potentially using information from the first objective, have treasure hunts for children and reach 50 children with the treasure hunt, and set up 3 earth caching locations, if feasible.
Specific activities	Please list here using bullet point the specific activities needed to complete the action and to reach the defined objective and target. Please also include dissemination steps that you plan for the action. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gather information from people about old travel paths. - Advertise for this information, speak to people who have this information • Map old travel paths, using GPS and/or ArcGIS. - walk the routes with a handheld GPS, map the routes in ArcGIS, using the GPS routes or the information gathered • Create a closed database for the information and the maps. • Dissect the information to see if it can be used for cultural enhancement, exhibitions, tour ext. • Create new hiking paths ideas from the information and/or themed.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create treasure hunts ideas for children set up treasure hunt games. • Create stamps and traveling books to have in selected locations, children can stamp their traveling books when they travel between the selected locations. • Geocaching with different difficulty level.
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	The Cultural heritage agency – guidance, Skogasafn Museum – preserve parts of the information gathered, dissect part of the information, Katla centre – create treasure hunts for children, the three municipalities -, Katla Geopark and individuals – mapping and gathering information, Katla Geopark – create new hiking paths ideas and themed trails. Everyone – Geocaching.
Beneficiaries	Skogasafn museum, the three municipalities, cultural heritage, Katla Geopark, children, tourists.
Timeframe	Start of action – 1st of March 2021, end of action – 1st of September 2022
Indicative costs	500€: equipment cost (the GPS)
Indicative funding sources	Geopark’s own resources, stakeholders’ resources, grant applications.

Code of the action	RM10.8
Title the action	Increase the knowledge and preparedness of individuals for natural hazards within the Geopark
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Resilience, migration
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Intangible – Knowledge and practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM9-1, RM9-3
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM9
Brief description of the action	The action aims to increase the knowledge, awareness, and the preparedness of individuals regarding natural hazards. There is already an established network in Iceland, that the department of civil protection and emergency management oversees. There is, however, a need to make that information more accessible, especially for non-Icelandic speaking people and tourists. This action plans to make this material more readily available, find a way to increase the awareness of people about the material and encourage them to read it. The action also aims to try to increase the amount of training exercises responding to natural hazards for locals, readily available list of equipment people should have easy access to and better signage to facilitate evacuations of certain areas. This action will be developed and carried out only with the permission and full cooperation with the Department of Civil protection and Emergency Management. The objectives and the specific activities might therefore change to be better adapted to the requirements of the agency.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM10.2
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The target is to increase the awareness and accessibility of information of geohazards within Katla Geopark, both to locals and tourists. This will be done by facilitating access for people to the information that is already available by setting up a sub-page on Katlageopark.is/ where all the available information will be gathered. Furthermore, 1 pdf brochure will be made, with information about natural hazards, which will be in at least 2 languages. This brochure will be made available online and the target is that everyone that moves into the area receives one, as a part of a larger project of welcoming in new residence into the area. The brochure can also serve as a guide for tourists regarding natural hazards within the Geopark. Another objective is to increase the readiness of the residence of Vik village to eruptions in Katla volcano. There the target is to have annual information meetings on the status of Katla volcano and regular training exercises for evacuating the village. Furthermore, it is the target to make evacuation posters readily available for people who move to the village and set up 3

	<p>signs that will facilitate the evacuation of tourists from the village. Finally, a pre-made emergency natural disaster bag will be made, using list from the department of civil protection and hazard management, and the target is to get the Ice-sar unit of Mýrdalur to sell those bags to residence.</p>
<p>Specific activities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up a webpage on the Geopark webpage about natural hazard, where all information about them is gathered in one place, easily accessible and in at least two languages. What needs to be done is gather the information that is available, mostly from the department of Civil protection, and organize them more readily for the area within the Geopark and publish it on the webpage, in both Icelandic and English. • Get the municipalities and the Department of Civil Protection to have more information meetings and trainings for the public, in English as well. – What needs to be done is to have a meeting with the Department of Civil protection, which will happen after Covid is over (their request) and see if funds are available for this project. Once that is clear, the Department can facilitate the events with the help of the municipalities. • Re-publish/re-make brochures (pdf) about the evacuation plan for the area within the Geopark – possibly one for each town. – Once the information is collected for the webpage, the information can be broken down into what needs to be available for a brochure, rest will be done with a QR code. A new evacuation plan is being made for the town of Vík, so once that is completed it can be integrated into the brochure. Alternatively, the brochures that already exist can be re-published. • Increase the number of languages the information is in. – several people have volunteered to translate the brochures to their language but needs to be validated by the Department of civil protection. • Create an Information booklet/packet for people who move into the area. – part of another program that the municipality of Mýrdalshreppur is already involved with. This will be done at the same time as the two previous points and is the same data. • Increased availability and visibility of evacuation and respond brochures for tourists – distribute the brochures once they are made. Talk to hotels, hostels ext., and get them to have the brochures readily available. • Ensure the availability of the evacuation poster for Vík, teach people how to use it. Do this in co-operation with agencies responsible for the poster, Víkverja ice-sar unit. The Department of civil protection needs to create new evacuation posters, and then the municipality of Mýrdalshreppur and the Víkverja ice-sar unit will oversee the training and distribution of the evacuation poster. This is one of the matters that will be discussed on the face-to-face meeting with the Department of civil protection. • Emergency bag – create a list of everything a household should have in case of an emergency / natural disaster. The information needs to be gathered and published on the webpage of the Geopark and in the pdf brochure. Víkverja ice-sar unit will be contacted and the idea of selling premade emergency bags will be discussed. • Signs that tell people that they are within an area that is potential hazard zone for natural hazards such as eruptions. The Road agency and the municipalities will be contacted about this idea, as well as the Department of civil protection, and if they like it, they will implement it.
<p>Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution</p>	<p>Department of Civil Protection and Emergency Management: The department needs to approve everything that will be done. The three municipalities: Help with the project visibility, The three Ice-Sar units of the municipalities: Oversee training and information meetings if they happen. The Geopark: Gather the information about natural hazards for its area, publish it.</p>

	Assist as possible in other aspects.
Beneficiaries	Department of Civil Protection and Emergency Management, the three municipalities, the three Ice-Sar units of the municipalities, the police, communities within the Geopark, especially the village of Vík, tourists, people who move into the area.
Timeframe	Start of the action – 7th of April, end of the action – End of the RURITAGE Project. Hopefully this action, once it is established, will continue for years to come. The work with the Department of civil protection will not start until after Covid-19.
Indicative costs	Not known yet, depends on the extent of the actions that the Department of Civil protection is willing and able to make and other stakeholders.
Indicative funding sources	The Geopark will fund the webpage and the pdf brochure. Depending on the situation, most funding could come through the state, if not then through the municipalities.

Code of the action	RM10.9
Title the action	Create a common vision for local businesses and producers
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage, local food
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature, Built Intangible – Social practices Rituals and festive events
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM1-1, RM3-1, RM2-3
Relevant RM/KFP involved	R1
Brief description of the action	Try to create a better cooperation between the companies in the Geopark and with the Geopark. Have everyone working together towards the same goal. One way to increase the cooperation is to establish a cooperation project in each town, based on the model of Vikunited that has already been established in the Town of Vik. The project consists of restaurants advertising each other openings hours and what is available. The project is being expanded as well to include the cultural heritage of each restaurant. This project is largely focused on Icelandic tourists, but will help with tourism in general.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	None
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Setting up a Vikunited project in Hvolsvöllur and Rangárþing-eystra municipality Setting up a Vikunited project in Kirkjubæjarklaustur and Skaftárhreppur municipality Supporting the Vikunited project in Vík Increasing the cooperation between the companies and local producers and the Geopark, by having at least 4 meetings per year and other cooperation events (these events have not been outlined yet) Set up a food trail within the Geopark
Specific activities	Please list here using bullet point the specific activities needed to complete the action and to reach the defined objective and target. Please also include dissemination steps that you plan for the action. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the co-operation of companies within the Geopark by setting up a joint program that links them together and advertises each other. That program will increase the accessibility of information about the services and activities within each municipality/town/the Geopark/areas. The information can be accessed at each company, online for example on the webpage of the Geopark (and the municipalities, VisitVik ext.). • Setting up project management in Hvolsvöllur and Kirkjubæjarklaustur for the project, already established in Vík. • Recruit companies to the project within each municipality – goal is to have minimum 5 companies in each municipality.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand the project to museums and exhibitions. • Continuous update of the posters, changing opening hours and new companies involved. • Increase the visibility of the cultural and historical heritage of restaurants (and other types of companies), where they cover the history of their businesses and the buildings they are located in. • Strengthen the involvement of local artists, producers and geotourism companies with the Geopark, through various methods such as hosting events, producing common marketing materials, hosting festivals, etc.
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Companies within the Geopark, many of whom are stakeholders – join Vikunited project in their municipality and participate in it.</p> <p>The three municipalities – post the poster of the project on their webpage and/or their visit-webpage.</p> <p>The Geopark - help to implement and maintain the project in each municipality, publish the project poster on its webpage. Help companies out with carrying out the project.</p>
Beneficiaries	The Geopark, the companies, tourists, and local people
Timeframe	Start of the action – 7 th of April. end of the action – 1 st of October 2021
Indicative costs	100€
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE: 100€ printing costs

6.11 RM11 Austrått and Ørland landscape (NMBU) Enhancement plan

Figure 77: This photo was a part of the RURITAGE photo contest. Photographer: Oda Leth-Jøssing

6.11.1 Background

The Ørland municipality sits on a peninsula in Sør-Trøndelag on the west coast of Norway, with Norwegian Sea to the west and Trondheim fjord to the east. Brekstad is the municipal centre of Ørland. Austrått is an ancient noble property situated in the municipality of Ørland. The place has a rich cultural history, as well as unique natural characteristics.

The landscape of Ørland peninsula is mostly open and flat, facing the sea at three sides and connecting to the mainland on the northern side. Comparing to the inland climate, Ørland has a relatively mild temperature.

Figure 78, 79, 80: The cultural landscape of Austrått. Photo courtesy of NMBU.

Rural Heritage Hub

The Austrått Rural Heritage Hub is situated in Ørland Cultural Centre in Brekstad. It was established as a municipal enterprise focusing on three areas of interest: history, nature and culture. Ørland Cultural Centre already has the function of networking local and regional governments which makes it an optimal place to gather stakeholders for the hub.

Figure 81: The RHH is located in Ørland Culture Center. Photo on courtesy of Ørland Kultursenter.

The RHH involves 5 types of stakeholders including local business organisation/individuals, local farmers, other residents, regional and municipal administrators, and researchers.

The reference SIA

Ørland and Austrått landscape is enrolled as a Role Model in Landscape SIA. For many locals of the municipality Ørland, their landscape is synonymous with Austrått. The manorial landscape of Austrått contains high natural

and cultural values with historical and military significance. This is embodied through Austrått manor with gardens, a hunting park, several crofts, larger farms and an old pilgrimage route. A landscape is more than its tangible dimensions though, it's also the perceptions, stories and memoirs. Therefore, the relation to the landscape is equally as important to safeguard and regenerate as the physical character.

Other relevant SIAs

PILGRIMAGE

Sitting at the entrance to the Trondheim fjord, Ørland is an important place where the coastal pilgrimage route (Kystpilegrimsleia) to Trondheim goes through. This pilgrimage route is part of St. Olav Ways - the roads the pilgrims followed on their journey from different parts of Nordic countries towards the pilgrimage destination Nidaros Cathedral in Trondheim - the burial church of St. Olav. The historical pilgrimage route in Ørland today is underexplored and largely unknown by the locals and visitors.

LOCAL FOOD

Surrounded by the sea, Ørland has rich fish resources, which have been an important source of food for local people. Ørland also has fertile soil and mild climate. There were a variety of fruit trees planted in Ørland historically, and old recipes recorded food made from these fruits. These orchards and recipes have disappeared in daily life in Ørland today. But there is a potential to bring them back to life.

6.11.2 Starting point

Code	Role Model Action name	Objective
RM11.1	Develop a participative process for the recognition and the evaluation of the cultural and natural heritage features (tangible and intangible) signals, maps, radio...	Understanding comprehensive values of the landscape
RM11.2	Design a framework for integrated management	Integrated management that both protects CNH and ensures sustainable development

We (researchers) have been working over 10 years with the local people in Ørland about the historical landscape management and heritage-based development. Therefore, when approaching local and regional stakeholders for participatory workshops in 2020, we brought the ideas of 'historical fruit trees' and 'pilgrimage routes' for discussion. These ideas were generated from participatory processes we had earlier with the local and regional stakeholders, as well as from other RMs and Rs in RURITAGE. In the participatory workshops, we aimed to check with stakeholders how they were interested in such ideas, and how to interpret them into action plans.

Because of the restrictions in the pandemic, the participatory workshops were mostly held online, in the forms of video meetings and telephone calls. Participants included regional and local Agricultural officers, municipality officers, local businesspeople, farmers, visitors, local scholars, researchers. The actions appeared to be very attractive. Two action plans were formed based on the workshops.

6.11.3 Objectives of the enhancement plan

The overall objective of the plan is, through digging into natural and cultural resources in Ørland, to find opportunities for enhanced social, economic and environmental values for both local people, visitors and broader society.

Opportunities and/or open issues to address	Specific objectives	
<p>There are rich historical resources that have not been well exploited yet. For example, there is a recorded history of orchards and fruit processing in Ørland, and Ørland is one of the key sites on the pilgrimage routes.</p>	O1	Enhance local identity
	<p>The cultural and natural heritage of Ørland plays an important role in Local people's identity building. There is potential to dig into the cultural and natural resources and use them to enhance the local identity</p>	
	O2	Generate local economy
<p>By developing new products (such as cider made from historical fruit species) and new services (such as pilgrimage tourism), new job opportunities can be created.</p>		
<p>O3 Enrich visitors' experience in Austrått and Ørland landscapes.</p>		
<p>Currently visitors coming to Ørland are mainly for bird watching, camping and visiting Austrått Manor. By developing more services and products related to the local area, we can offer more experiences for visitors to enjoy.</p>		
<p>There is an underexplored historical pilgrimage route that extended from Norway to Sweden and Finland.</p>	O4	Enhance the visibility of the pilgrimage routes in Nordic countries, especially on regional and national levels
	<p>The pilgrimage routes in Ørland was not clearly marked in the fields and rarely recognised by visitors. However, it has historical significance and is part of the local, regional and national heritage and should be bringing to the front</p>	
<p>Ørland offers great resources, including good soil and mild climate for growing orchards, unique set local knowledge and skills associated with fruit production</p>	O5	Preserve traditional knowledge on fruit products
	<p>There were a variety of fruit trees planted in Ørland historically, and old recipes recorded food made from these fruits. These orchards and recipes have disappeared in daily life in Ørland today. By digging into historical knowledge and bringing it to the local people's life, we hope to preserve the tradition.</p>	

6.11.4 List of actions

Enhancement action	Title of Enhancement action	Objective (please refer to section 1.2)
RM11.3	Develop local fruit products with historical roots linked to Ørland landscape	O1, O2, O3, O5
RM11.4	Link the pilgrimage routes Finland—Sweden—Norway	O1, O2, O3, O4

6.11.5 Operational programme

Code of the action	
Title the action	Develop local fruit products with historical roots linked to Ørland landscape. (short name: Fruit Action)
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Local food; Landscape

Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Intangible – Knowledge and practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	Pre-selected actions: RM3.1 Support local farmers and producers in innovation projects RM3.4 Definition of standards of quality for the selected products RM3.5 Promote the environmental sustainability of the agro-food production, packaging and selling RM13.3 Local Economic and Community Plan developed for the region R3.7 Local and new inhabitants are an active part in preserving Orchard meadows and old Fruit varieties. Besides, additional Replicator Styrian Eisenwurzen UNESCO Global Geopark (specialized on fruit trees) can also be referenced.
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM 3 Preserving old traditions for innovating agro-food production in Apulia (ITALY), RM13 The Wild Atlantic Way (IRELAND)
Brief description of the action	<p>Historical documents (cuisine recipes, historical maps etc.) have shown the evidence of a variety of fruit productions in Ørland. Today this knowledge has largely disappeared in local life. The remains of historical orchards are sparse (such as one in Austrått east garden). There is no local fruit production in the commercial market, which has not been active since the 19th century.</p> <p>The action aims to re-establish this tradition by re-introducing old fruit varieties to local farmers. It involves two main steps during the project period:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Research on orchard species grown in the area historically, as well as relevant knowledge such as planting and fruit processing methods. 2. Transfer knowledge to local farmers. <p>The Fruit Action will be continuing after the project period, if funding is granted. The post-project stage of the Fruit Action will be focusing on producing and marketing fruit products.</p>
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	No
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>The Objective is to bring old varieties of fruit trees to Ørland and nearby regions. This will open opportunities for creating new jobs, enhancing local identity, enriching visitors' experiences by tasting local food, and also preserving the cultural heritage by bringing historical knowledge to life.</p> <p>The Target is to select and promote at least one species of fruit trees to local farmers.</p>
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applying for funding from regional or national funding bodies for the fruit tree project. • Narratives on old fruit varieties and processing methods (such as recipes) in Ørland, and analysis of the possibilities of reintroducing them to local farmers • Organising a round-table meeting at RHH with local farmers and other stakeholders, to explore possibilities of reintroducing old fruit varieties, and to clarify ideas and approaches • Visiting the Replicator in Finland (St. Olav's Way), together with farmer representatives from Ørland. • Introducing the Fruit Action on local newspaper or social media • Implementing the Fruit Action, including hiring specialists for fruit tree survey and propagation, training local farmers and so on. • Applying for funding from regional or national funding bodies to support expanding the fruit tree project in the long term.
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NMBU (research) • Regional and local agricultural office (networking, knowledge transfer)

contribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ørland Cultural Center (networking) • RHH of RM11 (networking, training) • Farmers (trainee, fruit product producer) • (Kyst Hotel Brekstad and other potential sellers (end market))
Beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality of Ørland, • Regional government of Trøndelag • Local and regional farmers and food processing industry personnel • Hotels • Local people and visitors
Timeframe	Spring 2021-Autumn 2022 (The Fruit Action is likely to continue after the project period)
Indicative costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders meetings in Ørland (ca. 1,500 EUR) • Research cost (To be funded by separate project funding) • Promote old fruit varieties, including purchasing materials, trainings, , hiring specialists for surveying fruit tree species and fruit tree propagation/cultivating new trees from cuttings of historical species, etc. (ca. 40,000 EUR) <p>Note: The scale of fruit tree promotion depends on the funding that can be applied. Therefore, the lump sum is not clear at this stage.</p>
Indicative funding sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundings from Ørland Culture Centre and Regional government (depending on the funding application results) • Funding from RURITAGE: 1,500 EUR

Code of the action	RM11.4
Title the action	Link the pilgrimage routes Finland—Sweden—Norway (short name: Pilgrimage Route Action)
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage; Art&Festivals; Landscape; Local food
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature, Built, Artefacts Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Social practices Rituals and festive events
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	Pre-selected actions: RM1.3 Form a tourism body with the specific character for developing these resources and attracting tourism RM1.5 Study and research the historic traces of the pilgrimage routes and the traditions related to them (in literature, historic maps, art,...) RM8.4 Enhance the narrative of the place and promote the discovering of the territory through history: guided tours, thematic excursions, games, re-enactment RM13.1 Set out a strategy and an implementation framework and program for the sustainable implementation of the Wild Atlantic Way RM13.3 Local Economic and Community Plan developed for the region
Relevant RM/KFP involved	Mainly Replicator ‘St. Olav’s way’ are involved. We may also exchange knowledge and experiences with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RM1 (Camino de Santiago) - RM13 (Wild Atlantic Way) - RM8 (Visegrad)
Brief description of the action	This action aims to enrich the experiences and enhance the visibility of the pilgrimage routes in Ørland, especially on regional and national levels. Ørland is an important site on the coast pilgrimage route which starts in Egersund and ends at the Nidaros Cathedral in Trondheim. Nidaros was the most important pilgrimage destination in Northern Europe until the Reformation in 1537, and was used by both Norwegians and foreign pilgrims. Today the pilgrimage history in Ørland is largely lack of recognition.

	<p>During the project period, the pilgrimage routes in Ørland will be marked (both in the field and on website) and promoted through various medias.</p> <p>After the project period, funding opportunities and collaboration potentials will be explored to support further activities under the frame of Nordic pilgrimage routes.</p> <p>The 'Pilgrimage Route Action' sets up a framework, in which other actions will be integrated to enrich the dimensions of pilgrimage route experiences. For example, the 'Local Food Action' can be linked here, and farmers in Ørland can exchange experiences with fruit producers in other regions along the Nordic Pilgrimage Routes.</p>
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	No
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>The Objective is to enhance the visibility of the pilgrimage routes in Ørland, which will not only bring more experiences to local people and visitors, but also create more job opportunities, and encourage communication and collaboration among different regions along the Nordic pilgrimage routes.</p> <p>The Target is successfully promoting the pilgrimage routes to local people and visitors by marking the pilgrimage routes in the field and by setting up a series of activities including at least 1 group walk and 2 presentations.</p>
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mark the pilgrimage routes in Ørland with signposts and billboards (Done) • Mark the pilgrimage routes on https://pilegrimsleden.no/kart • A launch event: a group walk in the newly marked pilgrimage route in Ørland (Done) • Give a presentation 'How to utilize cultural landscape in tourism – case Austrått landscape in Norway' on conference in Finland (Annegreth Dietze Schirdewahn, 5th March 2021), replicator St Olav's Way involved • Visit St Olav's Way in Finland • A meeting with St Olav's Way to explore products development, marketing strategies etc. • Exchange ideas on pilgrimage-routes related activities at DRHH • Promote the pilgrimage route where it is relevant (for example, in online social media, on newspapers, conferences and seminars)
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ørland Cultural Center (mark the routes, networking) • RHH of RM11 (mark the routes, networking) • NMBU (consultancy) • Managers of St Olav's Way • Users (local people and external visitors) (feedbacks on travel experience)
Beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality of Ørland, • Other regions and municipalities along the pilgrimage routes • Local people • Visitors/tourists
Timeframe	Spring 2021-Autumn 2022 (The Pilgrimage Route Action is likely to continue after the project period)
Indicative costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make and install signposts and billboards (funded by Ørland cultural center, and the municipality) • Launching events (funded by Ørland cultural center and municipality)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholders meetings in Ørland (ca. 1,500 EUR) <p>lump sum: 15,500 EUR</p>
Indicative funding sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> From RURITAGE: 1,500 EUR Local sponsors (making and installing road signs, launch events): 14,000 EUR

6.12 RM12 Douro cultural landscape (AEICE) Enhancement plan

Figure 83: This photo was a part of the RURITAGE photo contest. Photographer: Clorinda Galasso

6.12.1 Background

The initiative "Duero Douro: heritage for development" was born in the heart of the Heritage, Tourism and Language Working Group of the Habitat Cluster (AEICE) of Castilla y León. The work within the group, together with the extensive experience of the member companies, has led to the definition of an ambitious project. An initiative (project of projects) that aims to improve the competitiveness of companies through a common strategy that promotes the development of different actions that, however, share the same principle: Castilla y León has an extraordinary cultural heritage that must be mobilised to promote regional development.

To implement this initiative, a representative territory has been chosen: the Douro Valley, which brings together an extraordinary cultural legacy, a mosaic of very diverse landscapes and a dynamic business fabric. The combination of these three factors is essential for the strategy to work. Companies in the Douro Valley can recognise cultural heritage as an added value, as a differentiating argument to improve their competitiveness. A glocal strategy is thus implemented, which values endogenous resources in order to compete in a global scenario. A philosophy contained in the motto of the initiative "Douro Douro: heritage for development".

This is an initiative with an international vocation, Spain and Portugal. The Douro Douro territory is identified with a wide corridor around the Douro river valley, which has an extension of just over 34,000 km², a route of more than 900 km in length that runs east-west in the northern half of the Iberian Peninsula. This vast territory is home to an extraordinary variety of landscapes: mountainous areas such as the source of the river (Sierra de Urbión, 2,228 m) and the Sierra d'Estrela (1771 m), meadows and countryside in the central section of the route, the spectacular scenery of the arribes on the border and the valley deeply embedded between mountains in the Portuguese territory.

Just over 2.5 million people (2,660,385) live in this territory. The occupation of the territory is radically different between the two countries: in Spain the average density is low at 32.11 inhabitants/km² while in Portugal this figure reaches 211.35 inhabitants/km². On the Portuguese territory there is a very marked spatial segregation between the metropolitan area of Porto (Grande Porto) and the border areas with Spain in the districts of Douro and Tras Os Montes where the population density is very low (Vila Nova Foz Côa 17.54). Functionally, it should be noted that this is an essentially rural territory with only two urban areas: the metropolitan area of Porto (1,723,618 inhabitants) and the urban area of Valladolid (375,000 inhabitants). The administrative organisation of this area is also very different. In Spain the territory is organised around 608 municipalities whereas in Portugal there are only 35 concelhos.

	Total population	Density inhab/km²	No. of municipalities	NUTS3	AREA DD (Km²)
Spain	813.868	32,11	608	8	25347,24
Portugal	1.846.517	211,35	35	1	8736,97
DueroDouro	2.660.385	78,05	643		34.084,22

Table 4: Elaboration by AEICE based on INE and INÉ data.

The territory included in the Douro Douro Douro initiative is a rural cultural landscape. Historically, the uses and exploitation of this area have been linked to agricultural resources which, today, continue to be a strategic economic activity. The Douro Valley (897 km long) is home to some of the world's most famous wine regions, such as Alto Douro Vinhateiro and Ribeira do Douro, among others. Around the riverbed there is a succession of agricultural landscapes of great cultural and productive value, which are adapted to the potential of a diverse physical environment.

Another of the keys to the heritage value of this area is its important role in the history of Spain and Portugal. The Douro River served as a frontier between the Christian and Muslim kingdoms during the Reconquest and played an outstanding role in the repopulation process throughout the Middle Ages. Churches, castles, palaces, monasteries and urban centres follow one after the other along the river, forming a heritage complex of

exceptional importance on the European continent.

Figure 84: Map of the Douro Douro territory. Image courtesy of AEICE.

Rural Heritage Hub

The initiative "Duero Douro: heritage for development" was born in the heart of the Heritage, Tourism and Language Working Group of the Habitat Cluster (AEICE) of Castilla y León. The cluster is an organisation that brings together more than a hundred companies in the AECO sector (architecture, engineering and construction) that has been recognised for excellence by the Ministry of Industry and has been awarded the Bronze Label to participate in innovation projects.

Duero Douro is a private initiative, it is not a managing body of the territory, nor does it have public administration powers over the area, nor is it responsible for the protection and management of cultural heritage. From the private sphere, a collaborative initiative focused on the revaluation of the heritage as a basic resource for the development of the territory is addressed. The delimitation of the area derives from the functionality of the territory brand that is proposed as the guiding thread of the project. Duero Douro is a facilitating business agent. Agent, because it intervenes proactively in the socio-economic context with an integrated vision. Entrepreneurial, because it is born in the heart of a cluster in which companies are integrated. Facilitator, because the mission of Duero Douro is to contribute to the creation of an environment (ecosystem) that favours the activity of the

Figure 85 and 86 : The Duero Douro RHH. Image courtesy of AEICE.

member companies.

Since 2015, the interested companies have promoted the initiative with their own resources, which have allowed them to have a technical office that manages the group's activity. Their own contributions and the raising of funds in different competitive calls for proposals have enabled the development of different activities that are beginning to consolidate a Douro Douro community of interest.

The headquarters of the initiative is located in the building that houses the offices of the AEICE Cluster, where there is a classroom linked to the initiative, fitted out through a collaborative process in which companies from other working groups of the cluster have participated.

In any case, the deployment of the strategic plan's lines of action in such an extensive territory has required an itinerant formula that brings the initiative closer to the territory. The hub's activities have been carried out in different physical locations; depending on the objectives of the activities, the hub has been "installed" in different locations and events where the activities have been held. This formula has made it possible to bring agents, administrations and citizens closer to the initiative, and also to establish closer collaborations with the hub's temporary headquarters.

At the end of 2019, the need to reorient the focus of the proposed actions and proposals in order to better respond to the demands of the companies involved in the initiative arises. The knowledge acquired during these years allows for a clearer identification of the focus of the action: the new programme of actions must balance the creation of a context favourable to collaboration (Douro Douro community) with the development of projects and actions that generate a more direct return (business) for the companies.

The arrival of the pandemic poses an extraordinary challenge for focusing the actions of this new stage; on the one hand, because the activity of the agents concerned (tourism, hotels, culture, etc.) is seriously affected by the effects of the pandemic and because the health circumstances force the reinvention of communication and the activities carried out, many of which are based on face-to-face meetings.

The stakeholders involved in the RHH have a very diverse profile, although with a clear predominance of business activities (the initiative arises within a cluster). These include companies dedicated to the rehabilitation of historic buildings, specialised consultancy activities (archaeology, urban planning, environment); wineries with wine tourism activities, travel agencies, wine routes, heritage defence associations, town councils...

Figure 87: The Douro Douro RHH. Image courtesy of AEICE.

The reference SIA

The aim of the initiative is to turn the Douro Douro territory into an internationally recognised brand as a reference in the management of cultural heritage as a resource to articulate the development of the territory. This proposal requires an integrated vision of the cultural legacy, bringing together different types of cultural assets (monumental, archaeological, natural, intangible...), which are made tangible in the landscape.

The Douro Douro takes the river's discourse as a reference: between Soria and Oporto a rural landscape of great cultural value is developed; along its more than 900 km. of length, a great diversity of agricultural landscapes is

developed, among which the wine culture stands out; internationally recognised designations of origin such as the Alto Douro Vinhateiro or Ribera del Duero are settled here. The historical functionality of this territory, a frontier between the Christian and Muslim kingdoms, has generated an extraordinary cultural legacy that is tangible in the network of historical sites, monasteries and castles located in the Douro valley. The articulation of the area is also expressed in terms of economic activity; a very relevant percentage of the regional economic activity is based on this corridor, creating a context of opportunity.

This approach fits in with the SIA of landscape defined in the RURITAGE project, the territory on which action is taken corresponds to a landscape that is well identified both physically and culturally. The discourse of the river spatially delimits an area of action that stands out for both the quantity and quality of its heritage. Both natural and cultural perspectives are combined in the concept of landscape and in the proposed integrated model of cultural heritage management.

Other relevant SIAs

LOCAL FOOD

One of the hallmarks of the Douro River is its agricultural production of wine, a basic sector in the economy of our territory. Around the Douro valley, other agricultural productions of great value and quality are developed (cheese, horticultural products, sausages, sweets...) that need a boost to improve their competitiveness. These productions are testimony to the agricultural heritage of our territory, highly recognised by the local community and also by visitors; they are also the essential support of our gastronomy. The improvement plan expressly incorporates this vision in order to define actions aimed at these agents who, until now, have participated in the initiative without having a proposal so clearly focused on their interests

ART & FESTIVAL

The link between cultural activities and the Douro Douro initiative is considered fundamental, as it is a crucial element for the tourist competitiveness of an inland destination, but also because cultural activity is an essential vector for improving the reputation and competitiveness of a territory. The potential of the cultural agenda of the Douro Douro territory is many and the experiences of the RMs included in this SIA are very useful to advance in the integration of cultural activities as a dynamising element of our activity.

PILGRIMAGE

The idea underlying the pilgrimage models is also present in the Douro Douro initiative, as a route articulated around the discourse of the river between Soria and Oporto. The thread of the argument around the river brings together the territories along its banks. The experiences of the pilgrimage projects are a reference as they have consolidated a model of intervention based on a common brand, an idea that is also present in the Douro Douro initiative.

6.12.2 Starting point

Code	Role Model Action name	Objective
RM12.1	Promote joint actions (also through PPPs) to enhance heritage resources and create an internationally recognised brand.	To consolidate the Douro Douro as a reference brand in the management of cultural and natural heritage.
RM12.2	Creation of a social innovation laboratory for the valorisation of cultural and natural heritage.	Promote the emergence of a Douro Douro community that serves as a tool to boost economic activities linked to the enhancement of cultural and natural heritage.
RM12.3	Support the implementation of a regional Territorial Heritage System (STP).	Support the creation of a legal and administrative recognition of the Douro Douro ecosystem as a cultural landscape.
RM12.4	Develop strategies for understanding and managing changes and interactions between social and ecological systems, including conflict prevention and biodiversity management.	To highlight the close links between our way of life and changes in the ecosystem. The recognition of this linkage generates a sense of responsibility that incorporates sustainability as a basic objective of the actions.
RM12.5	Develop a high-level training programme for the management of the territory as a "cultural landscape" aimed primarily at professionals, researchers and staff of public bodies.	To train agents to be able to recognise the value of heritage and the need to address its preservation, conservation and revaluation from an integrated perspective.

The activities carried out so far has served to develop collaboration between all the agents present in the Douro territory in order to position a territory brand. Public administrations, companies from different sectors, knowledge centres, citizens' associations... are aware of the initiative and have participated in its activities. However, the degree of commitment and involvement in the initiative has not yet reached sufficient maturity to generate economic returns for companies. It is therefore necessary to better fit the value proposition to generate this return; an essential return for a private initiative arising from a business interest in improving its competitiveness.

On this basis, the actions have been reoriented so that they focus on the interests and culture of the companies and favor the incorporation of activities in the tourism sector.

According to the project guidelines, a first selection of good practices was made and the materials (letters, information on lessons learned) were disseminated among stakeholders. A session was convened for 23 March 2020, but the pandemic confinement prevented it from taking place.

Stakeholder contact was maintained between April and July, but the context and impact of the pandemic on the tourism sector did not favor the holding of the participatory workshop.

The activities linked to the co-creation process are at a delicate moment; the pandemic has severely impacted the activity of most of the actors (tourism), the limitations threaten the disappearance of many activities carried out by micro and small enterprises, and it is not easy to bring the actors together to involve them in actions with strategic content.

Undoubtedly, the entrepreneurial nature of the initiative conditions its evolution; in a context of crisis, it is more complex to reconcile the long-term vision (necessary for the success of a project such as Douro Douro) with the constant adaptation required by the environment.

Finally, the participatory workshop was held on 11 March with the attendance of 42 participants (see workshop report) in which the proposed actions were validated. Structural actions will be maintained, such as participation in the participatory process for the elaboration of the RIS3 and the strategy of collaboration with the business community in Portugal will be strengthened. For the development of the actions, working groups have already

been set up (bubbles, private territory forum, etc.).

6.12.3 Objectives of the Enhancement plan

The definition of the Enhancement plan has been articulated around a double reflection. Firstly, a preliminary assessment and reflection work was carried out with the companies that support the Douro Douro initiative in order to define the roadmap for the near future.

This process coincides with the outbreak of the pandemic, which requires a complete readjustment of the formulas for relations with our stakeholders; it is necessary to comply with the health protection measures (suspension of activities, meetings, trips, etc.) and, on the other hand, we are addressing our message to economic sectors (hotels, wineries, tourist guides, etc.) deeply affected by the economic consequences of the pandemic.

In this context, the focus of the actions proposed by the Douro Douro Hub has been reoriented: it is essential to consolidate the business community so that collaboration between the different sectors generates synergies that translate into new products and services. The reinforcement of the business community, which is also our greatest strength (we are a cluster) will allow us to establish enriching alliances with the other agents operating in the territory (public administrations, non-profit organisations in defense of heritage, knowledge centres...).

Subsequently, following the guidelines of the project, a series of actions have been defined, built with the references and good practices identified. It has been decided to integrate in the proposed actions the aspects that have been considered most feasible in the context of our territory. The actions thus defined have been presented in the participatory workshops for validation.

Considering the different objectives defined, three types of actions have been differentiated: structural, cohesion and articulation and, finally, the more concrete actions "around the Douro".

The group of structural actions includes the work carried out on the positioning of the initiative with regard to the public administrations with competencies in cultural and natural heritage. These actions are essential both to consolidate a strategic alliance with our environment and to participate in the definition of the basic guidelines for government action on cultural and natural heritage.

The articulation and cohesion of the business community is a strategic challenge. Considering that businesses play an essential role in the development of the territory (creation of activity and employment), it is essential to consolidate the professional sector around heritage. The characteristics of the business fabric (large volume of very small companies) do not favor the articulation of the value chain or the enhancement of competitiveness; it is necessary to improve this cohesion in order to generate economies of scale around a shared challenge: development of the territory around the enhancement of our territorial heritage. On the other hand

The actions related to the extension of the value chain around cultural and natural heritage have been included under the heading "around the Douro"; they are proposals aimed at opening lines of collaboration with actors in other areas of innovation such as Local Food Production or Art and Festivals.

In this context, there are three strategic objectives of this Enhancement Plan:

1. Improve the positioning of the Douro Douro initiative in the eyes of public administrations as a reference business agent in the cultural and natural heritage sector.
2. Strengthen the Douro Douro Douro business community as a tool to improve the competitiveness of companies that enhance the value of heritage resources.
3. Extend the value chain of cultural and natural heritage by incorporating agents related to local food production.

Opportunities and/or outstanding issues to be addressed	Specific objectives
Extraordinary cultural and natural	01 Strengthen the Douro Douro brand as a reference in the

heritage around the Douro river	<p>integrated management of cultural and natural heritage.</p> <p>The valorisation of the heritage resources around the Douro requires a brand that helps to recognise and exploit these resources for the benefit of the community. The brand is a tool that identifies a broad and integrated vision of both the agents called upon to participate (companies, public administrations, knowledge centres, citizens...) and the actions that are developed (conservation, dissemination, tourism promotion, business collaboration...).</p> <p>The recognition of a shared challenge (internal vision) and a single message (external vision) become tangible in the brand.</p>
Lack of business collaboration networks between Portugal and Spain	<p>O2 To promote business cooperation between region Castilla y León (Spain) and the Northern Region (Portugal) in the heritage, tourism and language sectors.</p> <p>One of the most relevant features of the Douro Douro initiative is its international character, which enhances its capacity to unite the territory. It is essential that the business agents of both countries work together to build a common space for action and collaboration that multiplies the effect of their actions.</p>
Lack of collaborative projects between complementary sectors of activity	<p>O3 Improve the articulation of the heritage, tourism and language business sector.</p> <p>The heritage and tourism sector is considered an economic activity of reference in the development of both region Castilla y León and the Northern Region of Portugal. The agents in these value chains do not have a business collaboration structure that allows them to identify shared challenges and develop collaborative projects to multiply the results; these are sectors of activity that, due to their transversality or small size, have a reduced social capital that needs to be strengthened.</p>
Existence of a number of high quality food designations of origin. Lack of cooperation initiatives between the heritage sector and quality agri-food production.	<p>O4 Promote the complementarity between cultural and natural heritage and local food production.</p> <p>Local food production is another example of the cultural heritage of a territory. Local production is the result of a sustainable and dynamic use of natural resources that has generated a cultural legacy (material, immaterial, landscape) that must be preserved. These high quality products are not only healthy but also a resource of great economic value.</p> <p>This agricultural heritage is one of the hallmarks of the Douro Douro region's identity (particularly recognised in the cultivation of vineyards). There are many agri-food protection figures that recognise these values, but there is no joint strategy to enhance this potential as a whole.</p>
Existence of a relevant cultural program. Emerging activities linked to the revaluation of the territory as a setting for activities: historical recreations, sporting competitions, ornithological tourism, etc.	<p>O5 Promote the complementarity between the different cultural activities as a platform to broaden the perception of the Douro Douro territory as a reference of cultural and creative destination.</p> <p>There are many cultural and sporting activities developed on the Douro Douro territory that have gained recognition and trajectory (Classical Theatre Festival, Sonorama...). At the same time, other cultural and leisure activities and initiatives emerge that need to be supported in order to favor their consolidation. The elaboration</p>

	of a joint cultural proposal would generate synergies between the different activities and would make it possible to take advantage of the potential of the territory as a common thread of a joint cultural proposal.
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6.10.4 List of actions

Enhancement action	Title of Enhancement action	Objective (please refer to section 1.2)
STRUCTURAL		
RM12.6	Participation in the regional RIS3 elaboration process	O1; O2
RM12.7	Collaborative Ecosystem in the Regional Ministry of Culture and Tourism	O1; O3
JOINT-COHESION		
RM12.8	Douro Douro Forum in Private	O2.; O3
RM12.9	Business bubble	O2; O4; O5
AROUND THE DUERO		
RM12.10	Duero Mission	O2; O3; O4; O5
RM12.11	CANAL DUERO On Line	O2; O3; O4; O5

The above figure was further developed by AEICE to fit their specific needs.

6.10.5 Operational programme

Action code	RM12.6
Title of the action	PARTICIPATION IN THE REGIONAL RIS3 ELABORATION PROCESS
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage; Art&Festivals; Landscape; Local food; Migration; Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature, Built, Artefacts Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Oral traditions
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	N/A
Relevant RM/KFP involved	ICLEI
Brief description of the action	In December 2020, the current programming period for the implementation of RIS3 in the region came to an end and the participation process to define the new programming period has just been launched. The aim is to maintain economic activities linked to the "heritage, tourism and language" sector as a strategic sector for the region of Castilla y León. The strategic value of heritage resources related to tourism activity must continue to be an area of specialisation for the region of Castilla y León.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM12.3
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Objective: To make visible the potential of the region's cultural and natural heritage as a basic resource in the reorientation of the productive model of the region of Castilla y León.

	Target: Define the activity around the heritage, tourism and language value chain as a strategic activity in the regional RIS3.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application to join the participation process • Participation in the heritage, tourism and language sectoral committees. • Elaboration of strategic priorities document for the sector.
Main stakeholders involved and their role and contribution	Stakeholders will report the needs and bottlenecks they identify to be presented in the working and discussion groups throughout the RIS 3 definition process. Among the participating agents are representatives of the innovation system (Universities and Technology Centres), technicians from the administration, companies linked to the sector's activity, professional associations, clusters, non-profit foundations
Beneficiaries	The business community of the macro-activity "Heritage, Tourism and Language".
Timeframe	February 2021-September 2021
Indicative costs	Only staff costs foreseen
Indicative funding sources	Own resources

Action code	RM12.7
Title of the action	COLLABORATIVE ECOSYSTEM IN THE REGIONAL MINISTRY OF CULTURE AND TOURISM
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage; Art&Festivals; Landscape; Local food; Migration; Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature, Built, Artefacts Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Oral traditions
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	N/A
Relevant RM/KFP involved	ICLEI, SAVONIA
Brief description of the action	The regional government wants to set up a meeting point between the administration, the innovation system (universities and technology centres) and companies in the sector. The aim is to identify synergies and complementarities for the construction of projects to be submitted to the calls for proposals within the framework of the Next Generation funds.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM12.3
Objective and target of the action (at the end of the project)	Objective: To promote the participation of companies (SMEs and micro-SMEs) in economic recovery funds. Target: To identify common interests in order to define expressions of interest for the presentation of projects. It has not been defined how the regional government will implement this strategic partnership action, although the definition of two expressions of interest is proposed as a goal.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in the process of setting up the working group • Networking to involve other non-represented interest groups (performing arts, crafts, audiovisual, etc.). • Identification of common interests • Monitoring and coordination of the participatory process
Main stakeholders involved and their role and contribution	Regional Government (DG Cultural Heritage, DG Tourism, DG Cultural Policies, DG Sports). Public Universities and Technology Centres AEICE-Duero Douro Technical Office
Beneficiaries	The business community of the macro-activity "Heritage, Tourism and Language". University research groups
Timeframe	March 2021-September 2021
Indicative costs	Only staff costs foreseen
Indicative funding sources	Own resources

Action code	RM12.8
Title of the action	DOURO DOURO FORUM IN PRIVATE
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage; Art&Festivals; Landscape; Local food
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Social practices Rituals and festive events
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM13; RM4
Relevant RM/KFP involved	N/A
Brief description of the action	<p>On-site forum in an emblematic space of the territory as a meeting and reflection point to promote the Douro Douro brand in order to discover the social and entrepreneurial capital already in place. The aim is to recognise the hidden champions who work every day to enhance the cultural and natural heritage, local efforts with a high level of personal commitment.</p> <p>The sessions will be organised as reflections open to participation so that the presentation of experiences can act as a lever for the discovery of common interests among all.</p>
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	Douro Douro Brand RM12.1
Objective and target of the action (at the end of the project)	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public recognition of the social capital of the Douro Douro territory. • Generate a space for relations between agents from complementary value chains (art and festivals, local food production, cultural tourism...) and from different geographical areas to explore shared interests. <p>Target: To make visible the work of the agents of the territory who work in the revaluation of heritage resources. 15 associations, 15 enterprises. 200 participants (face-to-face/On-line)</p>
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal dynamisation for the organisation of the event • Selection process for participating entities: citizens, companies, etc. • Preliminary digital marketing actions to build a community of interest • Partnership with the entity and the locality hosting the event
Main stakeholders involved and their role and contribution	<p>All entities of the cluster will be involved to identify initiatives and companies that meet the profile of Forum participants, especially those linked to local food and arts production and festivals.</p> <p>Business associations will be involved: wine tourism (Wine Routes), accommodation (hotel and rural), designations of origin, etc., as well as public administration bodies that support local entrepreneurship: Local Action Groups, Development Societies, Inter-municipal Communities, etc.</p>
Beneficiaries	The business community and citizens' heritage associations will be the main beneficiaries.
Timeframe	May-October 2021
Indicative costs	EUR 20,000 for Corporate Image, Web, Room hire, Speakers, Assembly
Indicative funding sources	Private sponsorships, call for innovation (Regional Ministry of Culture), own resources, collaborations with entities (wine routes, town councils, provincial councils).

Action code	RM12.9
Title of the action	BUSINESS BUBBLE
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage; Art&Festivals; Landscape; Local food; Migration; Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Social practices Rituals and festive events
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM3; RM9
Relevant RM/KFP involved	N/A
Brief description of the action	<p>After an initial contact, the identification of common interests for the definition of collaborative actions requires smaller relationship spaces that favor knowledge between entities.</p> <p>The dynamisation of small meetings (5 participating entities) that allow a more direct exchange to generate alliances is proposed. These meetings will be promoted both internally (companies and entities that are already members) and externally (companies of interest that do not belong to the organisation).</p> <p>The reference entity chosen for the session presents to the attendees its recent trajectory, the projects and actions in which it works as well as the needs and concerns that require alliances.</p>
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM12.2
Objective and target of the action (at the end of the project)	<p>Objective: Generate a more direct knowledge of the needs and possibilities of collaboration between the companies involved in order to favor collaboration agreements.</p> <p>Target: Organisation of one internal and one external bubble per quarter (8 bubbles).</p>
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mailbox open to receive applications from entities of interest or reference. • Contextualization of the exchange with the entity • Design and preparation of the sessions. • Dissemination among the partners to choose the participants in the session. • Ex-post evaluation, questionnaires
Main stakeholders involved and their role and contribution	Companies interested in building collaborative actions with other partners. In particular, alliances will be explored with entities linked to Arts and Festivals and Local Food Production.
Beneficiaries	Companies
Timeframe	January 2021-December 2021
Indicative costs	Only staff costs foreseen
Indicative funding sources	Own funds

Action code	
RM12.10	
Title of the action	DUERO MISSION
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art&Festivals; Landscape; Local food
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Social practices Rituals and festive events
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM3; RM13
Relevant RM/KFP involved	N/A
Brief description of the action	<p>This action is defined as a two-step approach. Initially, a presentation will be made in Portugal in a space of reference for the business community, with a message focused on the creation of collaborative ties to improve the competitiveness of companies, which will serve to gather the first expressions of interest in receiving the visit of Spanish businessmen.</p> <p>A familiarization trip to Portugal will then be organized to allow entrepreneurs from the selected value chains (local production, landscape, art and festivals) to learn about Portuguese experiences. The philosophy of this action combines the vision of twinning between territories with the objectives of a trade mission of recognition.</p>
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	Douro Douro Brand, RM12.1
Objective and target of the action (at the end of the project)	<p>Objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote spaces for relations between business agents in the field in order to develop a community of interests. Strengthening the international character of the initiative <p>Target: to develop a presentation event in Portugal and a business familiarization trip.</p>
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exploration of reception possibilities in Portugal: inter-municipal communities, rural development associations, business associations. Definition of a presentation programme that focuses on collaboration with reference to local food and art production and festivals. Identify the interests of companies in order to promote a profitable exchange (matchmaking) with Portuguese companies. Organize a familiarization trip to get to know the Portuguese business community and territory first-hand in order to explore opportunities for collaboration.
Main stakeholders involved and their role and contribution	Companies adhering to the initiative, wine routes that bring together companies that develop activities related to wine tourism, food quality designations of origin, artisan associations, etc. interested in promoting their internationalization. Local Action Groups that will act as links with micro-SMEs. Regional Development Entities or Associations interested in their promotion abroad. Portuguese Intermunicipal Communities (CIM) and local development associations interested in cross-border cooperation.
Beneficiaries	Companies
Timeframe	April 2022
Indicative costs	Presentation in Portugal: EUR 6,250 Familiarization trip to Portugal: (10 companies X 2 days) EUR 7,500 Total: EUR 13,750
Indicative funding sources	Own funds, business internationalisation calls, European projects (RURITAGE, cross-border cooperation, COSME...).

Action code	RM12.11
Title of the action	CANAL DUERO ON LINE
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Landscape; Local food
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Intangible – Knowledge and practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM3; RM4; RM13
Relevant RM/KFP involved	N/A
Brief description of the action	Creation of an online channel that will include: general dissemination content on the characteristics of the territory and local production, information on the who's who of the business fabric, and links to online sales pages. The channel is conceived as a tool to promote the agricultural and enogastronomic heritage of the territory and its companies between both countries (Spain/Portugal), between entrepreneurs from different sectors and between these and the end user (tourist, responsible consumer).
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	Douro Douro Brand RM12.1 Innovation Lab RM12.2
Objective and target of the action (at the end of the project)	Objective: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To disseminate the characteristics of the agricultural heritage and its local productions. Promote the business fabric of activities linked to the use of agricultural and enogastronomic heritage resources. Target: To create a space that recognises the value of agricultural heritage and promotes knowledge and collaboration between local producers. A minimum number of 6 companies promoting the action is considered for the implementation of the initiative. It is also advisable for the productive orientation of these companies to be diverse in order to promote a more productive exchange.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identification and analysis of designations of origin and other food quality figures in the Douro Douro territory Presentation of the proposal to food quality bodies/associations Presentation of the proposal to the hospitality sector Definition of contents and technological support (pilot test) Promotion and collaboration actions (Spain-Portugal)
Main stakeholders involved and their role and contribution	Companies adhering to the initiative, wine routes that bring together companies that develop activities related to wine tourism, food quality designations of origin... interested in promoting their internationalization. Entities promoting "Food from...". Portuguese Intermunicipal Communities (CIM) and local development associations interested in cross-border cooperation.
Beneficiaries	Companies
Timeframe	January-May 2022
Indicative costs	Website development and maintenance: EUR 2,500 Digital marketing campaigns: EUR 1,000 Total: EUR 3,500
Indicative funding sources	Own funds, calls for business internationalization, enhancement of business competitiveness (ministry); call for clusters (Junta de Castilla y León).

6.13 RM13 Wild Atlantic Way (WestBic) Enhancement plan

Figure 88: This photo was a part of the RURITAGE photo contest. Photographer: Mulleady

6.13.1 Background

The Wild Atlantic Way in Ireland, which is the Irish Role Model in the RURITAGE project, is the world's longest defined coastal touring route. From Malin Head in County Donegal, the country's most northerly point, to Mizen Head in County Cork, the most southerly point, the route weaves and winds across 2,500km of beautiful coastline.

The regions along with Wild Atlantic Way, have experience mixed fortunes in terms of population growth, with many experiencing decline in their rural areas. Counties with larger urban centres, e.g. Galway city, Cork city etc., exhibit strongest growth, and also have a relatively younger population profile.

Figure 89: Map of West Atlantic Way. Image courtesy of WestBic.

The West Coast of Ireland features a unique landscape formed by the many centuries of coastal erosion from the Atlantic Ocean, which also underpins a distinctive heritage and culture that is maintained against this backdrop.

The tourism product on the West Coast of Ireland is primarily based on its unique and preserved ancient, celtic heritage which is experienced by the visitor against a back drop of this renowned, unspoiled landscape, scenery and natural and historic features that are all along the Atlantic West Coast.

Until recently, whilst the overall region exhibited huge potential, this visitor experience was hap-hazard and directionless and each tourism product was responsible for its own marketing. Capturing or growing market share against the disadvantages of peripherality and negative public infrastructure indices has been a struggle and many have failed or become only seasonal, offering little job prospects or career continuity for the sector to become a full time, mainstream way of life for local populations. Hence, the sub-regions along the Atlantic Seaboard have experienced population drains as per the last Census (Counties Donegal and Mayo particularly).

The advent of the Wild Atlantic Way as a global brand has now started to address this challenge in a most meaningful way. The visitor has a recognised 'destination' to go to with significantly more to offer than the 'garden route' of the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa, the Great Ocean Road of Australia or PCH1 of California. On the Wild Atlantic Way, the products and experiences are more about stopping and 'experiencing' than driving! Indeed, along with way, there are 157 discovery points, 1,000 attractions and more than 2,500 activities.

This project came into being when Fáilte Ireland, the tourism authority in Ireland, along with other key stakeholders set out a strategy and an implementation framework and programme for the sustainable implementation of the Wild Atlantic Way. The process took place in six stages: 1) Proposition and Brand Development 2) Identification of Route 3) Way-finding Strategy 4) Delivery of Discovery Points 5) Selling Wild Atlantic Way Experiences 6) Marketing and Communications.

Apart from some large urban centres, this is very much a rural region, with low population density, and low

population growth. The Northern headlands Area (Donegal) which is focused on in this study has a population of 161,137.

Aging population is a factor in the region. Average age is 38.5 years compared with 37.4 years nationally. Rural depopulation of young people - those pursuing third level education and employment opportunities.

There is relatively poor ICT infrastructure. Only 70% of households have internet. Poor investment by State in ICT infrastructure in rural and peripheral areas.

Donegal Unemployment rate is high (18%) compared to national (12.9%) average in 2016. Donegal down from 26.2% in 2011. National down from 19% in 2011.

Donegal is poorest county in Ireland. In 2016, it had the lowest disposable income in Ireland at €16,099. The National Average was €20,939. Donegal in 2011 had a deprivation score of -6.25, the second most deprived local authority area in Ireland.

Of note, whilst the promotion of the Wild Atlantic Way in general has benefited the entire region, the counties along the Northern Headlands of the Wild Atlantic Way have fared less well, despite its abundance of landscape and attractions, and could benefit with additional support to achieve its potential.

Figure 90: The location of the Wild Atlantic Way. Image courtesy of WestBic.

RURAL HERITAGE HUB

The area operates with dual physical Rural Heritage Hubs. Sliabh Liag in Teelin and gteic@Cill Charthaigh in Kilcar.

The Rural Heritage Hub of Sliabh Liag (Slieve League) is located in Teelin in Co, Donegal, Ireland on the Northern Headlands of Ireland's Wild Atlantic Way. It is Ireland's Ultimate Sea Cliff Experience where visitors experience the local culture, heritage and people of Donegal against the backdrop of spectacular and rugged coastline.

Figure 91: The RHH of Sliabh Liag. Image courtesy of WestBic.

Prior to the pandemic, visitor numbers were at approximately 185,000 per year with capability of increasing to 250,000 per year. Over the past 5 years there has been significant investment by the local authority, the tourist board and Interreg in the road and access infrastructure. Work has also been carried out on the spectacular mountain path which has been upgraded and improved. A transport hub building, coach/car park and ranger's station have been provided. In addition, promotion and marketing activities have begun.

The project is located in what is known in Ireland as a Gaeltacht area where the Irish language, music, culture and heritage is still celebrated. Visitors already visit the region to sample these traditional cultures and the addition of a new visitor experience to the area is a positive development for a peripheral area where many young people leave to seek employment elsewhere in Ireland or overseas.

Figure 92: Photo courtesy of Donegal County Council.

The village of Carrick is only 3 kms from the new Visitor Centre and other villages are nearby such as Cashel, Meenanearny, Malinmore, Malinbeg and Kilcar. The largest fishing / sea-port in Ireland, Killybegs is 20km from Sliabh Liag which presents many additional opportunities such as the cruise ship and cruise market which is expanding every year. The Hospitality and Tourism College of LYIT is also an excellent support to the project with potential for training courses and events in the areas of tour guiding, customer care, hospitality, food etc.

Most overseas visitors travel to Sliabh Liag from Dublin which is approx. 200 kms away. Proximity to Northern Ireland is an advantage with Belfast only 170 km away.

Figure 93: The RHH at gteic@Cill Charthaigh. Image courtesy of WestBic.

The second Rural Heritage Hub is gteic@Cill Charthaigh in Kilcar. This is a Gaeltacht Digital Hub and is part of the Gaeltacht network of 31 gteic digital hubs throughout Ireland promoted by Údarás na Gaeltachta, the regional state agency which is responsible for the economic, social and cultural development of Irish-speaking regions of Ireland. This hub provides co-working, hot desking and unit spaces for cultural and heritage start-ups in a creative and innovation friendly environment. This is an ideal workspace for these types of businesses where new start-ups and existing projects can grow and develop. The centre has a lower carbon footprint than many other centres as a result of a geo-thermal heating system which provides heating to all clients free of charge.

WestBIC, the Business and Innovation Centre for the Northern and Western Region of Ireland, provides on-site business mentoring and supports to start-ups and established businesses in the centre and in the surrounding region.

WestBIC is the organization representing the region within the RURITAGE project. Support for the project has been generous from stakeholders such as the local authority, the enterprise agencies, the Irish Tourism authority, higher education institutes, community organisations, private enterprises operating in the cultural and natural heritage space.

THE REFERENCE SYSTEMIC INNOVATION AREA (SIA)

LANDSCAPE

Figure 94: The unique landscape of the Wild Atlantic Way. Photo courtesy of WestBic.

In South West Donegal, the mix and blend of attractions range from awesome landscape features like the Sliabh Liag Cliffs, the highest cliffs in Europe, Muckcross Head which is a small peninsula with a very unique and attractive cliff with two beautiful beaches in the parish of Kilcar and Glen Head where the notable former Napoleonic-era signal tower occupies a dramatic coastal location, and is a prominent local landmark. Donegal has a fantastic range of heritage and culture related activities, across all the genres to include ancient hill walks to festivals and artisan local food events, all with a healthy dappling of traditional music and dance, unique Gaelic sports, literature and drama, with much of it still preserved in our unique and fully alive, ancient Celtic language, An Ghaeilge.

As a model, the Wild Atlantic Way with its unique landscape and as a most competitive global brand, has become the 'scaffolding' on which the Tourism Providers centred on the natural culture and heritage can grow and scale heritage and related tourism products, build a real business and generate wealth retention and higher value employment in the economies of these sub-regions. Scale and critical mass is now starting to emerge. Visitor numbers are improving and the standards of Tourism Products is on the rise. The incidence of linked and grouped packaging for the visitor is now becoming common and the use of the internet is countering the heretofore problem of peripherality or low level of available investment in marketing. Along the route, the leveraging effect from one successful visitor experience to the next is most encouraging and private sector investment is starting to return to the sector. Case studies are numerous and can be explored individually as can their 'story' of how the Wild Atlantic Way branding is working and is a model for more to follow.

OTHER RELEVANT SYSTEMIC INNOVATION AREAS

LOCAL FOOD

Donegal and the Sliabh Liag peninsula region are renowned for the quality of their food and drink. This area has a strong tradition of fishing and farming and has a strong distilling heritage. Fresh fish from the Atlantic Ocean is available from fishing ports around the county and local restaurants and hotels feature this fresh produce on their menus. Many other local gastronomic products and experiences are available to visitors to the area. In more recent times a strong food network and food brand has been established involving the many stakeholders in the food and drink sector and there are many food related activities in the form of food trails and food events and festivals which bring alive the rich food heritage in the county and illustrate the strong connection between the wild Donegal landscape, the local communities and the authentic food and drink experiences.

PILGRIMAGE

Ireland is known as the land of saints and scholars. There are numerous pilgrim paths and trails in all parts of Ireland. Donegal and the Sliabh Liag peninsula are no different. Among the saints who resided in the area are St.

Figure 95: Photo courtesy of WestBic.

Asicus and St Colmcille. St Asicus (who was St. Patrick's coppersmith) became a hermit and travelled to Sliabh Liag and also to Rathlin Island where he remained for seven years. St Colmcille also spend a number of years in the area. One of the main parishes in the area, Glencolmcille is named after him and there are many visible legacies of his presence in the area. In the participatory workshop in March 2021, the development of a number actions in the Pilgrimage Systemic Innovation Area were proposed. These actions surround the reintroducing and promoting of the Colmcille pilgrimage routes in the local area and the celebration of the 1500th anniversary of the birth of St Colmcille.

RESILIENCE

The rural communities of Donegal always displayed a resilience in the way they continued to keep their communities alive despite being the county that is “cut-off” from the rest of Ireland. This goes back to the days of the conflict in Northern Ireland when Donegal was perceived as a no-go area by tourists because it could only be easily access by travelling through Northern Ireland. This resilience came to the surface again in recent times during Covid-19 pandemic when the county was the worst hit in Ireland for long periods, again partly as a result of its proximity to the open border of Northern Ireland and the free movement of people between both jurisdictions.

The Donegal people engaged in many activities to support the vulnerable in their communities during the Covid-19 crisis and while many challenges were evident, resilience was also very present in the community where many community groups and businesses showed by their actions that the communities were willing to work together to get through the crisis. The vulnerable in the community became the priority especially frontline healthcare workers, older people, those with underlying conditions etc. There were many examples of actions which took place which displayed this including local community response groups who targeted older and vulnerable people with underlying medical conditions who were cocooning under Irish government guidelines. Volunteers in the community delivered hot food, groceries and medication to "cocooning" older and vulnerable people. This range of services was provided by local volunteers from the community organisations and the Gaelic Football Associations.

Private businesses got involved and among the examples were a local SME in the textile sector who pivoted to making PPE gowns and scrubs for frontline healthcare workers to help to alleviate the early scarcity of personal protective equipment. Another example was a local whiskey distillery who scaled back production of its spirits to make hand sanitiser for the local community and for healthcare facilities.

6.13.2 Starting point

Code	Role Model Action name	Objective
RM13.1	To set out a strategy and an implementation framework and programme for the sustainable implementation of the Wild Atlantic Way	This Operational Programme was the first in a series of strategies which set out a vision for the continued evolution of the Wild Atlantic Way over a long period. The Wild Atlantic Way brand was intended to and became synonymous with great experiences of Ireland’s Atlantic heritage, culture, landscapes and seascapes in a high-quality environment. This Operational Programme constituted an iterative process which continually adapts to meet the needs of Ireland’s visitors, the local community and culture, the environment and the tourism industry and trade, while striving all the time to strike a balance between them.
RM13.2	External Monitoring Group to ensure robust	The purpose of this was to work with and

	systems in place to ensure that there are no adverse effects on the environment.	demonstrate to stakeholders and partners that FI were committed to the sustainable development of the Wild Atlantic Way, and to be able to pre-empt and avoid environmental effects in the future should they occur. This was achieved by ensuring robust systems were in place to ensure that there were no adverse effects on the environment.
RM13.3	Local Economic and Community Plan developed for the region	The purpose of the Plan is to identify and implement actions to strengthen and develop the economic and community dimensions of the County and to reflect and support the implementation of existing and proposed National and Regional spatial, community and economic strategies.
RM13.4	Action Plan for Jobs developed for the region and the State	The Government's Action Plan for Jobs placed an emphasis on developing the jobs potential of the regions. It included a commitment to develop and publish a suite of Regional Action Plans for Jobs to support enterprise growth and job creation in the regions.
RM13.5	Údarás na Gaeltachta Strategic Plan 2018-2020	The objective of this strategy is to maintain, strengthen and develop a thriving native language speaking (Gaeltacht) community that is defined by language and culture.

The process of developing the Enhancement plan was carried out in conjunction with many local stakeholders in the Rural Heritage Hub region. The Covid-19 pandemic meant that physical meetings were not possible and this meant that the participatory meetings that took place were online and many of them were bilateral discussions between the stakeholders and WestBIC. These included the local authority, the enterprise agencies, the Irish tourism authority, higher education institutes, education and training institutes, community organisations and private enterprises operating in the cultural and natural heritage space. There were actions that were in the original plan that were removed because they were more long-term actions or that were delayed because of Covid-19 and new more achievable, shorter term actions were included. The participatory workshop in March 2021 was a very positive meeting with many creative new actions coming to light.

6.13.3 Objectives of the enhancement plan

The overall objective of this Enhancement plan is to capture the plans and actions in the Sliabh Liag catchment area that will be central in regenerating the area through the development of our natural and cultural heritage resources. The locality is dependent on our heritage and culture and the area is proud of our unique heritage from our weaving and textiles industry, our sheep farming, our fishing tradition, our music, language and dance, our archaeology and our history, our pilgrimage history etc. This plan is meant to complement and support any new and existing development and regeneration plans which are being discussed and planned in the area by various stakeholder such as community groups, state agencies, local authorities and others.

Opportunities and/or open issues to address	Specific objectives	
The Donegal region has the highest level of unemployment in Ireland. While SW Donegal has fared better and many of the	O1	Create an environment for creation of employment
		This objective is to create an environment for the creation of employment, to enable the enterprise ecosystem in the area

<p>available workspaces are occupied by factories and employers, there is still a need to create more jobs to prevent the depopulation of young people and to attract people back to the area to work and live.</p>	<p>which includes the creation of appropriate connected workspaces and infrastructure and the promotion of the area as a place to work and live.</p>				
<p>While the Wild Atlantic Way set out a vision for the continued evolution of the Wild Atlantic Way over a long period, the Wild Atlantic Way brand was intended to and became synonymous with great experiences of Ireland's Atlantic heritage, culture, landscapes and seascapes in a high-quality environment. In order to maintain those great experiences and to improve on the level of excellence experienced by the visitor, the challenge and opportunity in this case is to create new tourism experiences and to develop and improve the existing tourism experiences based on culture and heritage.</p>	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="667 443 730 510">O2</td> <td data-bbox="738 443 1445 510">Enhance & promote visitor experiences to the region to add new experiences based on heritage and culture</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2" data-bbox="667 517 1445 1010"> <p>The objective is to enhance & promote visitor experiences to the region and to add new experiences based on heritage and culture, to utilise the rich heritage in the area in terms of pilgrimages, geology, archaeology etc.</p> </td> </tr> </table>	O2	Enhance & promote visitor experiences to the region to add new experiences based on heritage and culture	<p>The objective is to enhance & promote visitor experiences to the region and to add new experiences based on heritage and culture, to utilise the rich heritage in the area in terms of pilgrimages, geology, archaeology etc.</p>	
O2	Enhance & promote visitor experiences to the region to add new experiences based on heritage and culture				
<p>The objective is to enhance & promote visitor experiences to the region and to add new experiences based on heritage and culture, to utilise the rich heritage in the area in terms of pilgrimages, geology, archaeology etc.</p>					
<p>One of the challenges in the region is the need for education and training relevant to local industry and tourism. This is a key factor in the regeneration of the region. Upskilling of the local population in many sectors is necessary and traditional skills in some sectors are in danger of fading away, being in the hands of older members of the population.</p>	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="667 1014 730 1059">O3</td> <td data-bbox="738 1014 1445 1059">Upskilling of local population</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2" data-bbox="667 1064 1445 1323"> <p>The objective is to upskill the local population in skills to make them more employable in local industry and in the tourism sector.</p> </td> </tr> </table>	O3	Upskilling of local population	<p>The objective is to upskill the local population in skills to make them more employable in local industry and in the tourism sector.</p>	
O3	Upskilling of local population				
<p>The objective is to upskill the local population in skills to make them more employable in local industry and in the tourism sector.</p>					

6.13.4 List of actions

Enhancement Action Code	Title of Enhancement action	Objective (please refer to section 1.2)
RM13.6	Development and upgrading of Digital Hub facilities	O1
RM13.7	Marketing campaign to promote remote working	O1
RM13.8	Training needs assessment of Cultural and Natural Heritage entrepreneurs and businesses	O3
RM13.9	Pilgrimage Route development	O2
RM13.10	Weaving Skills Programme	O1, O3
RM13.11	Promote geoheritage and geotourism through education programmes	O1, O2, O3
RM13.12	Digitalisation of Placenames Project	O2
RM13.13	Celebrations of the birth of St Colmcille (1500 years)	O2

RM13.14	Irish language courses targeted at businesses	01, 02, 03
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6.13.5 Operational programme

Code of the action	RM13.6
Title the action	Development and upgrading of Digital Hub facilities
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Landscape, Food
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature, Built Digital Heritage
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM16-3 Promoting the creation of new companies and jobs
Relevant RM/KFP involved	WestBIC
Brief description of the action	Development and upgrading of facilities for remote and hybrid working in one of the Rural Heritage Hubs (an opportunity for CNH start-ups and employees to move to a rural remote working facility).
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM 13.5 Údarás na Gaeltachta Strategic Plan 2018-2020
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The objective is to provide co-working, hot desking and unit spaces for cultural and heritage start-ups. It is also intended to make remote working facilities available for entrepreneurs and workers from rural areas to return to their place of origin from their urban work bases ultimately leading to increased employment in this rural area. In the context of Covid-19, ensure that the building is Covid-19 friendly and safe. The targets are to accommodate 26 users in 1 creative and innovation friendly environment and to provide 1 x high speed fibre line which will be 1 Gb enabled.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply for and drawdown funding for the development of appropriate workspace • Apply for Covid-19 funding to make the workspace safe for employees and customers. • Procure the necessary equipment, furniture etc following approval. • Ensure high speed fibre broadband is made available.
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	WestBIC through their digital hub, gteic@Cill Charthaigh, Údarás na Gaeltachta, AEC, Donegal Co Co
Beneficiaries	CNH Start -ups, remote workers
Timeframe	Jan 2021 – June 2021
Indicative costs	€60,000 already approved
Indicative funding sources	Grant aid from: DCC and AEC, matched with own funds

Code of the action	RM13.7
Title the action	Marketing campaign to promote remote working
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Landscape, food
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature, Built Digital Heritage
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM3-3 Definition of Marketing and Communications Strategies
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM3 Apulia (D.A.R.e)
Brief description of the action	Marketing campaign to promote remote working and the new opportunities to live in rural Ireland.
Previous RM action to	RM 13.5

enhance (if any)	Údarás na Gaeltachta Strategic Plan 2018-2020
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The objective is to promote remote working in the Digital Hub as well as promoting remote working ion the wider area and region. The targets are to launch a new website for the Digital Hub, to launch a social media campaign for the hub and to engage with a wider network of digital hubs to promote the entire region as a suitable location for remote working. An internet-based phone system will be commissioned when fibre broadband is installed to improve the offering to potential remote workers.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply for and drawdown funding for the marketing and VOIP system • Follow procurement procedures to source suppliers and equipment following approval • Develop new website and associated campaign/launch • Install VOIP system when high speed broadband becomes available • Engage with Digital Hub networks for promotion of region to remote workers • Promote the facility to target entrepreneurs, urban workers.
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	WestBIC through their digital hub, gteic@Cill Charthaigh, Údarás na Gaeltachta, AEC, Enterprise Ireland
Beneficiaries	CNH Start -ups, remote workers
Timeframe	Promotion to begin when restrictions are lifted. (July 2021 – Dec 2021)
Indicative costs	€10,000 approved
Indicative funding sources	Grant aid from: Enterprise Ireland at 80%. Balance of 20% from gteic@Cill Charthaigh

Code of the action	RM13.8
Title the action	Training Needs Assessment of Cultural & Natural Heritage (CNH) entrepreneurs, businesses, young people and adults
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Landscape, food
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature, Built Intangible – Knowledge and practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM4.2 Develop training courses to upskill Cultural & Natural Heritage entrepreneurs, businesses, young people and adults
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM4 Colombia (FCM)
Brief description of the action	Assess training needs of Cultural & Natural Heritage entrepreneurs, businesses, young people and adults and develop support programme. The plan is to assess the personal development needs of young people and adults as well as the needs of local employers and all industry including the tourism sector.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM 13.5 Údarás na Gaeltachta Strategic Plan 2018-2020
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	A Training Needs Analysis will be completed assessing the needs of young people and adults in the community. The skills needs of local enterprise, industry and tourism will also be assessed. The results will be analysed and the first support programme will be developed.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify organisation to carry out Training Needs Analysis on Cultural & Natural Heritage (CNH) start-ups, micro enterprises, young people and adults through tendering process • Agree Terms of Reference with appointed organisation • Complete Training Needs Analysis and publish results with relevant stakeholders,

	<p>primarily businesses, training providers and also to the general public and participants in the survey.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop draft support programme for individuals and businesses in conjunction with the appropriate stakeholders based on the results. The support programme will be likely to take place in 2022 as a separate and new action.
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	gteic@Cill Charthaigh, Údarás na Gaeltachta
Beneficiaries	CNH Start-ups, entrepreneurs, young people adults
Timeframe	July 2021 – Dec 2021
Indicative costs	€5,000 for Training Needs Analysis
Indicative funding sources	Údarás na Gaeltachta or Donegal Education and Training Board

Code of the action	RM13.9
Title the action	Pilgrimage Route development
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Landscape, Pilgrimage
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM 14.2 Develop resources and expand tourism (Camino de Santiago)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM1 (Camino de Santiago) and RM 14
Brief description of the action	Examine how existing pilgrimage route (Slí Colmcille / Bealach na Gaeltachta) can be developed further and promoted.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM 13.1 To set out a strategy and an implementation framework and programme for the sustainable implementation of the Wild Atlantic Way
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Improve the condition of existing pilgrimage routes (Turas Colmcille and Slí Colmcille) Promote pilgrimage routes
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Study to be carried out on existing pilgrimage route by Údarás na Gaeltachta employment scheme in conjunction with Paths and Trails Development officer when restrictions are lifted to identify where remedial work on route needs to take place. Remedial work plan to be developed on which sections of route are priority. Application to be made by Lár Chomhairle (who recently employed a full-time Development Officer) to Údarás na Gaeltachta for a small promotional funding budget (leaflets and online promotion). If approved the leaflets and online promotion will be managed by the Lár Chomhairle.
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	This will be led by Lár Chomhairle Paróiste GCC with support from Donegal County Council, Údarás na Gaeltachta and others.
Beneficiaries	Tourists, hill walkers, local population interested in hill walking
Timeframe	July 2021 – Dec 2021
Indicative costs	€1200 for promotional element. Remedial work to be carried out under employment scheme.
Indicative funding sources	Údarás na Gaeltachta

Code of the action	
RM13.10	
Title the action	Weaving Skills Programme
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Landscape / Arts and Festivals
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Traditional Craftmanship
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	n/a
Relevant RM/KFP involved	n/a
Brief description of the action	Provide facilities for a full-time traditional weaving programme which will help the revival of the traditional skill of weaving in an area with a very strong textiles traditions going back for over 100 years.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM 13.5 Údarás na Gaeltachta Strategic Plan 2018-2020
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The Donegal Education and Training Board (Donegal ETB), as part of their strategy to revive traditional skills and to pass them onto new generations, have been developing a Weaving Skills Programme for a number of years. They assessed four locations in South West Donegal for suitability to run such a training programme. Because of the rich textile and weaving heritage in Kilcar and the suitability of the training space offered at gteic@Cill Charthaigh by WestBIC, the gteic has been selected as the training facility now that the course is ready to roll out and that the accreditation has been approved. The target is to provide accredited training to 10 participants in the traditional skill of weaving through a full-time 6 month accredited practical weaving programme.
Specific activities	WestBIC through their digital hub, gteic@Cill Charthaigh will provide a 100 m2 unit, perfectly suitable for the weaving programme to Donegal ETB WestBIC will support Donegal ETB in the promotion of the weaving programme to suitable participants locally and further afield. WestBIC will also support Donegal ETB in general high profile promotion delivering the message that traditional skills such as weaving are being revived and will strengthen the textile industry in the area.
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	WestBIC through their digital hub, gteic@Cill Charthaigh and Donegal Education and Training Board (Donegal ETB).
Beneficiaries	Young people wishing to upskill in traditional weaving and textile industry locally. Employers seeking employees fully trained in weaving
Timeframe	July 2021 – Dec 2021.
Indicative costs	€10,000 for facilities
Indicative funding sources	Donegal Education and Training Board have approved funding for the facilities. The running of the course is a separate action in the control of the Donegal ETB.

Code of the action	
RM13.11	
Title the action	Promote geoheritage and geotourism through education programmes
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Social practices Rituals and festive events Digital Heritage
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	n/a
Relevant RM/KFP involved	n/a

Brief description of the action	Promote geoheritage and geotourism through education programmes in the context of a cultural activity holidays including printed and digital maps outlining sites of interest
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM 13.5 Údarás na Gaeltachta Strategic Plan 2018-2020
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Develop a new Oideas Gael course “Exploring our geoheritage” and recruit 20 participants for the course per year. Develop a printed map of local geosites of interest Develop a website with tourist information on geosites of interest
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete the content for the course with identified expert in this area. • Promote the new course with existing database of Oideas Gael students and through Oideas Gael channels. • Gather information for printed map and digital version on geosites.
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Oideas Gael (Cultural Activity Holiday Provider) are the main drivers of this action with support from Geological Survey Ireland and other stakeholders.
Beneficiaries	Visitors participating in course, local people interested in geoheritage, tourists interested in geoheritage
Timeframe	June 2021 – Dec 2021
Indicative costs	€10,000 approved
Indicative funding sources	Geoheritage Grant Scheme 2020/21 from Geological Survey Ireland

Code of the action	RM13.12
Title the action	Digitalisation of Placenames Project
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Social practices Rituals and festive events Digital Heritage
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM1.6 Digitalization of the pilgrimage - through websites, GIS maps, apps.
Relevant RM/KFP involved	n/a
Brief description of the action	Digitalisation of Placenames Project to include the placing of the 1990s collection made by Dan McGinley to be placed on digital map. Other placenames from the area to be added and other sources to be utilised.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM 13.5 Údarás na Gaeltachta Strategic Plan 2018-2020
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Placenames of the area to be collected digitally in one place using previous collections and identifying previously identified placenames that should be added. Raise awareness through 1 x event, 1 x launch and by collaborating with at least 2 schools. Template developed for this work for continuing this work into the future.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dan McGinley collection for Teelin and Glencolmcille to be added to the digital map • Utilise existing Donegal Co Co map and Seamus Mac Giolla Easbuig collections to add further information • Additional information from S Uí Néill collection to be used for meanings, translations etc

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Info to be gathered on placenames for other Caiseal, Meenaneary and Teelin by organising events and ensuring valuable information is not lost. • Event during heritage week in August 2021. • Launch in September 2021 of 1st version of map. • Collaborate with 2 local schools on the placenames project in October 2021. • Develop template for this work so that it can continue and evolve.
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Oideas Gael
Beneficiaries	Locals interested in placenames and associated history, folklore etc., children in local schools, tourists, historians.
Timeframe	Jan 2021 – Jan 2022
Indicative costs	€3,000
Indicative funding sources	Heritage Council.

Code of the action	RM13.13
Title the action	Celebrations of the birth of St Colmcille (1500 years)
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage / Arts & Festivals
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Social practices Rituals and festive events
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	n/a
Relevant RM/KFP involved	n/a
Brief description of the action	A series of celebrations to commemorate the birth of one of Ireland's three patron saints, St. Colmcille who resided in the area 1500 years ago. This is a small part of a year's activities during 2021 which recognise the importance and legacy of the 6th-century saint, not only for Derry and Donegal but for the island of Ireland, Scotland and across the world.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM13.5
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>The primary objective is to raise awareness of St Colmcille, and his work in Glencolmcille and the surrounding regions, locally and among potential visitors / pilgrims. This includes the local pilgrimages associated with St Colmcille including St Colmcille Pilgrimage and the longer St Colmcille Trail, both of which are referred to in a separate action. Both the drama production and the folklore collection will help to bring the character to life and raise the awareness further.</p> <p>The target is to raise awareness of the importance of Colmcille in the area and the associated Colmcille pilgrimage through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 x local drama production • 1 x folklore collection to be produced • 1 x map or brochure to be completed. <p>The promoters of this action, Lár Chomhairle have already initiated the work on gathering information from historians, tour guides and other people with expert knowledge on the saint.</p>
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drama to be produced and enacted about St. Colmcille (script already identified) • Folklore Collection to be produced and made available for sale in printed form and online. • Map or brochure of Turas Cholmcille (Colmcille Pilgrimage) to be produced / updated and made available in tourist offices, accommodation providers, shops, post offices.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The feasibility of a sculpture of Colmcille is also being assessed but is subject to funding availability.
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Lár Chomhairle Paróiste Gleann Cholm Cille (LCPGCC)
Beneficiaries	Locals, school children, tourists
Timeframe	Jun 2021 – Dec 2021
Indicative costs	€2,000
Indicative funding sources	Donegal County Council (Colmcille 1500 Grant Scheme)

Code of the action	RM13.14
Title the action	Irish language course targeted at businesses
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Landscape / Arts & Festivals
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Knowledge and practices, Oral traditions
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM13.5: Strategy to maintain, strengthen and develop a thriving native language speaking (Gaeltacht) community, defined by language and culture
Relevant RM/KFP involved	n/a
Brief description of the action	Irish language course targeted at businesses from beginners to rusty Irish speakers. This will strengthen the Irish language among the business community while also raising the profile of local businesses through Irish language media. It will also raise awareness of how a business can add value and attract business in a simple and cost-effective way by using the Irish language in signage, stationary etc.
Previous RM action to enhance (if any)	RM13.5
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>The objectives are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design 1 x beginner's course Design 1 x intermediate course Identify 1 x Irish teacher Train 10 individuals at each course level in Year 1 (to be incorporated into Language Plan for the region, 2020-2027)
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meeting to take place between Language Planning Officer, Oideas Gael (training provider) and Sliabh Liag Distillers (local SME) Design 2 Irish language courses for different levels of fluency The course will be promoted to local businesses as the content will reflect the language needs of the business community Run the courses Evaluate the courses using the existing Oideas Gael
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Oideas Gael, Language Planning Officer (LCPGCC) and Sliabh Liag Distillers
Beneficiaries	Local businesses
Timeframe	Jun 2021 – Nov 2021
Indicative costs	€1,000
Indicative funding sources	Language Plan for SW Donegal (2020-2027)

